

Deliverable D2.8

Cybersecurity compliance report

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Table 1. Project terms and acronyms

Acronym/term	Explanation
1+MG	The European 1 Million Genomes initiative
1+MG cohort datasets	Datasets that can be disclosed to users by the Genome EDIC as controller in accordance with the 1+MG data governance.
1+MG compliant datasets	Datasets that can be disclosed to users by 1+MG data holders as controller in accordance with the 1+MG data governance.
1+MG data governance	The rules and requirements for data inclusion, data access management and decision and data use in the Genome EDIC secondary use framework.
1+MG data holder	Organisation in a Genome EDIC member country that is controller for the disclosure of 1+MG compliant data to users, i.e., is responsible for the access decision.
1+MG data host	Organisation that physically holds the data that are made available in the Genome EDIC secondary use framework by the 1+MG data holder.
1+MG NCP	1+MG National Coordination Point, an entity within Genome EDIC member countries responsible that serves as the central contract for the secondary use of data from the respective country. These are also referred to as “nodes” within this document.
1+MG IT Infrastructure	IT environment on the central, national and local level, as applicable, that hosts data and metadata for the Genome EDIC secondary use framework and enables workflows through suitable tools or to the providers of such infrastructure. Responsibilities assigned refer to features that the respective IT infrastructure should provide or services that the provider of such IT infrastructure should offer.
B1MG	Beyond 1 Million Genomes
B1MG-GB	Beyond 1 Million Genomes Governing Board
CER	Critical Entities Resilience Directive (EU) 2022/2557
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act Regulation (EU) 2024/2847
Consortium	The B1MG Consortium, comprising the named legal entities
DA	Data Act Regulation (EU) 2023/2854
Data Provider	Organisation in a Genome EDIC member country that brings genomic and/or health data into the Genome EDIC’s secondary use framework to be made available according to the 1+MG data governance.
DGA	Data Governance Regulation (EU) 2022/868
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DoA	Description of Action
EDIC	European Digital Research Infrastructure
EDIW	European Digital Identity Wallet
EE	Essential entities (from NIS2)

EHDS	European Health Data Space
GA	Grant Agreement - The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the EC for the undertaking of the B1MGplus project
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679
GDI	European Genomic Data Infrastructure (Digital Europe project, also supporting the 1+MG initiative)
Genome EDIC	Central legal entity incorporating the 1+MG infrastructure
Genome EDIC secondary use framework	The framework set up to give cross-border access to genomic and health data in a harmonised fashion.
Genome EDIC member country	A country that has become a full member of the Genome EDIC. Genome EDIC member countries must have established a 1+MG NCP and a 1+MG IT infrastructure or have access to a 1+MG IT infrastructure.
GoE	Genome of Europe
IE	Important entities (from NIS2)
IEA	Interoperable Europe Act Regulation (EU) 2024/903
International body	For purpose of Commission Decision (EU)2022/248, Art.14(1)(d) for VAT exemption
International organisation	For purpose of Commission Decision (EU)2022/248, Art.14(1)(d)
NIS2	Network and information Security Directive (EU) 2022/2555
Nodes	Also called 1+MG National Coordination Point, an entity within Genome EDIC member countries responsible that serves as the central contract for the secondary use of data from the respective country.
ODD	Open Data Directive (EU) 2019/1024
OES	Operators of essential services (from NIS)
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
User	The individual that is seeking access to data in 1+MG
User Organisation	The legal entity under which the User is requesting access. These may even include commercial entities, including self-employed consultants.
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1. Executive Summary

The general objective of WP2 is to “provide input to the GDI Project and the Genome EDIC that is to be set up to support the EDIC in becoming operational. The work will provide the foundation (i.e. content creation) for the negotiations of member countries in the GDI Pillar I on the data governance and governance implementation, sustainability and business model as well as the input into the development of the IT infrastructure. The work will be limited to cover a minimum viable product that allows the Genome EDIC to become operational but not cover any future developments yet as these plans will be too volatile during the lifetime of the project and the provided funds are not sufficient to cover additional scenarios.”

B1MGplus work package 2 comprises the D2.8 Cybersecurity assessment report for the creation of the EDIC. In performing the assessment of the consequences of cybersecurity law on the setup of the Genomic EDIC’s infrastructure, D2.8 analyses the legal roles from various EU legislations and the corresponding cybersecurity duties for those roles that might apply to the Genome EDIC and or to the 1+MG NCP. It also offers an assessment of the consequences of cybersecurity law for both the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG National Coordination Points.

Work accomplished

This deliverable starts with an explanation of this legal form “EDIC”, its nature and boundaries with the 1+MG NCP (also referred to as “nodes”), which are the 1+MG National Coordination Points.

Then D2.8 explains at a basic level the structure and data flows that we expect from decentralised data governance on which we build the legal analysis. This explanation introduces cloud computing arrangements and digital sovereignty, which are two aspects of cybersecurity to be considered by the “1+MG IT Infrastructure” that do not directly relate to the legal roles and cybersecurity duties explored subsequently in Section 4, but they are fundamental to understanding cybersecurity of the larger IT environment.¹ We explain the important aspects of data interoperability to be used in the Special Processing Environments (“SPE”), which are required by European Health Data Space Regulation (“EHDS”) and the Data Governance Act (“DGA”) and will be part of the Genome SPE Network. Moving from more general cybersecurity analysis, we go into the specific EU laws.

In Section 4, following the methodology described in Section 3, we break down six EU laws related to cybersecurity in a tabular mapping exercise, each followed by commentary on their applicability to the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP. After the 6 tables, the deliverable touches on EU laws treating data governance, interoperability, and product security laws

¹ By “1+MG IT infrastructure” we refer to the “environment on the central, national and local level, as applicable, that hosts data and metadata for the Genome EDIC secondary use framework and enables workflows through suitable tools or to the providers of such infrastructure.” “1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework”, June 2025, main author R. Becker, contributions B. Rodrigues, T. Rasmussen.

specific to health, data, and medical devices which also contribute to confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data. We point out where there may be national variations or national implementations of the EU Directives that must be checked by each 1+MG NCP. We provide guidance on the impact that such a law could have on legal roles and cybersecurity duties, but each 1+MG NCP must check their national laws for applicability.

Lastly, we point to implementation guidance published by ENISA, the EU Agency for Cybersecurity that the consortium can consult for a better understanding for cybersecurity in the EU.

Conclusion

We highlight throughout our legal review the similarities of cybersecurity practices, (cyber)risk management measures and incident response rules that would be imposed in different legislations, like CER, NIS2, GDPR, EHDS, and CRA, to inform the consortium of the opportunity to consider these as best practices to adopt when creating their data governance plans and cybersecurity strategy. If and when these legislations apply to one or more 1+MG NCP, they will already be ready in their cybersecurity approach. The implementation will be more efficient, and the staff of the Genome and 1+MG NCP will be more responsive.

In Annex 1 we have created a table pairing roles in the laws and roles in the EDIC and 1+MG NCP, which has been compiled to aid understanding across the various legislation for comparison of terms. It can be helpful to flag to the consortium what traits within legal roles of the EDIC and/or 1+MG NCP might trigger actions under these cybersecurity laws going forward.

It is understood that roles within the Genome EDIC are not yet stable and they might change overtime. Also, for these reasons this deliverable aimed at producing results that remain valid even if these changes materialize. Thus, the mapping of the legal roles remains valid along with the policy consideration suggested to guide the entities participating in the EDIC in understanding the potential players' obligations for cybersecurity. Please note that this can overlap at times with data protection roles and duties.

This way both the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCPs need only to check under their respective applicable national law the legal roles they are in to identify their actual duties. Accordingly, even if there is a significant change in the data governance structure, both Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCPs (more in general entities participating in the EDIC) will need only to check under the relevant applicable national legislation whether they fall in one of the legal roles listed in Annex 1 and refer to the corresponding legal analysis above to kick start their cybersecurity compliance. It goes without saying that the table in Annex 1 cannot reflect the complexity of the analysis and the policy considerations included in the analysis contained in sections 4-7.

This assessment does not analyse technical aspects of cybersecurity standards, interoperability, technical documentation, product documentation or maintenance that might apply.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached, or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1 Supporting the Genome EDIC WG and the 1+MG Member States on the establishment of the EDIC by carrying out the field work required to generate high quality landscape and scoping documents necessary for the compliance framework beyond the legal creation of an EDIC. These documents will drive EDIC to become operational and offer compliant access to health and genomic data, covering legal, policy, quality and security aspects of data provision.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2 WP2 will analyse the EHDS Regulation and will seek close exchange with relevant projects and stakeholders to investigate the conditions for a participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure, to give recommendations on the alignment of its policies, tools, security measures and IT framework with the requirements of the EHDS.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3 WP3 will provide a framework of reference for genomics in healthcare that supports the decision-making process, facilitating the definition of mid and long term targets and the path for genomics implementation, incorporating the feedback received from B1MG and the 1+MG experts.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4 The project will map existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to whole genome sequencing and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare. Building on the collected best practices, and together with experts in the field, the project will develop decision trees to be tested in national settings to guide decision making related to genomics in healthcare. The long-term impact of the work is the scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare to support future prioritisation in healthcare, policy makers and decisions on investment in genomic medicine.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 5</p>	No

<p>Enhancing the 1+MG MLM for the implementation of genomics medicine in healthcare systems with updated domains and indicators, promoting its use and benchmarking by more healthcare systems. This will provide an homogeneous assessment framework that will foster the alignment of optimisation aims in healthcare systems across Europe, closing gaps, reducing asymmetries and ensuring a path towards equity of access to personalised medicine for all Europeans.</p>	
<p>Outcome 6 Expand the 1+MG Framework to fully define the 1+MG minimal metadata model, data standards, ontologies and quality criteria providing accessibility and maintenance, ensuring continuous alignment and support of 1+MG data use for research, innovation and policy making.</p>	<p>Yes</p>

3. Methods

3.1 Scope of D2.8:

B1MGplus work package 2 comprises the D2.8 Cybersecurity assessment report. D2.8 analyses cybersecurity duties of the EDIC as a separate legal entity. Therefore, this deliverable will start with an explanation of this legal form “EDIC”, its nature and boundaries. This EDIC explanation should help clarify why the focus of D2.8 is narrowed to the cybersecurity duties of the EDIC itself, and not to the national research entities who will participate as eventual members.

This assessment does not analyse other technical requirements related to standards, interoperability, technical documentation, standards, product documentation or maintenance that might apply. That level of detail is not necessary and would be speculative at this stage (M6) of the project.

In order to discuss what might be the cybersecurity duties for the various legal roles in the EDIC, an explanation of the EDIC as a legal entity is a useful starting point in Section 4.

3.2 Methodology

Use key terms from projects to narrow search for relevant EU laws requiring cybersecurity directly or indirectly (in 5 steps)

Step 1 Selection of key terms. The methodology to create D2.8 report started by creating a list of_key terms related to the 1+ Million Genomes initiative and its related projects of B1MG project, GDI, B1MGplus relevant to cybersecurity, so that the research would be relevant to the nature of the infrastructure, and that the search for relevant laws would be closely matched but also comprehensive. By “key terms” it is meant those words or phrases used to describe the digital (i.e., online) nature of the EDIC that relates to cybersecurity.

This methodology was designed to investigate the most likely applicable duties arising from EU law related to cybersecurity responsibility for the EDIC’s function. The higher-level goal of this investigation and analysis is to inform the project participants how to plan the EDIC’s legal responsibilities and set up the EDIC to design to meet the cybersecurity responsibilities from the earliest possible stage. This is in line with the initiative goals to “translate requirements for data quality, standards, technical infrastructure, and Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI) into technical specifications and implementation guidelines that capture European best practice.”²

Key terms come from the project documents. The most recent versions of documents (where available) were preferred to ensure an analysis based on the current terms used to describe the nature of the data infrastructure, roles, and duties. In addition to those listed specifically below, other internal documents used by Pillar 1 were consulted to streamline the key terms selection.

The table below is not an exhaustive list of documents reviewed, but a selection of the most useful and relevant documents that contained key terms helpful to highlight the digital aspects of the project.

Table 2. Project documents used as sources

Document title or description
1+MG Data Governance for Research Document to vote on the principal framework
1+MG ELSI WG meeting May 2025, “EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC” word document and 1+MG ELSI Working Group Meeting May 13, 2025 Slide deck
1+MG ELSI WG meeting July 8, 2025 slide deck
CNECT note for MS on 1+MG sustainability options - 20 March 2025 with comments added by the 1+MG Task Force EDIC Legal Basis
Collated Member States consultations on 1+MG sustainability options
“1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework”, June 2025, main author R. Becker, contributions B. Rodrigues, T. Rasmussen.
Declaration Of Cooperation, Towards access to at least 1 million sequenced genomes
Deliverable D3.3, Infrastructure status report and updated roadmap, Genomic Data Infrastructure, Grant agreement no. 101081813
Deliverable D6.6, Report outlining the recommendations on data curation and ELSI compliance, Genomic Data Infrastructure, Grant agreement no. 101081813
Explanatory note: FEGA as short term-option for 1+MG sustainability
Grant Agreement no. 101194865 — B1MGplus
Legal sustainability options for the 1+ Million Genomes’ data infrastructure in the European Union by 2022

² <https://b1mg-project.eu/>, accessed 09/06/2025.

Preparatory document for the GDI Pillar I GOV

Slide deck “B1MGplus Proposal” from 8 March 2024 by ELIXIR

Slide deck DPbDD workshop 1MG internal May 2024

Template table for Member States consultations on 1+MG sustainability options

Towards a Proof of Concept of Federated Infrastructure for the EU 1+Million Genomes Initiative

Websites <https://b1mg-project.eu/>, <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

While reviewing the documents, the following key terms were selected based on their “digital” connection to health research in some way:

Table 3. Key terms and phrases

Access credentials	Decentralized data governance	Infrastructure
Authorized participant	Digital decade	Integrity
Availability	Digital Decade Policy Programme	Interoperability
Central interface	Digital health services	IOT, Medical IOT
Centralized data governance	Digital signature	Legislative framework
Cloud	EDIC	National nodes
Confidentiality	EHDS	Organisational safeguards
Consent	EHDS infrastructure	Personal health data
Controller	Electronic health data	Personalized medicine
Controllershship	Electronic health record	Public health
Cross-border	EU laws by name	Qualified and trustworthy users
Data curation	Federated architecture	Re-use of data
Data-driven	Federated data spaces	Research
Data flows	Genomic health data	Secondary use
Data holders	Genome initiatives	Secure, security, cybersecurity
Data infrastructure	Governance	Sensitive (personal) data
Data permit	Harmonized data governance	Software / hardware
Data pool	Health data	Special categories of data
Data processing	Health data access body	Technical safeguards
Data providers	healthdata@EU	Technical security measures
Data quality	ICT (components, products, services)	Transmission of data
Data spaces		Users
Data subjects		

Step 2. Selection of laws. This selection of laws was made based on the likelihood of their relevance based on key terms used and discussed in the project documents and common view of what the decentralized infrastructure is expected to become.

The table below lists the selection of EU laws that have been reviewed for cybersecurity duties, directly or indirectly. Those in green have an analysis in separate tables for comparison of roles as they are considered to date the most important for a cybersecurity analysis for the EDIC. Please note that the AI Act was considered and preliminary analysed, yet it has not been selected for analysis. No EDIC or project documents discuss the adoption of AI at this stage. Moreover, upon a preliminary analysis in the selection phase it has been ascertained that cybersecurity requirements do not change in the face of using AI based on the laws we analyzed. A further analysis of the AI Act would have been too speculative and out of scope of D2.8.

Table 4. Legislation reviewed

Legislation	Date of Legislation
Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 (eIDAS Regulation)	23 July 2014
Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR)	27 April 2016
Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 (Free Flow of Non-Personal Data)	14 November 2018
Regulation (EU) 2019/881 (Cybersecurity Act)	17 April 2019
Regulation (EU) 2021/694 (Digital Europe Programme)	29 April 2021
Regulation (EU) 2022/868 (Data Governance Act)	30 May 2022
Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 (Digital Markets Act)	14 September 2022
Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 (Digital Services Act)	19 October 2022
Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (NIS2 Directive)	14 December 2022
Directive (EU) 2022/2557 (Resilience of Critical Entities)	14 December 2022
Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (Data Act)	13 December 2023
Regulation (EU) 2024/903 (Interoperable Europe Act)	13 March 2024
Regulation (EU) 2024/1183 (European Digital Identity Framework)	11 April 2024
Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (Cyber Resilience Act)	23 October 2024
Regulation (EU) 2025/38 (Cyber Solidarity Act)	19 December 2024
Regulation (EU) 2025/327 (European Health Data Space)	11 February 2025

Step 3. Review laws for relevance to key terms, highlight roles for cybersecurity duties.

In this refined selection of cybersecurity-focused laws, the various legal roles as described within the legislation, such as ‘data processor’ or ‘data holder’ were checked across similar

descriptions in legislation for consistency and completeness. Through this step a sort of ‘bill of legal actors’ from EU cybersecurity law was obtained.

Step 4. The roles described in those laws were divided into two categories, in or outside the EDIC.

The roles can be essentially categorized by which roles might belong to actors within the IT infrastructure and those which could not be because they are not part of the EDIC or the 1+MG NCP to the extent they are not an integral part of the EDIC. This allows for a smaller, more relevant selection of legal roles with corresponding cybersecurity duties to be created. This way, the legal analysis of this deliverable does not focus unnecessarily on responsibilities that are assigned to actors outside of the EDIC.

It is assumed at this early point that these roles are not rigid definitions but could change. Considering the possible stakeholders help the EDIC and nodes plan for cybersecurity duties based around these potential roles as they might be viewed through EU legislation.

Table 5. Infrastructure stakeholders

Role in Infrastructure ³

1+MG Central Coordination (1+MG CC)

Support staff in the 1+MG EDIC; the 1+MG CC serves as a one-stop-shop for users.

1+MG Data Access Committee (1+MG DAC)

Data Access Committee, which may include several domain-specific sub-committees, provided by 1+MG that receives and reviews access requests and moderates consensus discussions on access requests where necessary.

1+MG data host

- a.) Organisation that physically holds the data that are made available in the Genome EDIC secondary use framework by the 1+MG data holder.
- b.) Entity holding 1+MG compliant data or 1+MG cohort datasets in 1+MG compliant IT infrastructure

1+MG data holders

National entities who have legal responsibility for data disclosure and therefore are controller for the disclosure. These entities will make the access decisions and have legal agreements with data users.⁴ “1+MG data holders can decide on the choice of 1+MG SPE. This means the decision whether or not data are made available also in SPEs outside the country is now in the first place with the 1+MG data holder as controller unless the 1+MG member countries decide to regulate this decision on the national level. [Data holders] assume responsibility for that choice, i.e. they become liable for the data protection compliance of the SPE that they impose on the user organisation.

³ Some roles and definitions are from “1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework”, June 2025, main author R. Becker, contributions B. Rodrigues, T. Rasmussen. See also Table 1 for a more complete list of project entities. Other roles are pulled from various project documents, and do not constitute an exhaustive list of possible infrastructure stakeholders.

⁴ Ibid. “Data holder” here indicates the legal responsibility, it does not require the entity actually physically holds the dataset. In addition, some data providers or entire countries may still prefer a transfer of controllership for the disclosure to the Genome EDIC.”

[Data holders] assume responsibility for guaranteeing the archiving of data and the availability for reproducibility.”⁵

1+MG IT infrastructure

Refers to the IT environment on the central, national, and local level, as applicable, that hosts data and metadata for the Genome EDIC secondary use framework and enables workflows through suitable tools or to the providers of such infrastructure. Responsibilities assigned refer to features that the respective IT infrastructure should provide or services that the provider of such IT infrastructure should offer.

1+MG National Coordination Point (1+MG NCP)

National node within Member Countries responsible for coordinating access requests and providing information to national stakeholders. Confirms the compliance of data before they are introduced into the data catalogue.⁶

Data provider

Institutions with the right to grant or refuse access to certain genomic and health-related data. In this case, the legal entity that has brought genomic and/or health data into the 1+MG legal entity. Data provider performs the data protection impact assessment (DPIA) and obtains ethics approvals for data inclusion and is the interface to the data subjects for information and consent around data inclusion. Data provider is responsible for data curation and characterisation.⁷

Data subject

Natural person whose data is requested in an access request.

FEGA node

May or may not be 1+MG data host depending on whether it complies with 1+MG IT infrastructure requirements and holds data that are made available through 1+MG. See ‘1+MG data host.’

1+MG Genome Legal Entity (EDIC)

Central legal entity incorporating the 1+MG infrastructure. It is established through a Commission Implementing Decision as a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium implementing the multi-country project based on the 1+MG Declaration.

Central coordinating body, responsible, based on member countries’ decisions, for defining the common data governance, setting minimum data quality risk and compliance standards, and operating the central user portal and a central Data Access Committee (DAC) to ensure consistency and efficiency⁸.

Genome EDIC member country

A country that has become a full member of the Genome EDIC. Genome EDIC member countries must have established a 1+MG NCP and a 1+MG IT infrastructure or have access to a 1+MG IT infrastructure.

Permit authority

Entity competent by law to approve data access requests for secondary use in a country. A Permit Authority can be an ethics review committee, a data protection authority, or a body with a dedicated mandate to decide on secondary use of genomic and/or health data, such as a genome centre or later a health data access body (HDAB) in the EHDS.

SPE network

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Updated from slide deck from July 8, 2025 meeting of 1+MG ELSI WG

⁷ From slide deck from July 8, 2025 meeting of 1+MG ELSI WG

⁸ Ibid.

Genome EDIC's network of Secure Processing Environments⁹
See also above "1+MG data holders" for interaction with SPEs.

SPE providers

"1+MG SPE providers must be able to realise the data use environment for and the ingestion of external high value externally governed data in 1+MG SPEs for the user's projects, also independent of 1+MG governed data."¹⁰

User (in this phase, the user has the status of a requester)

The individual that is seeking access to data in 1+MG SPEs.

User Organisation

The legal entity under which the User is requesting access. User Organisations are expected to be either policy makers in the public sector or entities that support public policy making. These may even include commercial entities, including self-employed consultants.

Step 5. Evaluate the roles that potentially have cybersecurity responsibilities.

The roles of actors as described in this set of cybersecurity legislation were analysed and matched based on their traits to the expected roles regarding data processing and operation of the 1+MG IT Infrastructure as envisaged. The roles as described in the legislation set were compared with the roles as described in the selection of project documents, websites, and meetings attended (listed in Table 2, "Document title or description") and the overlaps and gaps of terms were noted.

Based on the above stated parameters, the output of this legal cybersecurity analysis is summarized in the last table in the Conclusion, and there is also "Annex 1", designed to guide the entities participating in the EDIC preparation in understanding the potential players' obligations for cybersecurity. This can overlap at times with data protection roles and duties.

Where "grey areas" of legal responsibility for cybersecurity in a digital health infrastructure emerged, we cast our net a bit wider to bring in cybersecurity guidelines, cloud "code of conduct" and scholarly commentary but keeping the focus on *cybersecurity* legal roles and responsibilities of the EDIC and 1+MG NCP.

Since many of these legislations are figuratively in their infancy, there is little case law and guidance by EU authorities at this stage. We point out implementation guidelines from ENISA where they are relevant. We suggest using the similarities among the legislative requirements on cybersecurity as the starting point for a comprehensive cybersecurity strategy for the Genome EDIC to adopt that will put it and the nodes in a good position to be prepared to quickly adapt as necessary to cybersecurity regulations and best practices, as seen in the various EU laws that we review. This assessment is to help prepare the infrastructure to become an EDIC and develop its data governance across the 1+MG NCP, at

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid.

this M6 of the project, and to inform the drafting of the EDIC statutes and operational rules over the next several months.

4. Description of work accomplished

Per the description in the Grant agreement, “B1MGplus aims to support the scale up and sustainability of 1+MG by supporting Member States’ to create a federated European genomics data infrastructure based on a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC).¹¹ More specifically, WP2 includes the identification and mapping of the cybersecurity compliance needs for the infrastructure. This deliverable aims to explain the possible cybersecurity duties coming from EU regulation that the Genome EDIC should be aware of in its planning phase.

4.1 The structure of Section 4

The **first half** of Section 4 starts with an analysis of the Digital Decade Decision (EU)2022/2481 that created the EDIC, then looks at the terms and stakeholders that have been defined so far in this project and in previous related projects, covers hypotheses and assumptions about the traits of the 1+MG IT infrastructure in some provided details and more generally about cloud infrastructure that should be considered in planning a cybersecurity strategy.

The **second half** of Section 4 explains the legal analysis we have conducted. It goes through 6 EU legislations on cybersecurity, with details organized into tables, and **legal analysis below each table**. After the 6 tables are presented, there are additional laws considered at a more cursory level of detail, for completeness of the cybersecurity duty analysis. Lastly, we cover other broader aspects on legal analysis of cybersecurity duties in a European context, including some ENISA guidance on cybersecurity measures.

4.2 Research on the expected nature of Genome EDIC

4.2.1 EDIC is a new legal form presented in the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030

In December 2022, the Decision establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 was enacted, and with it the framework for multi-country projects and the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium was created as legal form.¹²

The “European Digital Infrastructure Consortium” (EDIC) is an instrument made available to Member States to speed up and simplify the setup and implementation of multi-country projects.¹³ Essentially, it is a modified European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC),

¹¹ Grant Agreement no. 101194865 B1MGplus, Annex 1, Description of the Action

¹² Decision (EU) 2022/2481

¹³ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Art. 12, 13; see also <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/edic>

but one advantage is that the EDIC allows membership to “entities other than Member States, third countries, international organisations of European interest, and public or private entities.”¹⁴

In order to establish a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC), at least three founding member states must submit an application to the Commission requesting to be acknowledged as an EDIC.¹⁵ The Commission’s decision to grant the request is made in consultation with the Digital Decade Policy Programme Committee, and is subject to the requirements outlined in the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030.¹⁶ The applicants must establish its governance structure and operational rules in its statutes, which are to be submitted with the application.¹⁷

The Commission, if it approves the application, will issue an implementing decision creating the EDIC.¹⁸ The legal seat of the EDIC will be in one of the Member States, as specified in the statutes, and the other locations are in national nodes.¹⁹

In each Member State the EDICs shall have the “most extensive legal capacity accorded to legal entities under the law of that Member State. They may, in particular, acquire, own and dispose of movable, immovable and intellectual property, conclude contracts and be a party to legal proceedings.”²⁰

It is for the host Member State to determine if the EDIC meets the requirements for recognition as an “international body”²¹ and/or as “an international organisation.”²²

Once an EDIC is recognized as an international organisation, it may be eligible for VAT and excise duty exemptions on goods or services.²³

4.2.2 Analysis of the initiative, projects, stakeholders, and terms for the 1+MG IT infrastructure

To put into context the work done in this deliverable, we first explain the system goals of the 1+MG IT Infrastructure. The project started as the 1+MG initiative in 2018 based on the Declaration of Cooperation signed by 13 countries, which aims at making genomic and health data available for secondary use in a harmonised way, ensuring distributed,

¹⁴ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Art. 15(4)

¹⁵ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Art. 15(1)

¹⁶ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Art. 14(2)

¹⁷ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Art. 14(1)(b), 16 (3); for the minimum contents of the EDIC statutes, see Art. 17(1)

¹⁸ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Art. 14(3)(a), “The EDIC shall have legal personality from the date of entry into force of the relevant Commission decision issued pursuant to Art 14(3)(a)”, Art 13 (3).

¹⁹ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Art. 13 (5)

²⁰ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Art. 13(4)

²¹ As referred to in Council Directive 2006/112/EC Art. 143, point (g), and Art. 151(1), point (b), on the common system of value added tax and exemptions in some cases.

²² As referred to in Council Directive 2008/118/EC Art. 12(1), point (b), related to the exemption of excise duty for international organizations.

²³ Decision (EU) 2022/2481, Rec. 45.

authorized and secure access to national and regional banks of genetic and other relevant data.²⁴

This harmonization goal is meant to cover both the data standards and the governance of how data can be accessed.²⁵ The development of secure federated IT infrastructure (1+MG IT infrastructure) and tools will enable cross-border sharing and analysis of genetic and other datasets via this federated infrastructure, but the genomic data itself is planned to stay within national borders.²⁶ This is referred to as the “decentralised model” where controllership of the data disclosure will stay at a national level.²⁷

In this model, the Genome EDIC will provide recommendations on data governance and will coordinate its harmonised implementation.²⁸ In a federated architecture, a cross-border transmission of data to a data pool is avoided, therefore mitigating legal challenges in several Member States.²⁹ In this way, data remains at the source (in a national node) and will be accessed there through a data infrastructure able to discover the right dataset and enable federated analysis.³⁰

Secondary use of health data in 1+MG IT infrastructure should not be limited to research but also be possible for healthcare (e.g., healthcare professionals consulting other patients’ data for diagnosing or treating their own patients), or for policy development and health care management.³¹ This data governance framework should open the way for European health and related data processing in compliance with the applicable EU legal framework with data privacy guaranteed, with specific reference to the GDPR and the EHDS.³²

The initiative has been fostered by a series of EU funded projects:³³

- B1MG project about designing the implementation of the 1+MG initiative as a cross-border genomic data infrastructure.³⁴

²⁴ Declaration Of Cooperation, Towards access to at least 1 million sequenced genomes in the European Union by 2022, 10 April 2018 (“Declaration of Cooperation”). See also <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>, see contextual explanation here: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

²⁵ Declaration of Cooperation

²⁶ “Preparatory document for the GDI Pillar I GOV vote via written procedure with deadline 30th May 2025”, from “European Genomic Data Infrastructure” project document, created by GDI Project Coordinator.

²⁷ Preparatory document for the GDI Pillar I GOV vote via written procedure with deadline 30th May 2025”, from “European Genomic Data Infrastructure” project document, created by GDI Project Coordinator, from “Definitions: Decentralized model”.

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ CNECT note for MS on 1+MG sustainability options - 20 March 2025 with comments added by the 1+MG Task Force EDIC Legal Basis, Task Force EDIC Legal Basis. (“CNECT note”)

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Ibid. See Sec. 4 “Legal environment.”

³³ See <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/> for a brief introduction on each of these projects.

³⁴ <https://b1mg-project.eu/about/>

- Genomic Data Infrastructure is about the deployment of the technical infrastructure and making it sustainable.³⁵ GDI Pillar II will design the implementation of the data governance through local, national, and central tools in the IT infrastructure.³⁶
- Genome of Europe (GoE) will provide B1MG infrastructure with a data pool to create reference genomes for the European population and should be made available through the EDIC by 2028 when the GoE project ends.³⁷
- B1MGplus to which this deliverable belongs is a coordination and support action to sustain the creation of the Genome EDIC.

To aid the contextual explanation, we include two graphics below to visualize the various projects, functions, and timelines:

Figure 1 1+MG initiative implementation projects.

Support to the implementation of the 1+MG 2023–2027 roadmap

This project aims to advance the implementation of the 1+MG 2023–2027 roadmap² (Figure 2) by addressing specific requirements outlined in the call text (the currently underfunded areas of the roadmap) and delivering or supporting the five implementation tracks of the 1+MG 2023-27 roadmap.

Fig 1: From Grant Agreement, no. 101194865 B1MGplus, Annex 1, Description of the Action

³⁵ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

³⁶ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/about/how-organised>, “Pillar II works on incrementally increasing the interoperability of technical services and readiness levels of European, national and regional data hubs.”

³⁷ CNECT note, “This dataset based on a representative sample of 100.000 European citizens should be made available through the 1+MG infrastructure at the end of the GoE project in 2028.”

1+MG roadmap

Fig. 2: Implementation of the Declaration: the 1+MG roadmap
From: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

4.2.3 Project timeline and structure for the Genome EDIC

Next, we cover three important terms from the projects that are necessary to know when thinking about how legislations might apply, including applying in terms of their timeline and sustainability. For example, how do legal roles apply during the interim period of sustainability for the Genome EDIC or how might they change in the longer term, when we expect implementation regulations to be published and implemented in full? These questions will make more sense in Section 4 when discussing newer legislations.

The concept of “decentralized model” is also important to think of how parts of the infrastructure could fall under certain legislations, and other parts, are not within their scope. This is critical for the 1+MG NCP to digest so that each will do its own legal research for national laws, taking into consideration how each node functions.

- Long-term sustainability “means that once implemented an option has the ability to remain feasible over time, including well into the future.”³⁸
- Interim sustainability “means that once implemented the option will be feasible for a limited period of time and in any case until an option that has long-term sustainability is implemented.”³⁹
- Decentralised model “means that controllership of the data disclosure stays at national level.⁴⁰ The Genome EDIC creates the rules on data governance and coordinates its harmonised implementation⁴¹. While the EDIC is not yet in place, coordination and definition of the data governance can be agreed and implemented

³⁸ From the document “Member States consultations on 1+MG sustainability options” produced by European Genomic Data Infrastructure.

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Ibid.

through the GDI and B1MGplus projects.” See the table on “Stakeholders” for more definitions on roles in the decentralized model.

4.2.4 Expected data governance within the 1+MG IT infrastructure

The most expected option to be implemented, to date, is a setup of **Decentralised Infrastructure** where the Controllershship will be executed at the national level and exercised through EHDS eventually.⁴² In order to understand what that means for data flows, we provide an overview of infrastructure functions and key stakeholders that are expected to eventually be in place (see Table 5. Infrastructure stakeholders).⁴³

This decentralized structure serves the original aims of the 1+MG initiative, which is “to establish the cross-border sharing of genomic and health data for secondary use in a harmonised fashion.”⁴⁴

This deliverable is based on assumptions about the hypothetical function of the 1+MG IT Infrastructure.⁴⁵ The extent to which the tools and structures for service delivery should be independent of each other or interoperable with each other or reusable / identical for both EHDS and 1+MG is not yet known.⁴⁶ Taking into account this rather large open point, the cybersecurity analysis is limited to what can be reasonably expected of a digital infrastructure used to host and support the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCPs in member states.

The subsequent section discusses the **common traits in cloud service arrangements** so that the cybersecurity implications can be better understood where the EU legislations pertaining to cybersecurity requirements will be explained in connection with cloud technology in a decentralized digital infrastructure before the full implementation of the EHDS and in transition to becoming an eventual Authorised Participant.⁴⁷ Cloud computing is ubiquitous, and we find it an element of cybersecurity that should be addressed in any digital environment.

4.2.5 Hypothesis on use of cloud by the infrastructure

One of the virtues of cloud is its accessibility by multiple entities (nodes, data providers) in multiple locations (different nodes) and jurisdictions (in national entities, across EU borders,

⁴² from 1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework.

⁴³ Two project documents were primarily relied on for this understanding: “1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework” and “Overview of expected implications of the sustainability vote for the short-term implementation, June 2025.”

⁴⁴ Overview of expected implications of the sustainability vote for the short-term implementation, June 2025.

⁴⁵ We base our description on the most recent document available “1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework.”

⁴⁶ On integration with EHDS see “1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework.”

⁴⁷ “The current understanding is that 1+MG would qualify as an authorised participant under said Regulation acting independent of individual countries and their HDABs.” From 1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework. See the EHDS table below for fuller explanation on roles and duties pertaining to the 1+MG NCP and Genome EDIC.

from third countries).⁴⁸ How cybersecurity responsibility can shift between different actors who can access the cloud will need to be understood to accurately map legal obligations. For now, **the cloud layers can only be surmised and the legal analysis for this deliverable prepared by M6 was conducted based on common cloud service offerings.** How legal responsibility based on these standard variations for the actual set up between the provider, customer and end-user would need to be clarified. In any case, for the more precise legal and compliance understanding, the answers would be based on the analysis of the exact service and components concerned.⁴⁹ It is enough to mention for our purposes here that cloud layers are part of the technology stack in a digital environment, and cybersecurity’s goal of confidentiality, integrity, availability must include these.

Defining cloud computing service.

Under Directive (EU) 2022/2555, (‘NIS2’), ‘cloud computing service’ is defined as a digital service that enables on-demand administration and broad remote access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable computing resources, including where such resources are distributed across several locations.⁵⁰

This cloud model is composed of five essential characteristics, three service models, and four deployment models.⁵¹ As we review this section it can be helpful to keep in mind what would be the needs of a decentralized data infrastructure for genomic data storage, processing and exchange between nodes. We cover at high level here below five common characteristics of cloud, to give a general, adaptable baseline explanation.⁵²

Five characteristics of Cloud:

On-demand self-service	A consumer can unilaterally provision computing capabilities as needed automatically.
Broad network access	Capabilities are available over the network and accessed through standard mechanisms that promote use by heterogeneous thin or thick client platforms (e.g., mobile phones, tablets, laptops, and workstations).
Resource pooling	The provider’s computing resources are pooled to serve multiple consumers using a multi-tenant model, with different physical and virtual resources dynamically assigned and

⁴⁸ Bayan H. Banimfreg, “A comprehensive review and conceptual framework for cloud computing adoption in bioinformatics” *Healthcare Analytics* 3 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.health.2023.100190>.

⁴⁹ W Kuan Hon, Christopher Millard, and Jatinder Singh, *Control, Security, and Risk in the Cloud*. In: *Cloud Computing Law*. Second Edition. Oxford University Press. 2021. DOI: 10.1093/oso/9780198716662.003.0002.

⁵⁰ NIS2 Art. 6(30)

⁵¹ (Mell and Grance 2011). This cloud paradigm is in line with ISO ISO/IEC 19086-1:2016 (Information technology — Cloud computing — Service level agreement (SLA) framework) and also ISO/IEC 27017:2015 (Information technology — Security techniques — Code of practice for information security controls based on ISO/IEC 27002 for cloud services). To compare to another major industry standard, see NIST’s definition of cloud computing: NIST Special Publication 500-322 on DRAFT - Evaluation of Cloud Computing Services Based on NIST 800-145.”

⁵² (Mell and Grance 2011), for a more detailed discussion of these traits deployed in cloud-based healthcare, see (Banimfreg 2023).

reassigned according to consumer demand. There is a sense of location independence in that the customer generally has no control or knowledge over the exact location of the provided resources but may be able to specify location at a higher level of abstraction (e.g., country, state, or datacenter). Examples of resources include storage, processing, memory, and network bandwidth.

Rapid elasticity

Capabilities can be elastically provisioned and released, in some cases automatically, to scale rapidly outward and inward commensurate with demand.

Measured service

Cloud systems automatically control and optimize resource use by leveraging a metering capability at some level of abstraction appropriate to the type of service (e.g., storage, processing, bandwidth, and active user accounts). Resource usage can be monitored, controlled, and reported, providing transparency for both the provider and consumer of the utilized service.

Cloud service providers can offer three models of services: Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), or it can offer Software as a Service (SaaS). It is assumed that all three of these models of services *could be used* within the 1+MG IT infrastructure. Since however, no details are known about the platforms or data governance models to be created, and certainly not any specific types of software to be created or used, we will point to the *infrastructure as a Service* (IaaS) for an example of our cybersecurity legal analysis of duties because it offers a common starting point for service layers built on top which may be managed by other entities/components or nodes. It is the lowest part of the technological stack of the three services, figuratively.

There may be points where there is a shared responsibility for cybersecurity between the cloud service provider of the infrastructure, and the user and end user who rely on it.⁵³ The cloud customer may use its own platforms or software from other providers to be hosted on the infrastructure or may create platforms or software in-house.

Regarding data location, both GDPR and rules on cloud sovereignty may bring up legal factors which need to be taken into account regarding “where” data is stored.⁵⁴ These questions of storage and access to the data would each be specific cases based on service

⁵³ EU Data Protection Code of Conduct for Cloud Service Providers, December 2020, <https://eucoc.cloud>, Accessed 23 March 2025; “What is the Shared Responsibility Model in the Cloud?” <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/blog/2024/01/25/what-is-the-shared-responsibility-model-in-the-cloud>, Accessed 05 June 2025; CISPE Data Protection Code of Conduct, 9 February 2021 (*n.b.* CISPE stands for “Cloud Infrastructure Services Providers in Europe”).

⁵⁴ (Michels et al. 2024) This article discusses the impact of data location and privacy requirements for US based cloud providers like AWS, Google or Azure servicing EU based clients.

agreements that would need to be analysed to better grasp specific responsibilities of the Genome EDIC.⁵⁵

Again, here we seek to provide an understanding of at least the basic service arrangements between parties who may share responsibility. For this reason, we cover next which legal roles in the “deployment type” are in IaaS to imagine who could have cybersecurity responsibilities of the providers and users.

Cloud can be deployed in four types:

- Private cloud** This is for exclusive use by a single organization comprising multiple consumers (e.g., business units). It may be owned, managed, and operated by the organization, a third party, or some combination of them, and it may exist on or off premises.
- Community cloud** This is for exclusive use by a specific community of consumers from organizations that have shared concerns (e.g., mission, security requirements, policy, and compliance considerations). It may be owned, managed, and operated by one or more of the organizations in the community, a third party, or a combination of them, and it may exist on or off premises.
- Public cloud** This is for open use by the general public. It may be owned, managed, and operated by a business, academic, or government organization, or a combination of them. It exists on the premises of the cloud provider.
- Hybrid cloud** This is a composition of two or more distinct cloud infrastructures (private, community, or public) that remain unique entities but are bound together by standardized or proprietary technology that enables data and application portability (e.g., cloud bursting for load balancing between clouds).

Cloud can be built in **layers of services**, which refers to the possibility of one cloud service being built on top of another.⁵⁶ Also known as “cloud infrastructure levels”, these layers are “related to cybersecurity, both within cybersecurity products and services and by means of threats targeting those infrastructure levels.”⁵⁷ To aid the understanding of legal duties between roles for cybersecurity that might arise in the infrastructure, we set out the cloud levels here:

- Data level** Represents the data household of cloud computing, with both stored data and data in transit;
- Application level** Represents installed applications using the cloud computing resources (hardware and software);

⁵⁵ Ibid.

⁵⁶ (Kuan Hon, Millard, and Singh 2021), EU Data Protection Code of Conduct for Cloud Service Providers, December 2020, <https://eucoc.cloud>,

⁵⁷ ENISA Cloud Cybersecurity Market Report, March 2023

Network level	Represents the network elements/service used by the cloud computing node, including security elements responsible for the network protection;
Host level	Represents all elements supporting the virtualisation functions, such as the virtual server, virtual machines, and the hypervisor. ⁵⁸

ENISA's 2023 report describes the "cloud ecosystem" as a "mix of technology, operational and organisational entities that make up the entire service provisioning chain and cover both supply and demand."⁵⁹ This ecosystem is made up of "different cloud service categories, cloud deployment models, cloud capability types and cybersecurity-related services, functions and capabilities. *Roles and relationships between stakeholders on the supply and demand sides are the most important part to define an ecosystem, together with specific resources, requirements and issues for certain organisations or users.*"⁶⁰

It will be important for the designers of the 1+MG IT infrastructure, the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP to understand that services, deployment types, and infrastructure levels or layers are basic architectural arrangements and could be provided *by different entities*. These arrangements are governed in lengthy and complex Terms of Services by each cloud provider and are important to understand in terms of their effect on legal liability for cybersecurity, especially when there are conflicts potentially between the contract terms from different service providers. For the contractual duties, it would likely follow the model of shared responsibility between the parties as set out in the contracts. It is worth mentioning here though to raise awareness that cybersecurity responsibility can come from both contracts and regulation.⁶¹

Although our goal in this deliverable is to better understand cybersecurity responsibility coming from EU regulations, we cannot ignore that contractual liability between 1+MG IT infrastructure and its contracting parties will need to be considered. Now we look to another issue on cloud supply that was mentioned briefly above, i.e., digital sovereignty.

Cloud digital sovereignty in the design of 1+MG IT infrastructure

Cloud digital sovereignty is raised here as an early issue to consider for the creation and/or interaction of the 1+MG IT infrastructure. At the very least, we raise awareness for the consortium to consider how it will contract for the use of cloud services. This aspect looks at which entities (public or private, national or international) will or even can provide cloud infrastructure and what difference that makes for cybersecurity's triad: confidentiality, integrity, and availability.

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Ibid.

⁶¹ See cloud cybersecurity practices updated in <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/>

It is also important to stress that national legislations (applicable to the 1+MG NCPs) and the law of the chair site most probably will have specific cybersecurity legal rules to be applied for cybersecurity well beyond the implementation of EU legislations, within the margins of manoeuvring offered to member states. For instance, public entities might be bound to specific cloud providers according to their classification in the given national state even if NIS2, for example, would not apply to these entities.

Member states are creating their own national clouds for public administrations.⁶² The EU, as part of its Digital Strategy, is planning to publish the “EU Cloud Rulebook” and also guidance on public procurement of data processing services that should guide member states and the various entities in the Genome EDIC further.⁶³ This Rulebook will be a “single European framework” on binding and non-binding rules for cloud service users and providers in Europe.⁶⁴ This will be important for the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP to align with when designing the 1+MG IT infrastructure.

Regarding the national clouds established for public entities, **a state-by-state legal analysis would need to be conducted on this issue by each NCP.** No such answers are readily available within the confines of this deliverable, but we take the opportunity to ask a few questions on this issue in the next paragraphs to enable member state participants to take advantage of the current mapping of roles.

As we previously mentioned, cloud services may be created either in-house or purchased, however at the end of the day, to so speak, the 1+MG IT Infrastructure must be created asking *what would it take for decentralized infrastructure to ensure the requisite level of security, confidentiality and integrity* (including for backups to ensure business continuity) of something as complex and sensitive as the genomic data infrastructure, in any political or physical environment? **The requisite level of security, confidentiality and integrity will depend on the legal classification performed under applicable (national) laws of each entity in the Genome EDIC.**

We will go through the legislations one by one and point out where national laws must be checked. For instance, if the entity is under NIS2 or under national cloud legislation, they will set both the legal duties related to their role(s) in the Genome EDIC and the level of security technically required.

Leaving now this concept of digital sovereignty, we turn next to this concept of “federated” digital structure and why it is important in applying EU legislation on cybersecurity.

⁶² As one example, Polo Strategico Nazionale is an Italian Cloud set up to host public administration in Italy. The migration under the Italian Cloud Strategy is happening now until approximately the end of 2025 to move to public administration to PSN by the end of 2025, as the national cloud infrastructure. Its role in the EHDS will need to be investigated.

⁶³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cloud-computing>.

⁶⁴ See <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cloud-computing>.

Federated cloud and Interoperability

We started this section with an overview of cloud computing as a service more generally because we would expect that a decentralized digital infrastructure will use cloud technology. Then we raised the issue of cloud digital sovereignty which could be important for sourcing cloud technology for the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP at the national level. Next we move from cloud to “federated cloud” because it should be similar in its function to the expected decentralized but harmonised data governance of the Genome EDIC and 1+NCP nodes.⁶⁵

One of the benefits of a federated cloud system is its interoperability. This is relevant to 1+MG IT infrastructure planning since it is aiming to be a decentralized, interoperable IT infrastructure. We look at an explanation of “federated cloud” next.

In a federated cloud, the “participating entities have official membership in the federation, along with identity credentials, and they choose to share specific resources and metadata which allow them to be discoverable and accessible to other federation members under specified conditions.

A cloud federation allows the interoperability and sharing of different cloud infrastructures to optimize resource utilization and provide a broader range of capabilities.”⁶⁶

We look at this notion of “interoperability” because it will come up in the legal analysis later in Section 4. Interoperability can mean not only data portability but also *application* portability.⁶⁷ We can envisage such a usage potentially for the Genome EDIC and its supporting 1+MG IT Infrastructure and 1+MG NCP, as it starts processing data and later the data is moved when it eventually integrates into the EHDS platforms. Interoperability for the Genome EDIC and its nodes will be relevant to meet harmonised requirements which will be discussed subsequently related to (at least) the Data Act, Data Governance Act, the Interoperable Europe Act, and of course in the context of the EHDS.

We anticipate that an interoperable, federated structure composed of an amalgam of cloud services will be complex to manage for the following reason (from ENISA): “Various gaps in the cloud cybersecurity market emerge through mismatches in deployment of cybersecurity functions between the demand side and supply side. The market gaps are rooted in

⁶⁵ The Genome EDIC is expected to be on a federated model as discussed in the document “Overview of expected implications of the sustainability vote for the short-term implementation”: “1+MG Compliant Datasets: The foundation of the federated model, where national entities retain control but adhere to the EDIC’s harmonised rules.” For a description on federated cloud computing, see <https://standards.ieee.org/beyond-standards/new-ieee-standard-advances-federated-cloud-computing/>.

⁶⁶ <https://standards.ieee.org/beyond-standards/new-ieee-standard-advances-federated-cloud-computing/>.

⁶⁷ (Hon, Millard, Singh, 2021 “Control, Security, and Risk in the Cloud”)

concerns about the management of various threats and *unclear distribution responsibilities about the implementation and maintenance of cloud cybersecurity functions.*⁶⁸

These complexities of cloud arrangements that will make up federated data structure present challenges in building the 1+MG IT Infrastructure, specifically looking at how to make it secure from cyberthreats. This interplay of cloud layers, and how it can impact cybersecurity responsibility is useful to consider no matter which legislation applies to which 1+MG NCP or the Genome EDIC.

We hope to have given the consortium a broader explanation of legal responsibility for cybersecurity in cloud layers, digital sovereignty, and federated data structures in the first half of Section 4. This should be helpful when reading the below analysis to put different legislations in the context of the digital environment in which they might apply.

4.3 Analysis of the legislation

4.3.1 Identification of the legal roles in the relevant legislations on cybersecurity and an explanation of their duties

4.3.2 Method of selecting legislation and classifications of roles, spotting the possible correspondences to roles identified under EDIC infrastructure

In this section we introduce the legal concept of cybersecurity in EU law, and we discuss the so-called attack surface, *i.e.*, where in the infrastructure cybersecurity can be threatened.⁶⁹ We then explain the various laws more generally before moving to specific legislations. This selection of laws was made based on the likelihood of their relevance based on key terms used and discussed in the project documents and common view of what the infrastructure is expected to become. As mentioned in the methodological part we have selected only legislations that appeared relevant excluding those that beyond a *prima facie* analysis proved not to be relevant.

The overall goal to make the reader aware of how cybersecurity is treated more generally under EU law, so that the presentation of each individual statute is understood in this broader context and systemic interpretation.

After this introduction, 4.2 contains three parts:

First, there are the 6 main legislations that each have a table, with legal analysis immediately afterward under “commentary”.

Second, we review more simply other EU legislations that in some way create or affect cybersecurity duties.

Third, we review more broadly important aspects of cybersecurity requirements and incident response, overlapping duties, and cybersecurity supply chain. We add information

⁶⁸ Cloud Cybersecurity Market Analysis Version 1.0 in March 2023, DOI 10.2824/050402

⁶⁹ Cyber Resilience Act, Rec. 9

for the 1+MG NCP on how ENISA provides guidance in NIS2 implementation, supply chain and to the healthcare sector, which might be useful in their own legal analysis of each national entity that makes up the nodes.

We focus here on 6 important legislation that impose duties for cybersecurity on actors that likely will have roles in the infrastructure now or in the future, presenting each one in a table that covers the same aspects of each legislation: scope, subject matter, definitions, legal roles and duties. Each table ends with a brief conclusion on the applicability to the EDIC and the 1+MG NCP. This visually highlights that the table contains mostly terms from the law, and there is commentary below which is our input.

We narrowed down the list of potentially applicable EU legislation to cybersecurity duties to focus on the 6 most important to the EDIC.

1. Directive (EU) 2022/2557 (Resilience of Critical Entities - CER)
2. Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (NIS2)
3. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR)
4. Regulation (EU) 2025/327 (European Health Data Space - EHDS)
5. Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (Cyber Resilience Act - CRA)
6. Regulation (EU) 2019/881 (Cybersecurity Act- CA)

As explained in greater detail below, these regulations impose a wide range of obligations on various actors, ensuring a multi-layered approach to protecting sensitive data, personal data, metadata, and anonymized data within the digital infrastructure that supports the data to achieve the cybersecurity triad of confidentiality, integrity and availability. So looking from the broadest laws, like the Cybersecurity Act, or the GDPR, to the narrower one of the Commission Decision itself, we see that the requirement for cybersecurity (and often interoperability) appears in one way or another, in each of these laws.

The **eIDAS 2** requirements are incorporated into the EHDS through its requirements on access and authentication using the EU digital wallet, so we include a brief discussion of that law. While the requirements of data portability and interoperability are not core to the definition of “cybersecurity” from the Cybersecurity Act, they are important to ensuring data governance, including quality and availability of data. However, since they are not part of the core concept of cybersecurity, they are not included as part of these tables, but a brief overview of requirements of data interoperability and portability as required by the **European Data Act** and the **Data Governance Act**, the **Interoperable Europe Act** is included. We also address the Medical Devices Regulation for completeness.

4.3.3 A definition of cybersecurity

Legal responsibility for the cybersecurity of a digital infrastructure needs to be clarified taking into account various roles that interact with that infrastructure which could directly or indirectly jeopardize security.

To understand the potential inroads, the Cyber Resilience Act explains in Recital 9, “Under certain conditions, all products with digital elements integrated in or connected to a larger electronic information system can serve as an attack vector for malicious actors. As a result, even hardware and software considered to be less critical can facilitate the initial compromising of a device or network, enabling malicious actors to gain privileged access to a system or to move laterally across systems.”⁷⁰ We would like to make the consortium aware that cybersecurity could be in theory weakened by any digital element that could connect to the 1+MG IT infrastructure, as they each can impact security. It may be worthwhile to keep in mind at this early stage that “many breaches originate from vulnerabilities in development and testing environments, where security controls are often weaker than in production.”⁷¹

The analysis below takes each law in turn and examines which set of rules we can expect to apply to the Genome EDIC and its NCPs. We start with the Cybersecurity Act (CA), NIS (Directive (EU)2016/1148), and NIS2 because they give certain definitions and cross-references that we will use as our base vocabulary and use the terms consistent within the other EU cybersecurity related laws and guidelines that come later.⁷²

We start by breaking down the elements of the definition provided in the EU Cybersecurity Act for the term “**cybersecurity**’ as

- [A] activities necessary to protect network and information systems,
- [B] the users of such systems, and
- [C] other persons affected by
- [D] cyber threats.⁷³

Taking these elements one at a time, we consider how they would apply to the Genome EDIC and its 1+MG IT infrastructure.

⁷⁰ Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital (Cyber Resilience Act), Rec. 9.

⁷¹ Ibid.

⁷² Some laws have since been updated or newly published since the CA was enacted, such as NIS to NIS2 and its implementations, eIDAS to eIDAS2, CER and its implementations, the Cyber Resilience Act, and of course, most recently the EHDS.

⁷³ Regulation (EU) 2019/881 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act), Art. 2(1).

Genome EDIC would be a “network and information system”^{74, 75} which is any device or group of interconnected or related devices, one or more of which, pursuant to a programme, carry out automatic processing of digital data; or digital data stored, processed, retrieved or transmitted by elements...for the purposes of their operation, use, protection and maintenance.

By this description, we assume that Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP would meet the definition of a network and information system.

The next element [B] then is to understand what activities would be necessary to protect the “**users of such systems.**” The “users” we assume, would be the separate national nodes, their employees, data holders and data users. Notice that here “users” is a category broader than the definition of users within the EDIC itself.⁷⁶

The third element [C] covers “other persons affected by cyber threats.” This group would likely include at a minimum the data subjects whose genomic or otherwise personal data is processed by the infrastructure, and end users of the genomic data who need to rely on that data being confidential, accurate and available. This could even include any individuals accessing the infrastructure with digital credentials.

The fourth element, a **cyber threat** [D] is “any potential circumstance, event or action that could damage, disrupt or otherwise adversely impact network and information systems, the users of such systems and other persons.”⁷⁷

We have now demonstrated that “cybersecurity” (per EU Cybersecurity Act) would be appropriately applied to the decentralized IT infrastructure of Genome EDIC and its nodes. Now we consider what makes up “cybersecurity” as a concept.

Before jumping into the individual legislations below, and discussing which roles and duties might apply, a general comment on cybersecurity practice may help the consortium absorb this discussion in context. Cybersecurity can be thought of as what to do for incident prevention and resiliency measures, and what to do when there is a cybersecurity “incident”

⁷⁴ Within the meaning of NIS2 Art.6 (1) which is “an electronic communications network as defined in Directive (EU) 2018/1972, Art. 2, point (1) (see next footnote).

⁷⁵ Directive (EU) 2018/1972 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code defines “electronic communications network” as a “transmission systems, whether or not based on a permanent infrastructure or centralised administration capacity, and, where applicable, switching or routing equipment and other resources, including network elements which are not active, which permit the conveyance of signals by wire, radio, optical or other electromagnetic means, including satellite networks, fixed (circuit- and packet-switched, including internet) and mobile networks, electricity cable systems, to the extent that they are used for the purpose of transmitting signals, networks used for radio and television broadcasting, and cable television networks, irrespective of the type of information conveyed.”

⁷⁶ See Table 5 for Stakeholder roles. “User” within the stakeholder roles is limited to the individual that is seeking access to data in 1+MG SPEs.

⁷⁷ (EU) 2019/881, Art. 2(8)

meaning an “event having an actual adverse effect on the security of network and information systems.”⁷⁸

Looking at the decentralized digital infrastructure, the Genome EDIC and its nodes should understand that online elements each in some way introduce potential cybersecurity risks and responsibilities toward the 1+MG IT infrastructure⁷⁹. By “elements” we refer more loosely to the online access points, tools, software, user portal, etc. that will eventually make up the digital environment for the Genome EDIC and nodes.

Next, we analyse 6 EU legislations and discuss what are the legal roles of each that have corresponding cybersecurity duties.

CER roles and duties

Title	Directive (EU) 2022/2557 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on the resilience of critical entities and repealing Council Directive 2008/114/EC	
Short name	CER	
Art. 1 Scope & subject matter:	<p>1. (a), (b) lays down obligations for critical entities aimed at enhancing their resilience and ensure that the ability to provide essential services for the maintenance of vital societal functions or economic activities are provided in an unobstructed manner in the internal market.</p> <p>2. CER shall not apply to matters covered by Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (NIS2), but shall be implemented in a coordinated manner.</p> <p>3. Where provisions of sector-specific Union legal acts require critical entities to take measures to enhance their resilience and where those requirements are recognised by Member States as at least equivalent to the corresponding obligations laid down in this Directive, the relevant provisions of this Directive shall not apply.</p>	
ANNEX	Types of critical entities (by sector) ⁸⁰	
	Health	Healthcare providers as defined in Article 3, point (g), of Directive 2011/24/EU
	Digital infrastructure	Providers of cloud computing services as defined in Article 6, point (30), of Directive (EU) 2022/2555
Providers of data centre services as defined in Article 6, point (31), of Directive (EU) 2022/2555		

⁷⁸ DIRECTIVE (EU) 2016/1148 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union, (“NIS”) Art. 4(7)

⁷⁹ See Cyber Resilience Act, Recital 9 states, “Under certain conditions, all products with digital elements integrated in or connected to a larger electronic information system can serve as an attack vector for malicious actors.”

⁸⁰ The CER Annex lists 11 sectors, we include here the two that are closest in application. See commentary below for more details on this selection.

<p>Art. 2 Definitions⁸¹:</p>	<p>For the purposes of this Directive, the following definitions apply:</p> <p>(1) ‘critical entity’ means a public or private entity which has been identified by a Member State in accordance with Article 6 as belonging to one of the categories set out in the third column of the table in the Annex;</p> <p>(2) ‘resilience’ means a critical entity’s ability to prevent, protect against, respond to, resist, mitigate, absorb, accommodate and recover from an incident;</p> <p>(3) ‘incident’ means an event which has the potential to significantly disrupt, or that disrupts, the provision of an essential service, including when it affects the national systems that safeguard the rule of law;</p> <p>(4) ‘critical infrastructure’ means an asset, a facility, equipment, a network or a system, or a part of an asset, a facility, equipment, a network or a system, which is necessary for the provision of an essential service;</p> <p>(5) ‘essential service’ means a service which is crucial for the maintenance of vital societal functions, economic activities, public health and safety, or the environment;</p> <p>(6) ‘risk’ means the potential for loss or disruption caused by an incident and is to be expressed as a combination of the magnitude of such loss or disruption and the likelihood of occurrence of the incident;</p> <p>(7) ‘risk assessment’ means the overall process for determining the nature and extent of a risk by identifying and analysing potential relevant threats, vulnerabilities and hazards which could lead to an incident and by evaluating the potential loss or disruption of the provision of an essential service caused by that incident;</p>
<p>Art. 3 Minimum harmonisation</p>	<p>Member states can adopt or maintain provisions of national law with a view to achieving a higher level of resilience of critical entities.</p>
<p>Legal roles</p>	<p>Critical entity</p>

⁸¹ For each legislation in the tables, only a selection of the definitions that are useful to the discussion are included.

	Critical entity of Particular European Significance (If the Critical Entity provides the same or similar essential services to or in six or more Member States & formally notified it falls into this category (per Art. 17 (3))
Cybersecurity duties for roles that could potentially be in EDIC and/or nodes	<p>Art. 12(1) Critical entity risk assessment critical entities carry out a risk assessment within nine months of receiving the notification by member state competent authority that an entity is “critical” under CER. The risk assessment must be done whenever necessary subsequently, and at least every four years to assess all relevant risks that could disrupt the provision of their essential services.</p> <p>Art. 13 (1) Resilience measures. Critical entities must take appropriate and proportionate technical, security and organisational measures to ensure their resilience. (Details on measures are listed Art. 12 (1)(a – f)</p> <p>Art. 14. (1)Background checks. Critical entity may submit a request for a background check for certain individuals in sensitive roles or with authority for remote access to control security of critical entity.</p> <p>Art. 15. (1) Incident notification to competent authority by critical entities of incidents that significantly disrupt or have the potential to significantly disrupt the provision of essential services.</p>
Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes	<p>Not likely for the Genome EDIC. It seems that the Genome EDIC itself would not qualify as a “critical entity” for the purposes of CER obligations since it does not fall within the “health sector” or “digital infrastructure” as described in the Annex of the CER.</p> <p>However, the 1+MG NCPs as individual nodes may fall under CER in the national implementations, and therefore each one must check based on the function of the 1+MG NCP and that national implementation of CER.</p>

Commentary on CER

Directive (EU) 2022/2557 on “the resilience of critical entities” (CER) imposes obligations on Member States to take measures enhancing the resilience of certain “critical entities” which provide essential services, as stated in CER Art 1.

We look first to the definition of “critical entity” to understand if the definition might apply to the Genome EDIC. “‘Critical entity’ means a public or private entity which has been identified by a Member State in accordance with Article 6 as belonging to one of the categories set out in the third column of the table in the Annex.”⁸²

⁸² CER Art.2(1)

The CER Annex lists 11 sectors, all but two can be excluded as possible options.⁸³ We focus on two sectors – health and digital infrastructure - to check if they could apply to the EDIC.

Sector 5. Health. Categories of entities:

- Healthcare providers as defined in Article 3, point (g), of Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council (14)
- EU reference laboratories as referred to in Article 15 of Regulation (EU) 2022/2371 of the European Parliament and of the Council (15)
- Entities carrying out research and development activities of medicinal products as defined in Article 1, point (2), of Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (16)
- Entities manufacturing basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations
- Entities manufacturing medical devices considered as critical during a public health emergency
- Entities holding a distribution authorisation

On its face, it would seem that the Genome EDIC itself, would *not* qualify as part of the health sector. It is not a health care provider; it is not a laboratory or an entity carrying out R&D activities of medical products for example. It is possible that these healthcare entities would use data from EDIC but EDIC itself does not carry out any of these activities. This is also consistent with the discussion (related to NIS2) in GDI legal analysis on “EU Regulations applicable to Genome EDIC. The GDI legal analysis document “EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC” states (in regard to NIS2) applicability, which also looks at healthcare as a sector: “Genome EDIC... is not a healthcare infrastructure.”

Now we consider whether the Genome EDIC might be within the “Digital Infrastructure” sector, which is broken down into nine categories of entities of those we consider the following three for potential application.⁸⁴

Section 8. Digital Infrastructure. Categories of entities:

- Providers of cloud computing services as defined in Article 6, point (30), of Directive (EU) 2022/ 2555
- Providers of data centre services as defined in Article 6, point (31), of Directive (EU) 2022/ 2555
- Providers of content delivery networks as defined in Article 6, point (32), of Directive (EU) 2022/2555

⁸³ The other sectors in the CER Annex are: energy, transport, banking, financial market infrastructure, drinking water, waste water, public administration, space, and ‘production, processing and distribution of food’.

⁸⁴ Of the 9 categories, 6 are not related to Genome EDIC or node activities.

We take the first definition referred to in NIS2 Art. 6 (30): ‘**cloud computing service**’ is a “digital service that enables on-demand administration and broad remote access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable computing resources, including where such resources are distributed across several locations.”

In order to analyse if Genome EDIC entities could fit into the “categories of entities” within Digital Infrastructure from the CER Annex, we will look at the different stakeholders within the Genome.

We consider whether certain stakeholders and/or terms (from Table 1 and Table 5) could be considered “providers of cloud computing services” per this NIS2 definition. We have put them here immediately below for ease of reference:

1+MG IT Infrastructure	IT environment on the central, national and local level, as applicable, that hosts data and metadata for the Genome EDIC secondary use framework and enables workflows through suitable tools or to the providers of such infrastructure.
Genome EDIC	Central legal entity incorporating the 1+MG infrastructure
Genome EDIC secondary use framework	The framework set up to give cross-border access to genomic and health data in a harmonised fashion.
1+MG data host	Organisation that physically holds the data that are made available in the Genome EDIC secondary use framework by the 1+MG data holder.
1+MG NCP	1+MG National Coordination Point, entity within Genome EDIC member countries responsible that serves as the central contact for the secondary use of data from the respective country.
SPE network	Genome EDIC’s network of Secure Processing Environments

We take for example the “Genome EDIC secondary use framework” which, as described, is expected to “give cross-border access to genomic and health data.” This description does *not* indicate that it will be scalable or an elastic pool of shareable computing resources.

Next, we take the example of the “SPE network” which will *process* data but does *not* provide cloud computing service. To understand what type of activity an SPE does, we look at the definition of a ‘secure processing environment’ in the Data Governance act Art 2(20):

“the physical or virtual environment and organisational means to ensure compliance with Union law, such as Regulation (EU) 2016/679, in particular with regard to data subjects’ rights, intellectual property rights, and commercial and statistical confidentiality, integrity and accessibility, as well as with applicable national law, and to allow the entity providing the secure processing environment to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including the display, storage, download and export of data and the calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms.”

The GDI legal analysis done by the ELSI group⁸⁵ also discussed whether (under NIS2) the SPEs could be considered ‘cloud computing service’ and concluded the SPEs are not likely to be a cloud computing service “insofar as it lacks configurable, on demand computing resources (users do not configure nor managed the computing environment; it is pre-configured and managed by the EDIC), the services offered are not elastic, and the environment is controlled and restricted.”

We continue looking at our examples from the stakeholders above to consider if there are any others within the “Digital Infrastructure” types of entities listed in the CER Annex.

“1+MG IT Infrastructure”, will host data and the “1+MG data host” will physically hold the data. The 1+MG NCP will be a contact point for use of data. We see that **none of these stakeholders listed fully fit the definition of a cloud service provider** as a “digital service that enables on-demand administration and broad remote access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable computing resources, including where such resources are distributed across several locations.”⁸⁶

We have just analysed the definition of “cloud service provider” as one of three categories of entities in “Digital Infrastructure” and determined that the Genome EDIC will not be a cloud service provider.

Now we consider the definitions for the other two digital infrastructure entities which could potentially apply to the Genome EDIC:

“‘Data centre service’ means a service that encompasses structures, or groups of structures, dedicated to the centralised accommodation, interconnection and operation of IT and network equipment providing data storage, processing and transport services together with all the facilities and infrastructures for power distribution and environmental control;

‘Content delivery network’ means a network of geographically distributed servers for the purpose of ensuring high availability, accessibility or fast delivery of digital content and services to internet users on behalf of content and service providers.”⁸⁷

At this time in the designing and planning phase we expect that the Genome EDIC will potentially use data center services, and use content delivery networks, but not provide them. There is no information in the description of project terms and stakeholder roles at

⁸⁵ In the GDI legal analysis document “EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC”

⁸⁶ NIS2, Art. 6(30)

⁸⁷ NIS2 Art. 6(31), (32)

this time in the project that indicate that the Genome EDIC or the 1+MG NCPs to indicate otherwise.

Based on this analysis of the three entities of the Digital infrastructure sector, the Genome EDIC is not within the Digital Infrastructure Sector.

Therefore, CER would not seem to apply to the Genome EDIC because it does not fall within any sector of the Annex. **This is not to make any statement about how the various nodes would be considered, which should be considered separate from the EDIC.** The 1+MG NCP are national coordination points from the member countries, but they are part of national entities.⁸⁸ We are not including these entities within the analysis as they may vary in the services or involvement related to the health sector and/or digital infrastructure.⁸⁹ Any node-by-node analysis should be conducted in the same way, looking at the definitions of the types of entities within the two possible Sectors of the CER Annex (Health and Digital Infrastructure) to see if CER would apply. If yes, then each national node must check the national implementations of the CER in that member state, since the CER is a directive, not a regulation.

Next, we consider NIS2, another EU directive imposing security measures to enhance resiliency, such as risk assessment and incident response duties, but specific to network information security in the EU. For NIS2, we conduct a similar analysis looking at the sectors and types of entities in those sectors from its Annex I and II, we compare them to possibly similar roles within the Genome EDIC, its stakeholders, and nodes.

We advise that each node will need to look at its own unique functions to make a similar analysis to see whether by itself it will need to apply NIS2. This is explained in the commentary below.

NIS2 roles and duties

Title	Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148
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⁸⁸ From the GDI legal analysis- 'EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC': "we consider their input that the national nodes may have multiple functions: "However, the situation may be different on the national level. As the secure processing environment are services that will be provided by the national nodes, it should be noted that NIS2 may in any case apply to the nodes directly. They may offer their IT infrastructure as computer service outside secondary use. They may also have a direct role for primary healthcare such as the Danish National Genome Center that hosts all the data for the Danish healthcare system."

⁸⁹ Ibid.

Short name	NIS2 Directive
Art. 1 Subject matter:	<p>(b cybersecurity risk-management measures and reporting obligations) for entities of a type referred to in Annex I or II as well as for entities identified as critical entities under Directive (EU) 2022/2557;</p> <p>(c) rules and obligations on cybersecurity information sharing;</p>
Art. 2 Scope:	<p>1) NIS2 applies to public or private entities of a type referred to in Annex I or II which qualify as medium-sized enterprises;</p> <p>2) Regardless of their size, this Directive also applies to entities of a type referred to in Annex I or II, where:</p> <p>(b the entity is the sole provider in a Member State of a service which) is essential for the maintenance of critical societal or economic activities;</p> <p>(c) disruption of the service provided by the entity could have a significant impact on public safety, public security or public health;</p> <p>(d disruption of the service provided by the entity could induce a) significant systemic risk, in particular for sectors where such disruption could have a cross-border impact;</p> <p>(e) the entity is critical because of its specific importance at national or regional level for the particular sector or type of service, or for other interdependent sectors in the Member State;</p> <p>3. Regardless of their size, this Directive applies to entities identified as critical entities under Directive (EU) 2022/2557.</p>
Annex 1: sectors of high criticality, type of entities ⁹⁰	Health sector includes health care providers, EU reference laboratories, Entities carrying out research and development activities of medicinal products, Entities manufacturing medical devices considered to be critical during a public health emergency.
	Digital infrastructure. Includes Cloud computing service providers Data centre service providers, Content delivery network providers
Annex 2: Other critical sectors ⁹¹	7. Research – Research organisations

⁹⁰ Annex I “Sectors of High Criticality” lists 11 sectors, we include here the two that are closest in application. See commentary below for more details on this selection.

⁹¹ Annex II “Other Critical Sectors” lists 7 sectors, we include here only one close enough to consider its application.

	[Art 6(41) ‘research organisation’ means an entity which has as its primary goal to conduct applied research or experimental development with a view to exploiting the results of that research for commercial purposes, but which does not include educational institutions.]
Critical entities under (EU) 2022/2557 CER	See CER analysis above
Art. 6 Definitions ⁹² :	<p>1) ‘network and information system’ means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) an electronic communications network as defined in Article 2,) point (1), of Directive (EU) 2018/1972; (b) any device or group of interconnected or related devices, one or) more of which, pursuant to a programme, carry out automatic processing of digital data; or (c) digital data stored, processed, retrieved or transmitted by elements covered under points (a) and (b) for the purposes of their operation, use, protection and maintenance; <p>(2) ‘security of network and information systems’ means the ability of network and information systems to resist, at a given level of confidence, any event that may compromise the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored, transmitted or processed data or of the services offered by, or accessible via, those network and information systems;</p> <p>(3) ‘cybersecurity’ means cybersecurity as defined in Article 2, point (1), of Regulation (EU) 2019/881;</p> <p>(5) ‘near miss’ means an event that could have compromised the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored, transmitted or processed data or of the services offered by, or accessible via, network and information systems, but that was successfully prevented from materialising or that did not materialise;</p>

⁹² A selection of definitions has been included here based on relevancy for this discussion. For every definition, see NIS2 Art. 6.

	<p>(6) 'incident' means an event compromising the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored, transmitted or processed data or of the services offered by, or accessible via, network and information systems;</p> <p>(7) 'large-scale cybersecurity incident' means an incident which causes a level of disruption that exceeds a Member State's capacity to respond to it or which has a significant impact on at least two Member States;</p> <p>(8) 'incident handling' means any actions and procedures aiming to prevent, detect, analyse, and contain or to respond to and recover from an incident;</p> <p>(9) 'risk' means the potential for loss or disruption caused by an incident and is to be expressed as a combination of the magnitude of such loss or disruption and the likelihood of occurrence of the incident;</p> <p>(10) 'cyber threat' means a cyber threat as defined in Article 2, point (8), of Regulation (EU) 2019/881;</p> <p>(11) 'significant cyber threat' means a cyber threat which, based on its technical characteristics, can be assumed to have the potential to have a severe impact on the network and information systems of an entity or the users of the entity's services by causing considerable material or non-material damage;</p> <p>(12) 'ICT product' means an ICT product as defined in Article 2, point (12), of Regulation (EU) 2019/881;</p> <p>(13) 'ICT service' means an ICT service as defined in Article 2, point (13), of Regulation (EU) 2019/881;</p> <p>(14) 'ICT process' means an ICT process as defined in Article 2, point (14), of Regulation (EU) 2019/881;</p>
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	<p>(15) 'vulnerability' means a weakness, susceptibility or flaw of ICT products or ICT services that can be exploited by a cyber threat;</p> <p>(30) 'cloud computing service' means a digital service that enables on-demand administration and broad remote access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable computing resources, including where such resources are distributed across several locations;</p> <p>(31) 'data centre service' means a service that encompasses structures, or groups of structures, dedicated to the centralised accommodation, interconnection and operation of IT and network equipment providing data storage, processing and transport services together with all the facilities and infrastructures for power distribution and environmental control;</p> <p>(32) 'content delivery network' means a network of geographically distributed servers for the purpose of ensuring high availability, accessibility or fast delivery of digital content and services to internet users on behalf of content and service providers;</p> <p>(38) 'entity' means a natural or legal person created and recognised as such under the national law of its place of establishment, which may, acting under its own name, exercise rights and be subject to obligations;</p> <p>(41) 'research organisation' means an entity which has as its primary goal to conduct applied research or experimental development with a view to exploiting the results of that research for commercial purposes, but which does not include educational institutions.</p>
<p>Legal roles</p>	<p>Management bodies of essential and important entities Essential & important entities</p>
<p>Cybersecurity duties for roles that could potentially be in</p>	<p>Article 21. Cybersecurity risk-management measures 1) take appropriate and proportionate technical, operational and organisational measures to manage the risks posed to the security of network and information systems which those entities use for their operations or for the provision of their services, and to prevent or</p>

<p>EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>minimise the impact of incidents on recipients of their services and on other services.</p> <p>Taking into account the state-of-the-art and, where applicable, relevant European and international standards, as well as the cost of implementation, the measures referred to in the first subparagraph shall ensure a level of security of network and information systems appropriate to the risks posed. When assessing the proportionality of those measures, due account shall be taken of the degree of the entity’s exposure to risks, the entity’s size and the likelihood of occurrence of incidents and their severity, including their societal and economic impact</p>
	<p>Article 23 Reporting obligations of any “significant incident” to CSIRT, or where applicable competent authority</p> <p>Art. 23. (4) the entities concerned submit to the CSIRT or, where applicable, the competent authority:</p> <p>(a without undue delay and in any event within 24 hours of becoming) aware of the significant incident, an early warning, which, where applicable, shall indicate whether the significant incident is suspected of being caused by unlawful or malicious acts or could have a cross-border impact;</p> <p>(b without undue delay and in any event within 72 hours of becoming) aware of the significant incident, an incident notification, which, where applicable, shall update the information referred to in point (a) and indicate an initial assessment of the significant incident, including its severity and impact, as well as, where available, the indicators of compromise;</p> <p>(c) upon the request of a CSIRT or, where applicable, the competent authority, an intermediate report on relevant status updates;</p> <p>(d a final report not later than one month after the submission of the) incident notification under point (b), including the following:</p> <p>(i a detailed description of the incident, including its severity and) impact;</p> <p>(ii the type of threat or root cause that is likely to have triggered the) incident;</p> <p>(iii) applied and ongoing mitigation measures;</p>

	(iv) where applicable, the cross-border impact of the incident;
Application to the Genome EDIC and/or nodes	Not likely. NIS2 applies only to certain sectors, which the Genome EDIC itself does <i>not</i> seem to fall within, namely healthcare, digital infrastructure (as listed in Annex I), or research organization (as listed in Annex II). See the commentary below for the sector-specific analysis. However, we raise the possibility that the individual nodes (1+MG NCP) could fall within NIS2’s scope based on their entity’s services in healthcare or because of services offered by IT facilities. ⁹³ A node– by– node analysis should be done to check for NIS2 applicability at a national level.

Commentary on NIS2

Directive (EU) 2022/2555 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2) creates a high common level of cybersecurity across the EU by expanding the risk management measures and reporting obligations for both essential and important entities in critical sectors.

The NIS2 directive gives “cybersecurity risk-management measures and reporting obligations for entities of a type referred to in Annex I or II as well as for entities identified as critical entities under Directive (EU) 2022/2557.”⁹⁴ It focuses more on active risk management, expanding the initial scope of NIS from 8 to 16 sectors. NIS2 requires improved risk management approaches, more stringent reporting obligations, and enhanced cooperation with authorities and Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs).⁹⁵

As a directive, there are many cybersecurity risk management measures and reporting obligations detailed in NIS2 which Member States have the duty to oversee that the management bodies of essential and important entities implement.⁹⁶ The duty passes through, so to speak, to the entities within the scope. We next consider whether or not the Genome EDIC could fall within the scope of NIS2.

⁹³ We align here with the analysis from the “GDI legal analysis -EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC:” “However, the situation may be different on the national level. As the secure processing environment are services that will be provided by the national nodes...They may offer their IT infrastructure as computer service outside secondary use. They may also have a direct role for primary healthcare.”

⁹⁴ NIS2 Art. 1(2)

⁹⁵ For a detailed list of cybersecurity management practices that respond to NIS2 requirements and GDPR security requirements, see (Luidold and Jungbauer 2024). Most recently, ENISA published in June 2025 its “Technical Implementation Guidance” for NIS2, covering guidance and implementation of a policy on the security of network and information systems, risk management policy, incident handling, supply chain security, security in network and information systems acquisition, development and maintenance, policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures, and basic cyber hygiene practices and security training.

⁹⁶ NIS2 Art. 20(1)

The analysis for NIS2 is similar to the CER analysis in so far as they both consider the sectors of Health and Digital Infrastructure. However, NIS2 uses the description of “Sectors of High Criticality” in Annex I, and the entities listed within the sectors are not identical. NIS2 also adds “research organizations” as “other critical sectors” in its Annex II.

Just like for the CER analysis above, we analysed each sector / entity that could conceivably be related to the Genome EDIC stakeholder activities. It can be foreseen that the Genome EDIC might provide data to these sectors (i.e., healthcare, digital infrastructure, research organisations) but the EDIC itself does not carry out any of these activities for the sectors of health, within digital infrastructure, or as a research organisation. We conclude at this point that the Genome EDIC itself seems outside the scope of NIS2.

Like our conclusion for CER, we **raise the possibility that the national nodes, as 1+MG NCPs, could potentially fall within the scope of NIS2.** We also provide a description of the duties that would need to be fulfilled for risk management reporting to help the nodes understand what obligations for cybersecurity they may face. This will come in useful for the nodes when considering the other similar cybersecurity obligations they would have (under GDPR, for example). Any cybersecurity planning could eventually take into account the duties under multiple legislations (CER, NIS2, GDPR, EHDS, etc) to be more efficient and comprehensive in fulfilling similar requirements.

We will now go through the analysis of NIS2 as applied to the Genome EDIC.

Is the Genome EDIC in a Sector of “high criticality” listed in Annex I of NIS2?

We look first to the entities that are considered within the health sector to determine if the Genome EDIC might fall in this category, and therefore potentially have NIS2 obligations.

Under NIS2, Annex I, “health” sector includes the following types of entities:

- Healthcare providers
- EU reference laboratories
- Entities carrying out research and development activities of medicinal products
- Entities manufacturing basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations
- Entities manufacturing medical devices considered to be critical during a public health emergency

The Genome EDIC does not perform any of these services within the health sector and therefore does not fall within the Health Sector.

Next, we look at the types of entities that are classified as “Digital Infrastructure” that could possibly apply the EDIC.⁹⁷

- Cloud computing service providers
- Data centre service providers
- Providers of content delivery networks

We take the first definition referred to in NIS2 Art. 6 (30): ‘Cloud computing service’ is a “digital service that enables on-demand administration and broad remote access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable computing resources, including where such resources are distributed across several locations.”

We consider whether certain stakeholders and/or terms (from Table 1 and Table 5) could be considered “providers of cloud computing services” per this NIS2 definition.

We have put them here immediately below for ease of reference:

1+MG IT Infrastructure	IT environment on the central, national and local level, as applicable, that hosts data and metadata for the Genome EDIC secondary use framework and enables workflows through suitable tools or to the providers of such infrastructure.
Genome EDIC	Central legal entity incorporating the 1+MG infrastructure
Genome EDIC secondary use framework	The framework set up to give cross-border access to genomic and health data in a harmonised fashion.
1+MG data host	Organisation that physically holds the data that are made available in the Genome EDIC secondary use framework by the 1+MG data holder.
1+MG NCP	1+MG National Coordination Point, entity within Genome EDIC member countries responsible that serves as the central contact for the secondary use of data from the respective country.
SPE network	Genome EDIC’s network of Secure Processing Environments

We take for example the “Genome EDIC secondary use framework” which, as described, is expected to “give cross-border access to genomic and health data.” This description does *not* indicate that it will be scalable or an elastic pool of shareable computing resources.

Next, we take the example of the “SPE network” which will *process* data but does *not* provide cloud computing service. To understand what type of activity an SPE does, we look at the definition of a ‘secure processing environment’:

⁹⁷ These three terms use the same definitions as in the CER (that come from NIS2 Art. 6), therefore the analysis is the same as in CER. We copied the analysis here so that each section can stand alone rather than cross-referencing.

“The physical or virtual environment and organisational means to ensure compliance with Union law, such as Regulation (EU) 2016/679, in particular with regard to data subjects’ rights, intellectual property rights, and commercial and statistical confidentiality, integrity and accessibility, as well as with applicable national law, and to allow the entity providing the secure processing environment to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including the display, storage, download and export of data and the calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms.”⁹⁸

The GDI legal analysis done by the ELSI group⁹⁹ also considered whether (under NIS2) the SPEs could be considered ‘cloud computing service’ and concluded the SPEs are not likely to be a cloud computing service “insofar as it lacks configurable, on demand computing resources (users do not configure nor managed the computing environment; it is pre-configured and managed by the EDIC), the services offered are not elastic, and the environment is controlled and restricted.”

We continue looking at our examples from the stakeholders above to consider if they are within the “Digital Infrastructure” types of entities listed in the NIS2 Annex I.

“1+MG IT Infrastructure”, will host data and the “1+MG data host” will physically hold the data. The 1+MG NCP will be a contact point for use of data. We see that **none of these stakeholders listed fully fit the definition of a cloud service provider** as a “digital service that enables on-demand administration and broad remote access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable computing resources, including where such resources are distributed across several locations.”¹⁰⁰

We have just analysed the definition of “cloud service provider” as one of three categories of entities in “Digital Infrastructure” and determined that the Genome EDIC will not be a cloud service provider.

Now we consider the definition (from NIS2 Art. 6) for the other two digital infrastructure entities which could potentially apply to the Genome EDIC.

(31) ‘data centre service’ means a service that encompasses structures, or groups of structures, dedicated to the centralised accommodation, interconnection and operation of IT and network equipment providing data storage, processing and transport services together with all the facilities and infrastructures for power distribution and environmental control;

⁹⁸ DGA Art. 2(20)

⁹⁹ In the GDI legal analysis document “EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC”

¹⁰⁰ NIS2, Art. 6(30)

(32) ‘content delivery network’ means a network of geographically distributed servers for the purpose of ensuring high availability, accessibility or fast delivery of digital content and services to internet users on behalf of content and service providers;

Based on these descriptions, at this time in the designing and planning phase we expect that the Genome EDIC will potentially use data center services, and use content delivery networks, but *not* provide them. There is no information in the description of project terms and stakeholder roles that indicate the Genome EDIC or the 1+MG NCPs to indicate otherwise.

Based on this analysis of the three types of entities of the Digital infrastructure sector listed in NIS2, Annex I (i.e., cloud computing service provider, data centre service provider, content delivery network provider), the Genome EDIC is not within the Digital Infrastructure Sector.

We raise the same point here as we did in the CER analysis earlier, which is that **the nodes should be analysed separately from the EDIC for the applicability of NIS2**. The NCP are national coordination points from the member countries, but they are part of national entities.¹⁰¹ We are not including these entities within the analysis as they may vary in the services or involvement related to the health sector and/or digital infrastructure.¹⁰²

Finally, we check and rule out one last possible sector for NIS2 applicability, i.e, research organisation.

NIS2, Annex II lists “other critical sectors”, which includes one possible sector to consider for the Genome EDIC and/ or its nodes, namely “7. Research – Research organisations “. We state the definition here from Art. 6(41):

‘Research organisation’ means an entity which has as its primary goal to conduct applied research or experimental development with a view to exploiting the results of that research for commercial purposes, but which does not include educational institutions.

The Genome EDIC itself might provide data for research, but it does not conduct research. Thus, it does not fall within this sector either.

¹⁰¹ From the GDI legal analysis, we consider their input that the national nodes may have multiple functions: “the situation may be different on the national level. As the secure processing environment are services that will be provided by the national nodes...They may offer their IT infrastructure as computer service outside secondary use. They may also have a direct role for primary healthcare...”

¹⁰² Ibid.

Therefore, we arrive at the conclusion that the EDIC neither appears to be in the healthcare sector, nor the digital infrastructure sector, nor a research organisation within the meanings provided in NIS2.

However, we stress that the **nodes** should be reviewed at the national level for the services that they provide, which are expected to each be different from those services to be offered by the Genome EDIC.

Next we provide an overview of the NIS2 cybersecurity measures. This can be helpful when the 1+MG NCP create their own cybersecurity strategies, if they determine that they fall within NIS2. Eventually such a cybersecurity strategy can be comprehensively designed to cover other legislations requirements (for example, CER, GDPR cybersecurity requirements, or the EHDS cybersecurity requirements, if and when they might apply).

The cybersecurity measures imposed by NIS2, can be summarized as **registration with the competent national authority, cybersecurity governance, risk management measures, and breach notification**.¹⁰³ We cover each in turn.

Registration

The entity (say for example, a national node) would have to notify the national competent authority that it believes it qualifies as an essential or important entity under the rules of “registration of entities” per Art. 27. The list of minimum information that the entity shall submit to the national competent authorities is in Art. 3(4). This would happen under the national legislation of the 1+MG NCP.

Cybersecurity governance by management bodies of essential and important entities

NIS2 assigns responsibility to the management body of the essential or important entity for approving cybersecurity risk management measures and overseeing their implementation.¹⁰⁴ The management body may be held liable directly for breaches of NIS2 and may be liable for administrative fines.¹⁰⁵ This cybersecurity strategy approved by the management body must create a comprehensive plan that addresses identified gaps and ensures ongoing compliance with NIS2.¹⁰⁶

¹⁰³ See for updated, detailed guidance, ENISA’s report “Technical implementation guidance on Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/2690 of 17 October 2024 laying down rules for the application of NIS2 Directive as regards technical and methodological requirements of cybersecurity risk-management measures” June 2025, version 1.0. doi:10.2824/2702548.

¹⁰⁴ NIS2 Art. 20

¹⁰⁵ NIS2 Art. 34

¹⁰⁶ NIS2 Art 21(h)

Cybersecurity risk-management measures

NIS2 requires the implementation of appropriate and proportionate technical and organizational measures to effectively manage cybersecurity risks.¹⁰⁷ These measures must encompass:

- (a) policies on risk analysis and information system security;
- (b) incident handling;
- (c) business continuity, such as backup management and disaster recovery, and crisis management;
- (d) supply chain security, including security-related aspects concerning the relationships between each entity and its direct suppliers or service providers;
- (e) security in network and information systems acquisition, development and maintenance, including vulnerability handling and disclosure;
- (f) policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures;
- (g) basic cyber hygiene practices and cybersecurity training;
- (h) policies and procedures regarding the use of cryptography and, where appropriate, encryption;
- (i) human resources security, access control policies and asset management;
- (j) the use of multi-factor authentication or continuous authentication solutions, secured voice, video and text communications and secured emergency communication systems within the entity, where appropriate.”

These risk management measures can be in any cybersecurity risk management policy that an entity would wisely adopt, whether or not NIS2 applies. This can be an opportunity for each stakeholder or 1+MG NCP, even the Genome EDIC itself, to build a comprehensive cybersecurity plan in line with measures. It could be useful to cover the GDPR security requirements which are imposed on entities acting as controllers or processors of personal data (see GDPR section below for commentary). These risk management measures found in NIS2 for managing cybersecurity risk are found also under common certification schemes, for example ISO 27001, to implement an information security management system.

Reporting obligations

NIS2 creates obligations on member states to ensure that essential and important entities notify competent authorities or Computer Security Incident Response Teams (“CSIRTs”) of

¹⁰⁷ NIS2 Art. 21 (a)- (j), This same proportionality measurement is also reflected in GDPR for safeguarding personal data.

incidents that have a significant impact on the provision of services (i.e., “significant incident”¹⁰⁸).

- The reporting bodies must provide details to the competent authority to determine any cross-border impact of the incident.¹⁰⁹
- Member states must ensure that essential and important entities communicate, without undue delay, to the recipients of their services that are potentially affected by a significant cyber threat any measures or remedies that those recipients are able to take in response to that threat. Where appropriate, the entities shall also inform those recipients of the significant cyber threat itself.¹¹⁰
- Incident notification procedures require the creation of processes for detecting, analyzing, and reporting security incidents, the establishment of communication channels with relevant competent authorities and CSIRTs, and ensuring adherence to NIS2 notification timelines.
- The reporting obligation has phases, which include the submission of initial notifications, update notifications, and a final report, with specific notification timelines defined within NIS2.¹¹¹

Enforcement

Both essential and important entities can be fined for infringement.¹¹² The penalties are to be established at a national level but “shall be effective, proportionate and dissuasive.”¹¹³ Infringements entailing a personal data breach are specifically addressed, directing the competent authorities handling the NIS2 incident to inform the supervisory authorities of GDPR.¹¹⁴

Documentation

NIS2 requires that documentation must be maintained to provide a thorough record of cybersecurity policies, risk assessments, implemented measures, incident response plans, and all notifications made. Regular audits should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of cybersecurity measures and ensure continuous compliance with NIS2.

The requirement for documentation, like many of the other cybersecurity risk management measures, are a best practice, and echoed in similar industry standards, like ISO 27001 on information security management. They are also similar to GDPR requirements that require

¹⁰⁸ NIS2 Art. 23(4), “An incident shall be considered significant if: (a) it has caused or is capable of causing severe operational disruption of the services or financial loss for the entity concerned; (b) it has affected or is capable of affecting other natural or legal persons by causing considerable material or non-material damage.”

¹⁰⁹ NIS2 Art. 23(1)

¹¹⁰ NIS2 Art. 23(2)

¹¹¹ NIS2 Art. 23(4)

¹¹² Enforcement measures for essential entities are listed in Art 32. The enforcement measures for important entities are listed separately in Art 33.

¹¹³ NIS2 Art. 36

¹¹⁴ NIS2 Art. 35 (1)

accountability and require controllers and processors to keep records of all data processing, which is examined next. The point is that whether or not the Genome EDIC or its nodes separately will be subject to NIS2 specifically, it can already adapt its cybersecurity strategy to meet most of the requirements on governance and cybersecurity risk management.

National variations. National implementation of NIS2 will result in transposition into national laws by EU member states but can vary, necessitating awareness of the specific requirements within each of the member states where the EDIC will eventually operate via its 1+MG NCP. The deadline for the national implementation was October 2024. Like CER, NIS2 cybersecurity requirements are a minimum harmonized standard and member states are free to adopt a higher level of cybersecurity.¹¹⁵

NIS2 is young as a directive and not much other than sector guidance from ENISA is available to explain how it may apply to certain entities. ENISA supports NIS2 implementation by issuing reports (which are discussed toward the end of Section 4). ENISA’s work in the report investigates how well operators of essential services (under NIS 1 terminology uses “OES”) implemented NIS 1 to create good practices to be adopted for NIS2 by essential and important entities. This study of entities which qualified as operators of essential services included operators in the healthcare sectors. The point being is that while NIS2 is young, we have NIS in place since 2016, and where there are similar requirements on similar actors, like healthcare providers, or cloud service providers, from the first NIS, we may be able to gauge the scope of NIS2, despite the scarcity of precedent on which the 1+MG NCP can rely on when doing their own analyses. The nodes are encouraged to read the ENISA guidance to understand better how NIS2 might apply to their entity.

Now that we have analysed the applicability of the CER and NIS2, we move onto the GDPR’s cybersecurity related requirements for data controllers (and joint controllers) and processors.

The sensitivity of secondary genomic data necessitates a strong alignment between the cybersecurity protection measures of NIS2 and those required by the GDPR which is considered in the next section. With reference to the GDPR we will confine the analysis to the security of data CIA (confidentiality, integrity, availability) requirements.

GDPR Cybersecurity Requirements

Title	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data
Short name	General Data Protection Regulation- GDPR

¹¹⁵ NIS2 Art. 5

<p>Art. 1 Subject-matter and objectives:</p>	<p>1. This Regulation lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data.</p> <p>2. This Regulation protects fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons and in particular their right to the protection of personal data.</p>
<p>Art. 2 Scope:</p>	<p>1. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than by automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system or are intended to form part of a filing system.</p>
<p>Art. 4. Definitions: (related to cybersecurity analysis)</p>	<p>(1) 'personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person;</p> <p>(2) 'processing' means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction;</p> <p>(5) 'pseudonymisation' means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person;</p> <p>(7) 'controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law;</p>

	<p>(8) 'processor' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller;</p> <p>(9) 'recipient' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or another body, to which the personal data are disclosed, whether a third party or not. However, public authorities which may receive personal data in the framework of a particular inquiry in accordance with Union or Member State law shall not be regarded as recipients; the processing of those data by those public authorities shall be in compliance with the applicable data protection rules according to the purposes of the processing;</p> <p>(10) 'third party' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or body other than the data subject, controller, processor and persons who, under the direct authority of the controller or processor, are authorised to process personal data;</p> <p>(11) 'consent' of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her;</p> <p>(12) 'personal data breach' means a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed;</p> <p>(13) 'genetic data' means personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person and which result, in particular, from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question;</p> <p>(14) 'biometric data' means personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data;</p>
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	<p>(15) 'data concerning health' means personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status;</p> <p>(23) 'cross-border processing' means either:</p> <p>(a) processing of personal data which takes place in the context of the activities of establishments in more than one Member State of a controller or processor in the Union where the controller or processor is established in more than one Member State; or</p> <p>(b) processing of personal data which takes place in the context of the activities of a single establishment of a controller or processor in the Union but which substantially affects or is likely to substantially affect data subjects in more than one Member State.</p> <p>(26) 'International organisation' means an organisation and its subordinate bodies governed by public international law, or any other body which is set up by, or on the basis of, an agreement between two or more countries.</p>
<p>Legal roles</p>	<p>Controller (and joint controller) Processor Data subject</p>
<p>Cybersecurity duties of roles that could potentially be in the EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Art. 5. Controller shall ensure appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorized or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures ('integrity and confidentiality').</p> <p>Art. 24. (1) The controller shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with this Regulation.</p> <p>Art. 25. Data Protection by Design and Default. 1. Taking into account the state of the art, the cost of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons posed by the processing, the controller shall implement</p>

	<p>appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation, which are designed to implement data-protection principles to integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing in order to meet the requirements of this Regulation.</p> <p>Art. 32. Security of processing.</p> <p>1. Taking into account the state of the art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risk of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller and the processor shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, including inter alia as appropriate:</p> <p>(a) the pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data;</p> <p>(b) the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services;</p> <p>(c) the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;</p> <p>(d) a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing.</p> <p>2. In assessing the appropriate level of security account shall be taken in particular of the risks that are presented by processing, in particular from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.</p> <p>3. Adherence to an approved code of conduct ...or an approved certification mechanism ...may be used as an element by which to demonstrate compliance with the requirements set out in paragraph 1 of this Article.</p> <p>4. The controller and processor shall take steps to ensure that any natural person acting under the authority of the controller or the processor who has access to personal data does not process them except on instructions from the controller, unless he or she is required to do so by Union or Member State law.</p> <p>Art. 33. Notification of breach to the supervisory authority</p> <p>1. In the case of a personal data breach, the controller shall without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it, notify the personal data breach to the supervisory authority competent in accordance with Article 55, unless the personal</p>
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	<p>data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.</p> <p>2. The processor shall notify the controller without undue delay</p> <p>3. The notification shall</p> <p>(b) communicate details of the data protection officer</p> <p>(c) describe the likely consequences of the personal data breach;</p> <p>(d describe the measures taken by the controller to address the personal) data breach, including to mitigate its possible adverse effects.</p> <p>Art 34. The controller shall communication of a personal data breach to the data subject when the personal data breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons</p> <p>Art. 37. (1) The controller and the processor shall designate a data protection officer where...(c) the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9</p> <p>Art. 89 Safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes</p> <p>1. Processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this Regulation, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.</p> <p>2. Where personal data are processed for <u>scientific</u> or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.</p>
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	<p>3. Where personal data are processed for <u>archiving</u> purposes in the public interest, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18, 19, 20 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.</p> <p>4. Where processing referred to in paragraphs 2 and 3 serves at the same time another purpose, the derogations shall apply only to processing for the purposes referred to in those paragraphs.</p>
<p>Application to the Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Yes, the GDPR would apply to the Genome EDIC and its nodes, as a controller, joint controller, and processor.</p> <p>The specific legal role of the Genome EDIC (e.g., as a potential joint controller) needs to be clarified.¹¹⁶</p> <p>For the interim implementation, the controllership for data disclosure remains in the country.¹¹⁷</p> <p>Consent (dynamic data subject consent) will be the legal basis for disclosure.¹¹⁸</p>

Commentary on GDPR cybersecurity aspects

This GDPR analysis is limited to cybersecurity aspects that would be required under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679, specifically examining requirements for different legal roles to safeguard personal data and notifying authorities of data breaches. The GDPR, NIS2, and CER establish similar requirements for information security, like prevention of data leaks, by using risk assessment measures and response protocols to (cyber) security incidents. However, a crucial distinction is that GDPR applies specifically to *personal data* (and mixed data sets which contain personal data) and is not limited to essential or important entities in select sectors as defined in NIS2 or critical entities as defined by CER. Instead, GDPR has a much broader application scope, extending globally to protect the personal data of data subjects within the EU.

We start by reviewing the general principle of security in data processing. Data shall be “processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures (“integrity

¹¹⁶ “1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework”, June 2025, main author R. Becker, contributions B. Rodrigues, T. Rasmussen.

¹¹⁷ Ibid.

¹¹⁸ Ibid.

and confidentiality’).¹¹⁹ This is essentially the standard that must be guaranteed by whatever cybersecurity measures are implemented.¹²⁰

We see that cybersecurity measures for processors and controllers alike must be “appropriate” and could change as technology changes. So, like the approach to risk management in NIS2 and CER, there needs to be ongoing reviews of the risk management measures to make sure security remains commensurate.

Next, we explain the nature of personal data that the Genome EDIC or the 1+MG NCP might process. This is important to gauge the sensitivity of the data, which is important to know when deciding how robust the security needs to be to keep it safe, always in the sense of the cybersecurity triad CIA (confidentiality, integrity, availability).

Personal Data which is expected to be processed by the Genome EDIC

Personal data can be further categorized into general personal data and "special categories" in Art. 9 GDPR. Conversely, 'non-personal data' is defined as "data other than personal data."¹²¹ We consider the following definitions:

Art. 2(13) defines ‘*genetic data*’ as “personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person and which result, in particular, from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question.”

Art. 2(15) defines ‘*data concerning health*’ as personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status.”

Genomic data is considered by GDPR as one of the ‘special categories’ of personal data that ‘merit higher protection’, meaning that it can be subject to stricter national regulatory frameworks in some circumstances, and genetic data is one of them.¹²²

Accordingly, there are differences amongst European Union member states in the concrete implementation of the GDPR into national regulations, complicating and fragmenting the cross-border sharing of sensitive data.

Now that we can say genomic data merits higher levels of protection, let us next look at who has the duty under the GDPR to deliver this level of protection.

¹¹⁹ GDPR Art. 5 (1)(f)

¹²⁰ These measures are elaborated in GDPR Art.32.

¹²¹ These definitions for personal data and data and data processing have been adopted by both the Data Governance Act (DGA) Art. 2(3)(4) and the Data Act Art. 2(3), (4).

¹²² GDPR Art. 9

GDPR Cybersecurity Requirements for Controllers and Processors

Understanding the allocation of responsibilities under GDPR is crucial for establishing legal roles that will appear in the decentralized 1+MG IT infrastructure and are relevant for cybersecurity matters. We look at the definitions of the roles under the GDPR and how they could be held by the EDIC, nodes, or various stakeholders as controllers, joint controllers, or processors.

GDPR defines the roles as follows:

Data Controllers are entities that determine the purposes and means of processing personal data¹²³. They bear primary responsibility for ensuring GDPR compliance and must be able to demonstrate compliance.¹²⁴

Joint Controllers exist when two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing (Article 26(1) GDPR). They must determine their respective responsibilities through a transparent arrangement.

Data Processors are entities that process personal data on behalf of controllers.¹²⁵ They must follow controllers' instructions and implement appropriate security measures. This includes a duty to record processing activity.¹²⁶

Data subjects are important to consider in the limits in which their behaviours must be taken into account in the framework of the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP (e.g. in their use of their access credentials).

Now we try to distil the roles of the EDIC and its parts as they have been described in recent project documents and explain how based on their expected actions, they would need to meet cybersecurity requirements of the GDPR.

Roles of the GDPR actors in the Genome EDIC:

We take an excerpt here from Stakeholders listed in Table 5 that could have a role from the GDPR as controller, joint controller or processor, or data subject:

¹²³ GDPR Art. 4(7)

¹²⁴ GDPR Art. 5 (2)

¹²⁵ GDPR Art. 4(8)

¹²⁶ GDPR Art. 30(1)

Role in Infrastructure ¹²⁷

1+MG Data Access Committee (1+MG DAC)

Data Access Committee, which may include several domain-specific sub-committees, provided by 1+MG that receives and reviews access requests and moderates consensus discussions on access requests where necessary.

1+MG data host

- c.) Organisation that physically holds the data that are made available in the Genome EDIC secondary use framework by the 1+MG data holder.
- d.) Entity holding 1+MG compliant data or 1+MG cohort datasets in 1+MG compliant IT infrastructure

1+MG data holders

National entities who have legal responsibility for data disclosure and therefore are controller for the disclosure. These entities will make the access decisions and have legal agreements with data users.¹²⁸

1+MG IT infrastructure

Refers to the IT environment on the central, national, and local level, as applicable, that hosts data and metadata for the Genome EDIC secondary use framework and enables workflows through suitable tools or to the providers of such infrastructure. Responsibilities assigned refer to features that the respective IT infrastructure should provide or services that the provider of such IT infrastructure should offer.

1+MG National Coordination Point (1+MG NCP)

National node within Member Countries responsible for coordinating access requests and providing information to national stakeholders. Confirms the compliance of data before they are introduced into the data catalogue.¹²⁹

Data provider

Institutions with the right to grant or refuse access to certain genomic and health-related data. In this case, the legal entity that has brought genomic and/or health data into the 1+MG legal entity. Data provider performs the data protection impact assessment (DPIA) and obtains ethics approvals for data inclusion and is the interface to the data subjects for information and consent around data inclusion. Data provider is responsible for data curation and characterisation.¹³⁰

Data subject

Natural person whose data is requested in an access request. Could also refer to natural person whose access credentials are processed.

FEGA node

May or may not be 1+MG data host depending on whether it complies with 1+MG IT infrastructure requirements and holds data that are made available through 1+MG. See '1+MG data host.'

¹²⁷ Some roles and definitions are from "1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework", June 2025, main author R. Becker, contributions B. Rodrigues, T. Rasmussen. See also Table 1 for a more complete list of project entities. Other roles are pulled from various project documents, and do not constitute an exhaustive list of possible infrastructure stakeholders.

¹²⁸ Ibid. "Data holder" here indicates the legal responsibility, it does not require the entity actually physically holds the dataset. In addition, some data providers or entire countries may still prefer a transfer of controllership for the disclosure to the Genome EDIC."

¹²⁹ Updated from slide deck from July 8, 2025 meeting of 1+MG ELSI WG

¹³⁰ From slide deck from July 8, 2025 meeting of 1+MG ELSI WG

1+MG Genome Legal Entity (EDIC)

Central coordinating body, responsible, based on member countries' decision, for defining the common data governance, setting minimum data quality risk and compliance standards, and operating the central user portal and a central Data Access Committee (DAC) to ensure consistency and efficiency.¹³¹

SPE network

Genome EDIC's network of Secure Processing Environments¹³²

SPE providers

"1+MG SPE providers must be able to realise the data use environment for and the ingestion of external high value externally governed data in 1+MG SPEs for the user's projects, also independent of 1+MG governed data."¹³³

User (in this phase, the user has the status of a requester)

The individual that is seeking access to data in 1+MG SPEs.

User Organisation

The legal entity under which the User is requesting access. User Organisations are expected to be either policy makers in the public sector or entities that support public policy making. These may even include commercial entities, including self-employed consultants.

The roles of these stakeholders for the Genome EDIC or any 1+MG NCPs can be matched up with the definition of controller / joint controller and / or processor based on their actions.

Where any one of these roles "*determines the purposes and means* of the processing of personal data" they will be a controller. "Where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing, they shall be joint controllers."¹³⁴

Regarding the determination of which stakeholder might be a "processor", we see that whomever /which entity will *process personal data on behalf of the controller* will be a processor considering that they are separated entities. Taking a recent example from project slides for the ELSI working group meeting for B1MG+, it was stated that the Genome EDIC could act as the potential joint controller responsible for data disclosure to users.¹³⁵ The roles of each of the 1+MG NCP should be reviewed in the new context of 1+MG data holders' controllership.¹³⁶

The GDPR roles of processor (and subprocessor) need to be clarified for the 1+MG data holder, the Genome EDIC, and the 1+MG IT infrastructure.¹³⁷ This analysis can - and must be

¹³¹ Ibid.

¹³² Ibid.

¹³³ Ibid.

¹³⁴ GDPR Art. 26.

¹³⁵ ELSI meeting July 8, 2025, slide "Principal stakeholders"

¹³⁶ "1+MG Data Governance for Research, Document to vote on the principal framework", June 2025, main author R. Becker, contributions B. Rodrigues, T. Rasmussen.

¹³⁷ Ibid.

done - as it becomes clearer for each of the stakeholders. It is up to them to determine their roles under the GDPR. Our goal in this deliverable is to explain what the cybersecurity duties are those roles are required to fulfil.

Next, we move onto considering in more detail the cybersecurity duties to keep secure (guarantee the 'CIA') of personal data by controllers and processors per the GDPR.

Security of Processing by controllers and processors

We start with the duty of record keeping. Controllers and processors are required to keep records of processing activities for monitoring and traceability.¹³⁸ Next we look at requirements under the GDPR for security of processing.

Article 32(1) – (4) of the GDPR gives details on what is required for “security of processing” that apply to both *the controller* and *the processor*.

Before getting into the details of this article, we flag to the reader that it would be useful, for example, for the 1+MG NCP (which determines that it is within certainly the scope of the GDPR, and maybe also NIS2 or CER) to develop a comprehensive security strategy that would fulfil the requirements for data security.

To give an idea of the type of security requirements under GDPR (which all nodes and Genome EDIC) will need to follow as either processor or controller, we paraphrase here the key requirements. **The point is to highlight the overlaps of the approach to security measures and risk assessment** which are embodied in NIS2 and CER discussed above, GDPR discussed here, and eventually other legislation discussed below.

Controllers and processors must:

- Implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security suited to the risks associated with processing. This includes consideration of the state of the art, implementation costs, and the nature and purpose of processing.
- Measures may include:
 - pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data;
 - ensuring the ongoing **confidentiality, integrity, availability**, and resilience of processing systems;
 - the ability to restore access to personal data after an incident;
 - regular testing and evaluation of security measures.
- Security measures must account for risks such as accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure, or access to personal data.

¹³⁸ GDPR Art. 30(1) for controllers, (2) for processors.

The adopted security measures by the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP (or any of the stakeholders that determine they are controllers or processors) must be proportionate with the risk presented by the processing activities, per GDPR Art. 32(1).

Although the specifics of the EDIC's operations at this point might well change and change over time, it is safe for the moment to say that for genetic data as a special category of data (per GDPR Art. 9), these security requirements would be particularly stringent due to the sensitive nature of the information as illustrated by specific national rules. They might be different among different member states since the GDPR allows for derogations, as we recalled earlier, making both more difficult and much needed the adoption of uniform policies at the level of Genome EDIC and of its 1+MG NCP.

It is advisable to design a comprehensive cybersecurity approach that, for instance, meets the record keeping duties under the GDPR, that are adequate to demonstrate the compliance duties under other legislations where applicable (e.g. CER, NIS2, EHDS, etc.), and at the same time provides to the 1+MG NCP uniform guidance on how to cope with different applicable duties. These entities may consider meeting an approved code of conduct or an approved certification scheme to have the presumption of compliance can help meet this burden.¹³⁹

We continue our discussion of security measures required by the GDPR.

Data protection by design and by default

Controllers “shall use only processors providing sufficient guarantees to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures in such a manner that processing ... ensure the protection of the rights of the data subject.”¹⁴⁰ This principle requires building security instructions for appointing data processors according to their different roles in the Genome EDIC and in the 1+MG NCP into systems from the earliest design stages rather than adding it as an afterthought. It is worthwhile mentioning that such an approach could be combined with the fulfilment of the requirements under NIS2 or CER, for instance, and streamlined along with a comprehensive Information Security Management System aligned with ISO 27001. In the context of the Genome EDIC, this could facilitate the adoption of uniform sets of security instructions (technical and organizational measures) for processors.¹⁴¹

Controller must perform a DPIA

For high-risk processing activities, potentially like processing health data and/or genetics on a large scale, GDPR mandates conducting a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).¹⁴²

¹³⁹ This is for GDPR duties, at least (Art. 32(3)); see Art. 40 on approved code of conduct, Art. 42 on demonstrating compliance of security measures.

¹⁴⁰ GDPR Art. 28(1)

¹⁴¹ GDPR Art. 24, 25 elaborate the responsibilities for controllers to ensure data protection by design and default.

¹⁴² GDPR Art. 35

Whichever entity within the Genome EDIC or its stakeholders determines itself to be in the position of data controller will need to perform a DPIA when it performs:

“(a) a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling, and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person;

(b) processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10.”

The Genome EDIC and the nodes will most probably satisfy the requirements under paragraphs (a) and (b) whenever they will be qualified as data controllers. Thus, they will be required to perform a DPIA. Accordingly, they will be called also to ask the *data providers* for their own DPIA, as we explain next.

Conducting a DPIA has already been foreseen as a duty to be carried out by the “data providers” (as listed in the Table 5 description). We recall here that in the most recent document (June 2025) it is stated that the “data provider” in the 1+MG IT infrastructure will be the role responsible to make the datasets “1+MG proof”, meaning that the data provider will:

- perform the data protection impact assessment (DPIA) and obtains ethics approval for data inclusion
- be the interface to the data subjects for information and consent around data inclusion
- be responsible for the data curation and characterisation¹⁴³

As a general point we can stress that a DPIA helps identify and mitigate cybersecurity risks before processing begins. It is possible and advisable to map the requirements under the GDPR into specific applicable cybersecurity legislations. For instance, a DPIA must include per GDPR Art. 35(7) “(a) a systematic description of the envisaged processing operations and the purposes of the processing, including, where applicable, the legitimate interest pursued by the controller.”

This will offer the occasion to link the accountable identification of the legal basis for personal data processing to the actual processing framework (that by definition imposes the levels of security for data, to prevent data breach, for instance) identifying in an appropriate document (the DPIA) both risks and risk mitigations measures that serves the requirements and controls for the GDPR and other cybersecurity rules where applicable, avoiding duplications and contradictions.

¹⁴³ From ‘Data-governance changes’, June 2025

A DPIA must also include “(b) an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes.”¹⁴⁴

This again offers a framework methodology (that of the DPIA) to assess in one place the (cyber)security duties allocated to the given organization in the Genome EDIC. It allows to streamline the application of the principles of necessity and proportionality across different sets of requirements emanating from different legislations.

The DPIA must include “(c) an assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects.” This certainly offers the proper locus to consider (as requested by the GDPR) the rights and freedoms of data subjects along with the interests of other relevant stakeholders to build a framework of trust in the Genome EDIC.

Finally, the DPIA must have “(d) the measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with [the GDPR] taking into account the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and other persons concerned.”

The DPIA is an opportunity for the controller to create a single document covering points (a) through (d) where to coalesce technical and organizational measures not only required by GDPR rules but also by other relevant legislations. This could be done with a uniform methodology, shareable with guidelines from the Genome EDIC to the 1+MG NCP and possibly, if eventually agreed, common best practices shared with the dedicated Health Data Access Bodies if created by member states (see in EHDS section below).

Now we move from the data security responsibilities of the controller to that of the processor.

Responsibilities of the Processor

The responsibilities of the processor essentially include all the same cybersecurity measures pursuant to Article 32 mentioned above. It includes documentation requirements to demonstrate compliance with the obligations and allow for and contribute to audits, including inspections, conducted by the controller or another auditor mandated by the controller.¹⁴⁵ For the Genome EDIC or any of the stakeholders listed in Table 5, which might be *processors* following the instructions of the controllers, the point is that they also must adopt the security measures that guarantee the same level of data protection as the controller. Therefore, they also can align the cybersecurity strategies to meet this same level.

¹⁴⁴ GDPR Art. 35(7)

¹⁴⁵ GDPR Art. 28 (3)(h)

Data Protection Officer (DPO)

We take the opportunity to signal yet another GDPR requirement to be analysed for the controller or the processor: appointing a DPO. A DPO is a requirement for the controller and the processor in any case where (per Art. 37):

(a) the processing is carried out by a public authority or body, the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on *a large scale of special categories of data.*

(c) the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9.

Regardless of the eventual public nature eventually assumed by any of the organisations' roles within the architecture of the Genome EDIC, it is clear that those ones assuming the role of data controllers will fall under the requirements of Art. 37(1)(C), (5), i.e., they must appoint a DPO who is qualified with expertise in data protection law and practices.

Thus, it is better to instruct all potential data controllers within the Genome EDIC, 1+MG NCP, and stakeholders to have a DPO - in house or as a contract service - that would be appropriately qualified to fill this role.

Please note that such an organisational measure can naturally be leveraged as a cybersecurity component in the overall management of cybersecurity risks.

Technical Security Measures that the Genome EDIC or the 1+MG NCP could consider:

While reviewing the (cyber)security requirements under the GDPR, we cannot move into an analysis nor a prescription of specific measures. We stress that since the GDPR indicates - often as suggestions - specific safeguards that would serve as well the compliance requirements with other legislations, it is both wise and advisable to consider them in the overall approach to understand and implement as a whole cybersecurity requirements. A quick comparison to the cybersecurity risk-management measures of NIS2 Art. 21(2) or the CER Art. 13 resilience measures, reveals many similarities.

An example of such an approach, to meet GDPR requirements, controllers and processors should implement:

- Data encryption: Both during transit and at rest (using storage encryption), as implied by Art. 32(1)(a).
- Access controls: Implementation of strong identity and access management (IAM) policies and multi-factor authentication (MFA) to ensure that only authorized personnel can access data, supporting the confidentiality requirement in GDPR Art. 32(1)(b).
- Audit trails / monitoring / traceability: This would include logging mechanisms to monitor access and modifications to personal data, supporting both security assessment requirements (GDPR Art. 32(1)(d)) and accountability principles (GDPR Art. 5(2)).

- Regular security assessments: Vulnerability scanning, penetration testing, and security audits to evaluate the effectiveness of security measures, as required by GDPR Art. 32(1)(d).
- Data backup and recovery procedures: Systems to ensure data can be restored in the event of a physical or technical incident, as required by GDPR Art. 32(1)(c).

Similar to the directives CER and NIS2, when something goes wrong with the security, there are mandatory reporting obligations (i.e., ‘incident notification’) depending on the nature of the incident. Under the GDPR this applies to controllers and processors. The duty to inform of a breach can, depending on the severity of the personal data breach, even include informing the data subject. We look at these details next.

Data Breach Notification to Supervisory Authorities

In this section we look at the notification duties that arise in case of a personal data breach that come from either being a controller or a processor. This is a particularly sensitive issue since other cybersecurity legislations discussed in this document require *similar, but not identical*, duties in terms of triggering events, addressees of notifications, timelines, duties towards data subjects or interested parties, and roles of public authorities and police.

Here we map the GDPR duties that data controllers (and processors in some cases) of entities that could potentially be designed to align with reporting duties under NIS2 or CER.

Per GDPR Art. 33(1) Controllers must notify the competent supervisory authority of personal data breaches without undue delay and, where feasible, within 72 hours of becoming aware of the breach, unless the breach is unlikely to result in risks to individuals' rights and freedoms. Article 33(3) specifies that the notification must:

- "(a) describe the nature of the personal data breach including where possible, the categories and approximate number of data subjects concerned and the categories and approximate number of personal data records concerned;
- (b) communicate the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other contact point where more information can be obtained;
- (c) describe the likely consequences of the personal data breach;
- (d) describe the measures taken or proposed to be taken by the controller to address the personal data breach, including, where appropriate, measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects."

When a breach is likely to result in a high risk to individuals' rights and freedoms, controllers must also communicate the breach to the affected *data subjects* without undue delay.¹⁴⁶

¹⁴⁶ The communication must describe in clear, plain language the nature of the breach, contact details of the DPO or another contact point, the likely consequences of the breach, the measures taken or proposed to address the breach and mitigate its effects. GDPR Art. 34(2).

Processors must notify controllers without undue delay after becoming aware of a personal data breach.¹⁴⁷ Although it applies by default as a statutory duty, this obligation must be incorporated into the data processing agreement pursuant to Art. 28(3). Indeed, the processor's timely notification is crucial to enable the controller to meet its 72-hour notification deadline.

Cross-Border Breach Considerations

Since the Genome EDIC will operate across the EU, we raise here the issue for it to consider how it might react in the event of a personal data breach that would occur across multiple member states. This point could, and should, be addressed in a comprehensive cybersecurity strategy, so that no time is lost when an incident occurs in coordinating the triggered responsibilities to inform potentially multiple national authorities of an incident.

If a personal data breach were to occur in multiple member states, the lead supervisory authority mechanism under Article 56 GDPR may apply, where the controller main establishment's Data Protection Authority (DPA) would act as the lead authority. However, each affected local DPA may still need to be informed under certain circumstances. The details of how to evaluate the interaction and competences of multiple supervisor authorities that could be potentially involved is outside the scope of this deliverable. The analysis could eventually be made looking at the application to GDPR Art. 56. Since this is a matter between DPAs, it will not be further discussed here.

Clear guidance on the matter should be offered even when considering that data holders and 1+MG NCP might be fully under national implementation legal rules and, of course, remain fully under the jurisdiction of their member state.

As a good practice, the breach response plan that must be prepared by the data controllers should specify between the processors and controllers how to respond. This information should include identifying the right Data Protection Authorities for different scenarios. We repeat, this can be developed to harmonize response protocols where they overlap with responsibilities of NIS2 and CER where they apply also keeping in mind the requirements for initial reporting and follow up reporting are different. We flag it as a topic for further investigation so that in the event of a cross-border personal data breach, the Genome EDIC, 1+MG NCP, and its various entities would be prepared on how to handle the notification duties that might arise as a controller or as a processor.

This same cross-border analysis for preparation for a cybersecurity incident would also need to be made for NIS2 and CER notification duties, assuming that a 1+MG NCP would be within their scope.

¹⁴⁷ GDPR Art. 33(2)

Designing for GDPR compliance in a cybersecurity strategy: policy recommendations

The Genome EDIC will eventually need to finalise which stakeholders (from the Table 5 above) will act as controllers, joint controllers, or processors at each stage of data processing within the EDIC ecosystem including the 1+MG NCP. These should be documented in formal agreements that comply with GDPR Articles 26 and 28. Even in the absence of a formal agreement, the controller/processor relationship may be determined on the factual circumstances.¹⁴⁸

The Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP will need to develop data processing agreements which clearly delineate responsibilities between parties, specify security measures required at each processing stage, establish breach notification procedures and timelines, and address liability allocation and indemnification. Best cybersecurity practices should be in place by the controller and the processor. Where it exists, achieving a certification scheme for cybersecurity compliance can help to demonstrate compliance with the GDPR (for example, ISO 27001 on security of information management systems).

The decentralized infrastructure will need a security framework across the EDIC that applies appropriate security measures proportionate to the sensitivity of health data. This would include ensuring interoperability of security controls between different actors, and implementing common standards for encryption, access control, and logging. The harmonized breach detection and response procedures would also need to be adopted.

A new legislation, the European Health Data Space, helps implement and coordinate with the GDPR. We review it next to see what cybersecurity duties arise from the new legal roles it creates.

European Health Data Space cybersecurity responsibilities

Title	Regulation (EU) 2025/327 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 February 2025 on the European Health Data Space and amending Directive 2011/24/EU and Regulation (EU) 2024/2847
Short name	EHDS
Art. 1. Subject matter and Scope:	<p>1. This Regulation establishes the European Health Data Space (EHDS) by providing for common rules, standards and infrastructures and a governance framework, with a view to facilitating access to electronic health data for the purposes of primary use of electronic health data and secondary use of those data.</p> <p>2. This Regulation:</p> <p>(a specifies and complements the rights laid down in Regulation (EU)) 2016/679 of natural persons in relation to the primary use and secondary use of their personal electronic health data;</p>

¹⁴⁸ EDPB, Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR, 7 July 2021, available at <https://www.edpb.europa.eu/system/files/202310/EDPB_guidelines_202007_controllerprocessor_final_en.pdf>

	<p>(b lays down common rules for electronic health record systems ('EHR) systems') in relation to two mandatory harmonised software components, namely the European interoperability software component for EHR systems and the European logging software component for EHR systems, as defined in Article 2(2), points (n) and (o), respectively, and for wellness applications which are claimed to be interoperable with EHR systems in relation to those two harmonised software components, as regards primary use of electronic health data;</p> <p>(c) lays down common rules and mechanisms for primary use of electronic health data and secondary use of electronic health data;</p> <p>(d establishes a cross-border infrastructure enabling the primary use of) personal electronic health data across the Union;</p> <p>(e) establishes a cross-border infrastructure for secondary use of electronic health data;</p> <p>(f) establishes governance and coordination mechanisms at Union and national level for both primary use of electronic health data and secondary use of electronic health data.</p>
<p>Art. 2. Definitions:</p>	<p>1. For the purposes of this Regulation, the following definitions apply:</p> <p>(a the definitions of 'personal data', 'processing', 'pseudonymisation',) 'controller', 'processor', 'third party', 'consent', 'genetic data', 'data concerning health' and 'international organisation' laid down in Article 4, of Regulation (EU) 2016/679;</p> <p>(b the definitions of 'healthcare', 'Member State of affiliation', 'Member) State of treatment', 'health professional', 'healthcare provider', 'medicinal product' and 'prescription' laid down in Article 3, of Directive 2011/24/EU;</p> <p>(c) the definitions of 'data', 'access', 'data altruism', 'public sector body' and 'secure processing environment' laid down in Article 2 of Regulation (EU) 2022/868;</p> <p>(d the definitions of 'making available on the market', 'placing on the) market', 'market surveillance', 'market surveillance authority', 'non-compliance', 'manufacturer', 'importer', 'distributor', 'economic</p>

	<p>operator’, ‘corrective action’, ‘recall’ and ‘withdrawal’ laid down in Article 3 of Regulation (EU) 2019/1020;</p> <p>(e)the definitions of ‘medical device’, ‘intended purpose’, ‘instructions for use’, ‘performance’, ‘health institution’ and ‘common specifications’ laid down in Article 2 of Regulation (EU) 2017/745;</p> <p>(f)the definitions of ‘electronic identification’ and ‘electronic identification means’ laid down in Article 3 of Regulation (EU) No 910/2014;</p> <p>(g the definition of ‘contracting authorities’ laid down in Article 2(1),) point (1), of Directive 2014/24/EU;</p> <p>(h the definition of ‘public health’ laid down in Article 3, point (c), of) Regulation (EC) No 1338/2008 Council.</p> <p>2. In addition, for the purposes of this Regulation the following definitions apply:</p> <p>(a ‘personal electronic health data’ means data concerning health and) genetic data, processed in an electronic form;</p> <p>(b ‘non-personal electronic health data’ means electronic health data) other than personal electronic health data, including both data that have been anonymised so that they no longer relate to an identified or identifiable natural person (the ‘data subject’) and data that have never related to a data subject;</p> <p>(c)‘electronic health data’ means personal or non-personal electronic health data;</p> <p>(d ‘primary use’ means the processing of electronic health data for the) provision of healthcare, in order to assess, maintain or restore the state of health of the natural person to whom those data relate, including the prescription, dispensation and provision of medicinal products and medical devices, as well as for relevant social, administrative or reimbursement services;</p> <p>(e)‘secondary use’ means the processing of electronic health data for the purposes set out in Chapter IV of this Regulation, other than the initial purposes for which they were collected or produced;</p>
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	<p>(f) ‘interoperability’ means the ability of organisations, as well as of software applications or devices from the same manufacturer or different manufacturers, to interact through the processes they support, involving the exchange of information and knowledge, without changing the content of the data, between those organisations, software applications or devices;</p> <p>(g) ‘registration of electronic health data’ means the recording of health data in an electronic format, through the manual entry of such data, through the collection of such data by a device, or through the conversion of non-electronic health data into an electronic format, to be processed in an EHR system or a wellness application;</p> <p>h) ‘electronic health data access service’ means an online service, such as a portal or an application for mobile devices, that enables natural persons not acting in a professional capacity to access their own electronic health data or the electronic health data of those natural persons whose electronic health data they are legally authorised to access;</p> <p>(i) ‘health professional access service’ means a service, supported by an EHR system, that enables health professionals to access data of natural persons under their treatment;</p> <p>(j) ‘electronic health record’ or ‘EHR’ means a collection of electronic health data related to a natural person and collected in the health system, processed for the purpose of the provision of healthcare;</p> <p>(k) ‘electronic health record system’ or ‘EHR system’ means any system whereby the software, or a combination of the hardware and the software of that system, allows personal electronic health data that belong to the priority categories of personal electronic health data established under this Regulation to be stored, intermediated, exported, imported, converted, edited or viewed, and intended by the manufacturer to be used by healthcare providers when providing patient care or by patients when accessing their electronic health data;</p> <p>(l) ‘putting into service’ means the first use, for its intended purpose, in the Union of an EHR system covered by this Regulation;</p> <p>(m) ‘software component’ means a discrete part of software which provides a specific functionality or performs specific functions or procedures and which can operate independently or in conjunction with other components;</p> <p>(n) ‘European interoperability software component for EHR systems’ means a software component of the EHR system which provides and receives personal electronic health data under a priority category for</p>
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	<p>primary use established under this Regulation in the European electronic health record exchange format provided for in this Regulation and which is independent of the European logging software component for EHR systems;</p> <p>(o) ‘European logging software component for EHR systems’ means a software component of the EHR system which provides logging information related to access by health professionals or other individuals to priority categories of personal electronic health data established under this Regulation, in the format defined in point 3.2. of Annex II thereto, and which is independent of the European interoperability software component for EHR systems;</p> <p>(p) ‘CE marking of conformity’ means a marking by which the manufacturer indicates that the EHR system is in conformity with the applicable requirements set out in this Regulation and other applicable Union law providing for its affixing pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 765/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council (30);</p> <p>(q ‘risk’ means the combination of the probability of an occurrence of) a hazard causing harm to health, safety or information security and the degree of severity of such harm;</p> <p>(r ‘serious incident’ means any malfunction or deterioration in the) characteristics or performance of an EHR system made available on the market that directly or indirectly leads, might have led or might lead to any of the following:</p> <p>(i the death of a natural person or serious harm to a natural person’s) health;</p> <p>(ii) serious prejudice to a natural person’s rights;</p> <p>(iii) serious disruption of the management and operation of critical infrastructure in the health sector;</p> <p>(t ‘health data holder’ means any natural or legal person, public) authority, agency or other body in the healthcare or the care sectors, including reimbursement services where necessary, as well as any natural or legal person developing products or services intended for the health, healthcare or care sectors, developing or manufacturing wellness applications, performing research in relation to the</p>
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	<p>healthcare or care sectors or acting as a mortality registry, as well as any Union institution, body, office or agency, that has either:</p> <p>(i the right or obligation, in accordance with applicable Union or) national law and in its capacity as a controller or joint controller, to process personal electronic health data for the provision of healthcare or care or for the purposes of public health, reimbursement, research, innovation, policymaking, official statistics or patient safety or for regulatory purposes; or</p> <p>(ii the ability to make available non-personal electronic health data) through the control of the technical design of a product and related services, including by registering, providing, restricting access to or exchanging such data;</p> <p>(u ‘health data user’ means a natural or legal person, including Union) institutions, bodies, offices or agencies, which has been granted lawful access to electronic health data for secondary use pursuant to a data permit, a health data request approval or an access approval by an authorised participant in HealthData@EU;</p> <p>(v)‘data permit’ means an administrative decision issued to a health data user by a health data access body to process certain electronic health data specified in the data permit for specific secondary use purposes, based on conditions laid down in Chapter IV of this Regulation;</p> <p>(w) ‘dataset’ means a structured collection of electronic health data;</p> <p>(x)‘dataset of high impact for secondary use’ means a dataset the re-use of which is associated with significant benefits due to its relevance for health research;</p> <p>(y)‘dataset catalogue’ means a collection of dataset descriptions, arranged in a systematic manner and including a user-oriented public part, in which information concerning individual dataset parameters is accessible by electronic means through an online portal;</p> <p>(z ‘data quality’ means the degree to which the elements of electronic) health data are suitable for their intended primary use and secondary use;</p>
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	<p>(aa ‘data quality and utility label’ means a graphic diagram, including) a scale, describing the data quality and conditions of use of a dataset;</p> <p>(ab) ‘wellness application’ means any software, or any combination of hardware and software, intended by the manufacturer to be used by a natural person, for the processing of electronic health data, specifically for providing information on the health of natural persons, or the delivery of care for purposes other than the provision of healthcare.</p>
<p>Legal roles</p>	<p>Controller (as defined in GDPR) Processor (as defined in GDPR) Third Party (as defined in GDPR)</p> <p>Health Professional (as defined in Directive 2011/24/EU) Healthcare provider (as defined in Directive 2011/24/EU)</p> <p>Public Sector Body (as defined in DGA Reg (EU) 2022/868) Secure Processing Environment (as defined in DGA Reg (EU) 2022/868)</p> <p>Manufacturer/Importer/Distributor/Economic Operator (as defined in Regulation (EU) 2019/1020)</p> <p>Health Institution (as defined in MDR (EU) 2017/745)</p> <p>Authorised participant Health Data holder “Trusted” health data holder (per Art. 72(2).) Health Data user</p> <p>Health Data Access Body (HDAB)¹⁴⁹ Digital Health Authority</p>
<p>Cybersecurity duties for roles that could potentially be</p>	<p>Art. 60 Duties of health data holders: 1. Health data holders shall make relevant electronic health data referred to in Article 51 available upon request to the health data access body, in accordance with a data permit or upon a health data request</p>

¹⁴⁹ EHDS Art. 55 - 59 describe the role and duties of HDAB. The Genome EDIC and nodes are not expected to be in this legal role, but it is listed in the roles for the consortium’s awareness. HDAB will interact with health data users in issuing data permits (per Art. 57(1)(a)) and interact with health data holders to monitor implementation of data management compliance aspects. (Art. 57 “Tasks of health data access bodies”).

<p>in the EDIC and/or nodes¹⁵⁰</p>	<p>2. Health data holders shall put the requested electronic health data referred to in paragraph 1 at the disposal of the health data access body within a reasonable time and no later than three months from the receipt of the request by the health data access body.</p> <p>3. The health data holder shall communicate to the health data access body a description of the dataset it holds. The health data holder shall... check that its dataset description in the national dataset catalogue is accurate and up to date.</p> <p>4. Where a data quality and utility label accompany the dataset pursuant to Article 78, the health data holder shall provide sufficient documentation to the health data access body for that body to verify the accuracy of the label.</p> <p>5. Health data holders of non-personal electronic health data shall provide access to data through trusted open databases to ensure unrestricted access for all users and data storage and preservation. Trusted open public databases shall have in place robust, transparent and sustainable governance and a transparent model of user access.</p> <hr/> <p>Art. 61 Duties of health data users</p> <p>1. Health data users may access and process the electronic health data referred to in Article 51 for secondary use only in accordance with a data permit issued pursuant to Article 68, a health data request approved pursuant to Article 69 or, in situations referred to in Article 67(3), an access approval from the relevant authorised participant in HealthData@EU referred to in Article 75.</p> <p>2. When processing electronic health data within the secure processing environments referred to in Article 73, health data users shall <u>not</u> provide access to the electronic health data, or make those data available to third parties not mentioned in the data permit.</p> <p>3. Health data users shall not re-identify or attempt to re-identify the natural persons to whom the electronic health data obtained by the health data users on the basis of a data permit, a health data request or an access approval by an authorised participant in HealthData@EU relate.</p>
	<p>Art. 75 (4). Health-related research infrastructures or similar infrastructures whose functioning is based on Union law and which provide support for the use of electronic health data for research,</p>

¹⁵⁰ See GDPR for analysis for roles of controller, joint controller and processor.

	<p>polycymaking, statistical, patient safety or regulatory purposes may become authorised participants in HealthData@EU and connect to it.</p> <p>Art. 75(6). Each authorised participant in HealthData@EU shall acquire the required technical capability to connect to and participate in HealthData@EU. They shall comply with the requirements and technical specifications needed to operate HealthData@EU and to allow them to connect to it.</p>
<p>Art. 50 exemption of health data holders</p>	<p>The following categories of health data holders shall be exempt from the obligations on health data holders laid down in (Chapter 6- secondary use):</p> <p>(a) natural persons, including individual researchers</p> <p>(b legal persons that qualify as microenterprises BUT –</p> <p>) 2. Member states may provide in their national law that the obligations of health data holders laid down in this Chapter apply to the health data holders referred to in paragraph 1 which fall under their jurisdiction.</p> <p>3. Member States may provide in their national law that the duties of certain categories of health data holders are to be fulfilled by <u>health data intermediation entities</u>. In that case, the data shall nevertheless be considered as being made available by several health data holders.</p>
<p>Application to the Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Yes, the Genome EDIC is aiming to be an authorised participant of the EHDS as its long-term sustainability goal. The 1+MG NCP could also potentially be health data holders or data users. It will depend on the internal organization at NCP level.</p> <p>The various implementation regulations for cybersecurity and data interoperability specifications will be published by the Commission by 26 March 2027, including its platform for Secondary Use, HealthData@EU. Genome EDIC and nodes should align its data governance with the adoption of the European Digital Health Wallet, and the rest of eIDAS2 that will be used for access, identification and authentication mechanisms.</p> <p>The rules and definitions for EHR and components could become relevant depending on how the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP develop the ICT tools and/or portal.</p>

Commentary on EHDS (cybersecurity)

The European Health Data Space Regulation (EU) 2025/327, of February 11, 2025, is the first European data space to be enacted into legislation. The EHDS creates a comprehensive framework and platform for the interoperable use of electronic health data across the European Union covering primary use (MyHealth@EU) and secondary use (HealthData@EU). It shall apply from March 26, 2027, but will not apply in full until 2031.¹⁵¹

We narrow the discussion of this large regulation to three parts:

1) Roles that are relevant directly for the Genome EDIC and/or its 1+MG NCP. We will go through each role as defined by the Genome EDIC in its recent project documents, and as set out in the EHDS relevant articles to see how similar they are projected to be, and based on those roles, what are their corresponding cybersecurity duties. We will proceed in the order of Authorised Participant, Data Holders, Data Users, and Manufacturer of an EHR system.

2) We present certain components of the EHDS for the management and functioning of the EHDS that the EDIC and 1+MG NCP need to be aware of in its design of its own data governance to ultimately integrate into the EHDS in any of the roles covered.

3) We comment on two roles to be held by bodies for the implementation and compliance monitoring in the EHDS: Health Data Access Body and Digital Health Authority.

These roles, components, and two bodies are introduced here to help guide the Genome EDIC and its 1+MG NCP when they each consider their cybersecurity strategy and data governance planning (including ICT tools) between now and 2031. Data governance for research is relevant for compatibility with the EHDS as it will be implemented in each Member State by the various Health Data Access Bodies. It is the Member States which must align with the IT infrastructure components and protocols to be published by the European Commission to connect with the platform for the secondary use at HealthData@EU.¹⁵²

Roles introduced in the EHDS that might apply to the Genome EDIC or its 1+MG NCP

Key actors in the EHDS hold specific responsibilities related to data security, but also data governance in terms of data and system interoperability. We look first at what is an “authorised participant” as defined by the EHDS.

Authorised participant. The Genome EDIC may eventually operate within this data space as an authorised participant, but the EHDS implementation will occur in phases with many

¹⁵¹ See Art. 105 for the details on which articles apply at different points in time, with delegated acts and implementing acts to be passed providing the necessary specific rules to meet these different milestones.

¹⁵² EHDS Art. 57(1)(e) lists the tasks of the health data access bodies, including “facilitating cross-border access to electronic health data for secondary use hosted in other Member States through HealthData@EU.”

technical specifications and rules still to be specified in forthcoming implementing acts. The Genome EDIC and its 1+MG NCPs should keep their eyes on these technical specifications for cybersecurity and data governance so that they will develop in a compatible way their own data and decentralised infrastructure.

We list the details here of those acts so that the Genome EDIC will know it needs to follow these rules to meet the status of “authorised participant,” and also for the responsibilities of controllers and processors, and the controllers and processors for the SPE:

By 26 March 2027, the Commission shall, by means of implementing acts, set out:

- (a) requirements, technical specifications and the IT architecture of HealthData@EU, which shall ensure state-of-the-art data security, confidentiality, and protection of electronic health data in HealthData@EU;
- (b) conditions and compliance checks required to be able to join and remain connected to HealthData@EU;
- (c) the minimum criteria that need to be met by the national contact points for secondary use and the authorised participants in HealthData@EU;
- (d) the responsibilities of the controllers and processors participating in HealthData@EU;
- (e) the responsibilities of the controllers and processors for the secure processing environment managed by the Commission;
- (f) common specifications for the architecture of HealthData@EU and for its interoperability with other common European data spaces.¹⁵³

Authorised participants would need to meet these forthcoming technical compatibility standards: “Each authorised participant in HealthData@EU shall acquire the required technical capability to connect to and participate in HealthData@EU. They shall comply with the requirements and technical specifications needed to operate HealthData@EU and to allow them to connect to it.”¹⁵⁴

These are requirements for operating in the cross-border infrastructure. The Genome EDIC, as the central coordinating body will be responsible for defining the common data governance, setting minimum data quality risk and compliance standards, and operating the central user portal and a central Data Access Committee (DAC).¹⁵⁵ Therefore, it is very

¹⁵³ EHDS, Art. 75 (12). This article covers the creation of HealthData@EU. The Genome EDIC and nodes must review this entire article in order to plan for integration.

¹⁵⁴ EHDS Art. 75(6)

¹⁵⁵ “Overview of expected implications of the sustainability vote for the short-term implementation” June 2025.

important that the Genome EDIC creates its cybersecurity practices and data governance rules for itself and its 1+MG NCP to be compatible with the requirements that will be published in the implementing acts from the Commission providing the security and data governance for being an authorised participant.¹⁵⁶ Note that these data standards presumably would apply to the high-value externally governed datasets, the 1+MG Compliant Datasets, and the Genome EDIC Cohort Datasets, as well as the 1+MG IT architecture.¹⁵⁷

It is possible that the 1+MG NCP may operate as data holders or data users, we look at those roles as created in the EHDS next.

Data Holders in the EHDS

We present a few key aspects that the Genome EDIC and its 1+NCP would need to consider on how they might fulfil the legal role for “data holder” for secondary use of health data, and based on that role, what would be the corresponding cybersecurity duties.¹⁵⁸

First it must be understood who / what entity could qualify as a data holder. Per EHDS regulation, health data holders include “any natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body in the healthcare or the care sectors, including reimbursement services where necessary, as well as any natural or legal person developing products or services intended for the health, healthcare or care sectors, developing or manufacturing wellness applications, performing research in relation to the healthcare or care sectors or acting as a mortality registry, as well as any Union institution, body, office or agency, that has either:

- (i) the right or obligation, in accordance with applicable Union or national law and in its capacity as a controller or joint controller, to process personal electronic health data for the provision of healthcare or care or for the purposes of public health, reimbursement, research, innovation, policymaking, official statistics or patient safety or for regulatory purposes; or
- (ii) the ability to make available non-personal electronic health data through the control of the technical design of a product and related services, including by registering, providing, restricting access to or exchanging such data.”¹⁵⁹

¹⁵⁶ The concern on developing data governance for compatibility was already raised in the project. For example: “it is not yet clear to which extent an authorised participant can pursue its own data access governance. 1+MG should therefore at minimum cover the elements required by EHDS but we should strive to be able to keep up our higher standards where applicable.” From *1+MG Data Governance for Research Document to vote on the principal framework*.

¹⁵⁷ These are planned datasets listed in “Overview of expected implications of the sustainability vote for the short-term implementation” June 2025.

¹⁵⁸ Art. 60 covers “Duties of health data holders” but we focus here only on cybersecurity duties.

¹⁵⁹ EHDS Art.2 (2)(t)

These entities must ensure the security of health data under their control, implementing appropriate technical and organizational measures. However, Art. 60 does not create unique cybersecurity duties. The data holders' duties can be summarised as a duty to make available upon request to the HDAB (Health Data Access Body) relevant electronic health data as specified in the data permit.¹⁶⁰

By 26 March 2027, the Commission shall, by means of implementing acts, set out the minimum elements health data holders are to provide for datasets and the characteristics of those elements.¹⁶¹ Even now in Art. 78 there are already provisions on “data quality and utility label”, anticipating cybersecurity requirements, which will be useful for the eventual data holders to prepare their datasets for compatibility.

Per Art. 74, the health data holder shall be deemed controller for the making available of personal electronic health data requested pursuant to Art. 60(1) to the health data access body. This is aligned within the 1+MG project stakeholder (listed in Table 5) description of the “1+MG data holder” which is expected to be an organisation in a Genome EDIC member country that is controller for the disclosure of 1+MG compliant data to users, i.e., is responsible for the access decision.

“Trusted health data holder” is a subcategory of data holder that benefits from a simplified procedure for access to electronic health data held by this type of data holder. This status is achieved by application requesting to be deemed as such, if they meet certain requirements.¹⁶² One of those requirements which might be relevant for the 1+MG NCP as potential (trusted) data holders is that they are able to provide access to health data through a secure processing environment. It should be noted that an NCP might be organized to coordinate several trusted health data holders ensuring a unique policy and a unique SPE at national level. We emphasize this aspect to stress the variability of organizational options that might lead to coordinated results at national and EU levels.

There is an interesting point here to connect to the GDPR roles of processor and controllers. The “trusted health data holder” shall be deemed controller for its processing of personal electronic health data related to the provision of electronic health data to the health data user pursuant to a data permit or a health data request. The trusted health data holder shall be deemed to act as a processor on behalf of the health data user when providing data through a secure processing environment.¹⁶³

¹⁶⁰ EHDS Art. 68 lists the rules on Data Permits. Of relevance to cybersecurity is that the health data *applicant* must demonstrate to the HDAB “sufficient technical and organisational measures” to prevent misuse. Art. 68(1) (e).

¹⁶¹ EHDS Art. 77(4), 78(6)

¹⁶² See EHDS Art. 72(2) for specifics on requirements to be considered a “trusted” data health holder.

¹⁶³ EHDS Art. 74 on “controllership”, para. (2)

Normally the HDAB provides access to the electronic health data in its own secure processing environment.¹⁶⁴ The details on its compliance requirements, including security, could be adopted by the trusted data holders as well. The 1+MG NCP would do well to create security protocols that align with the technical and organisational measures, including security and interoperability spelled out in this Art.73.

Now looking at the “1+MG data holders” description per Table 5 we can see that there is alignment between “data holders” in terms of EHDS and the Genome EDIC expectation for the data holders’ role, at least in terms of the duty to disclose data:

1+MG data holders

National entities who have legal responsibility for data disclosure and therefore are controller for the disclosure. These entities will make the access decisions and have legal agreements with data users.¹⁶⁵

“1+MG data holders can decide on the choice of 1+MG SPE. This means the decision whether or not data are made available also in SPEs outside the country is now in the first place with the 1+MG data holder as controller unless the 1+MG member countries decide to regulate this decision on the national level.

[Data holders] assume responsibility for that choice, i.e. they become liable for the data protection compliance of the SPE that they impose on the user organisation.

[Data holders] assume responsibility for guaranteeing the archiving of data and the availability for reproducibility.”¹⁶⁶

Secure Processing Environments Providers

Two other roles (from Table 5) are related to the processing in SPE, and we list them here next:

SPE network

Genome EDIC’s network of Secure Processing Environments¹⁶⁷

See also above “1+MG data holders” for interaction with SPEs.

SPE providers

“1+MG SPE providers must be able to realise the data use environment for and the ingestion of external high value externally governed data in 1+MG SPEs for the user’s projects, also independent of 1+MG governed data.”¹⁶⁸

¹⁶⁴ EHDS Art. 73 provides more details on the requirements for the SPEs, with more details to be laid out in implementing acts by 26 March 2027.

¹⁶⁵ Ibid. “Data holder” here indicates the legal responsibility, it does not require the entity actually physically holds the dataset. In addition, some data providers or entire countries may still prefer a transfer of controllership for the disclosure to the Genome EDIC.”

¹⁶⁶ Ibid.

¹⁶⁷ Ibid.

¹⁶⁸ Ibid.

It will be important for the Genome EDIC in developing its data governance to keep aligned with requirements for security and technical measures in the SPEs in the EHDS that will eventually be published.

1+MG SPE providers will make up the Genome EDIC's SPE network.¹⁶⁹ The data user / user organisation is expected to be able to access data in the federated 1+MG SPEs.¹⁷⁰ This helps demonstrate that a digital infrastructure will need to integrate concepts of data federation, interoperability and managing an SPE. We look at that definition next.

A Secure Processing Environment is defined as “the physical or virtual environment and organisational means to provide the opportunity to re-use data in a manner that allows for the operator of the secure processing environment to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including to display, storage, download, export of the data and calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms.”¹⁷¹

A number of EU member states have already established SPEs (also known as Trusted Research Environments) but there is no common EU or industry standardization for SPEs.¹⁷² The EHDS offers some rules at this stage, stating such “secure processing environments” must be subject to “technical and organization measures and security and interoperability requirements.... And shall comply with the following security measures listed in EHDS Art. 73:

- (a) the restriction of access to the secure processing environment to authorised natural persons listed in the data permit issued pursuant to Article 68;
- (b) the minimisation of the risk of the unauthorised reading, copying, modification or removal of electronic health data hosted in the secure processing environment through state-of-the-art technical and organisational measures;
- (c) the limitation of the input of electronic health data and the inspection, modification or deletion of electronic health data hosted in the secure processing environment to a limited number of authorised identifiable individuals;
- (d) ensuring that health data users have access only to the electronic health data covered by their data permit, by means of individual and unique user identities and confidential access modes only;
- (e) the keeping of identifiable logs of access to and activities in the secure processing environment for the period necessary to verify and audit all processing operations in that environment; logs of access shall be kept for at least one year;

¹⁶⁹ Overview of expected implications of the sustainability vote for the short-term implementation.

¹⁷⁰ Ibid.

¹⁷¹ DGA Art. 2 (14)

¹⁷² (Rak 2024)

(f) ensuring compliance and monitoring the security measures referred to in this paragraph to mitigate potential security threats.”

We can expect the Commission to provide by March 2027 an implementing act setting out the technical, organisational, information security, confidentiality, data protection and interoperability requirements for these SPEs.¹⁷³ It must cover technical characteristics and tools available to the health data user within the secure processing environments.¹⁷⁴

Nevertheless, if the NCP or the Genome EDIC plan to have a SPE, and this to be connected with the EHDS environment, such cybersecurity requirements must be followed for compatibility and interoperability with the EHDS legal and technological ecosystem. We take this chance to point out that the EHDS provides its own definition of “interoperability” as “the ability of organisations, as well as of software applications or devices from the same manufacturer or different manufacturers, to interact through the processes they support, involving the exchange of information and knowledge, without changing the content of the data, between those organisations, software applications or devices.”¹⁷⁵

Next, we look at “health data user” as presented in the EHDS.

Health data users in the EHDS

‘Health data user’ means a natural or legal person, including Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies, which has been granted lawful access to electronic health data for secondary use pursuant to a data permit, a health data request approval or an access approval by an authorised participant in HealthData@EU.”¹⁷⁶

Health data users must adhere to the limitations specified in their data permits and take responsibility for the security of data under their control, as stipulated in Article 47(3), which prohibits sharing with unauthorized third parties. This puts on health data users the responsibility to keep the data secure, employing measures to ensure confidentiality, integrity and availability. In this case the duty includes keeping the data confidential from unauthorized third parties.

Users (defined by the project) will apply for data through the single-entry point created “portal” of the Genome EDIC.¹⁷⁷

¹⁷³ EHDS Art. 73(5)

¹⁷⁴ EHDS Art. 73(5)

¹⁷⁵EHDS Art. 2(2)(f). By comparison, the Data Act defines ‘Interoperability as “the ability of two or more data spaces or communication networks, systems, connected products, applications, data processing services or components to exchange and use data in order to perform their functions.” Art. 2(40). We discuss later the requirement of ‘interoperability’ as mentioned in different EU legislations.

¹⁷⁶ EHDS Art. 2(2)(u)

¹⁷⁷ “Overview of expected implications of the sustainability vote for the short-term implementation” June 2025.

We compare this EHDS concept of “user” to the stakeholder defined in Table 5 as “user” so that the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP can use consistent terminology and understand which entities that make up its environment might correspond to “users” in the sense of the EHDS:

User (in this phase, the user has the status of a **requester**)

The individual that is seeking access to data in 1+MG SPEs.

User Organisation

The legal entity under which the User is requesting access. User Organisations are expected to be either policy makers in the public sector or entities that support public policy making. These may even include commercial entities, including self-employed consultants.

We have just covered the roles of authorised participant, data holder, trusted data holder, and data user so that the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP can align its security measures and data governance to be up to the same level of security and interoperability. The technical details will be coming out by 26 March 2027 via implementing acts.

Now in the next part of the EHDS analysis we introduce to the Genome EDIC the possibility that cybersecurity requirements might fall on it if it were to be considered a “manufacturer” of the EHR System. This is more cautionary and informative as there is no information at this stage of the B1MGplus project or the ELSI working group discussion that would clearly indicate this type of role will be fulfilled.¹⁷⁸ We will raise this discussion also in the analysis of the CRA and the MDR later in this document.

Manufacturers¹⁷⁹ of EHR Systems: Starting with Article 25, EHDS places responsibility on these entities for the security of their products, both software and hardware components, requiring them to implement appropriate security measures.¹⁸⁰

¹⁷⁸ In the document “1+MG ELSI WG meeting May 2025, “EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC”, it was discussed about the type of software that might be developed: “The Genome EDIC will likely not develop its own software products but may collaborate with other entities for suitable and, if necessary, custom-made products within the framework of the services it will offer.”

¹⁷⁹ The Genome and nodes must also ask themselves if they could fall also into the role of importer or distributor (or other economic actor) in case they are placing the EHR or harmonized software components on the market. They would have duties related to cybersecurity of these components or systems, among many other obligations (Art. 36 – Art.39) that apply for the different economic actors listed in EHDS Art. 26, Art 30 - 35.

¹⁸⁰ EHDS Chapter III covers “EHR Systems and Wellness Applications” that include the security and interoperability requirements of these. The entities working with the Genome EDIC that might develop or use wellness applications connected to the EHR system should read this chapter carefully. We raise it here, but it is too broad to be included in D2.8.

It is important for the 1+MG NCP and Genome EDIC to note that the EHR systems must include also a “European interoperability software component” for the EHR systems¹⁸¹ so that if, now or in the future, they plan to be part of the IT architecture, they need to follow the technical requirements.

These EHR system and component requirements would overlap with similar requirements put on manufacturers/importers/distributors in the Cyber Resilience Act. It potentially would be part of a supply chain traceability for relevant sectors of high criticality in NIS2. Therefore, when developing IT tools and components of those tools, the entity developing it, or modifying it should do an analysis of their roles and duties under these legislations. It is important to note that EHR systems that are developed and used in-house are not placed on the market, and the CRA also thus would not apply to such in-house work.¹⁸²

Next, we leave aside for the moment the focus on “roles” and turn the discussion to components, or features, of the EHDS as it is presented in the EHDS. This is to make the consortium and its entities aware of the components of the EHDS that would need to be considered in their planning for data governance and cybersecurity. Tying in the discussion earlier in this deliverable related to cloud layers and what makes up an “attack surface” we point out here that separate components need to be considered in terms of presenting a potential vulnerability to the confidentiality, integrity and availability of electronic health data. We go through the components below.

[EHDS components that support healthcare delivery and data management that impact cybersecurity:](#)

European electronic health record exchange format. This is important for the Genome EDIC and its entities, including the 1+MG NCP, to follow the technical specifications on the European electronic health record exchange format. “Such format shall be commonly used, machine-readable and allow transmission of personal electronic health data between different software applications, devices and healthcare providers. Such format shall support transmission of structured and unstructured health data.”¹⁸³

Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems: These serve as the foundation for digitized health information storage and sharing, with interoperability requirements to be specified in implementation acts. It is mentioned for completeness here but otherwise not part of our

¹⁸¹ EHDS Art 25(1). Art. 36 covers the information and elements of the common specifications for the harmonized software components of EHR systems. The details will be released in implementing acts by 26 March 2027.

¹⁸² EHDS Rec. 112

¹⁸³ EHDS Art. 25(1)

cybersecurity assessment for the EDIC more than we already mentioned above to raise general awareness for potential manufacturers and other economic operators.

MyHealth@EU platform for primary health data: This establishes mandatory cross-border access to primary health data, requiring mutual recognition of health data across Member States.¹⁸⁴ This infrastructure will replace the existing cross-border framework under Directive 2011/24/EU within six years of the EHDS coming into force. By 26 March 2027, the Commission will adopt measures for the technical development of MyHealth@EU, including detailed rules concerning the security, confidentiality and protection of personal electronic health data.¹⁸⁵

HealthData@EU platform for secondary use: Article 75 introduces a decentralized EU infrastructure specifically designed for secondary use of health data. “The Commission shall develop, deploy and operate a central platform for HealthData@EU by providing information technology services needed to support and facilitate the exchange of information between health data access bodies as part of HealthData@EU.”¹⁸⁶ The interaction with the Genome EDIC and 1+NCP is expected to be via the roles of “authorised participant”, “data holder” and “data user” as analysed above.

European Digital Identity Wallet integration: eIDAS and eIDAS2 together provide for secure access to health data through the EU Digital Identity Wallet (EDIW) system, adding another layer to digital identity management within healthcare.¹⁸⁷ The Commission will eventually issue the requirements via implementing acts for identification and authentication for natural persons and health professionals.¹⁸⁸ The Genome EDIC or its 1+MG NCP would need to meet the requirements for “relying party” if they use the EDIW for accepting credentials for access management, for example, or to provide credentials. EIDAS2 is discussed as a separate legislation below.

Interoperability of components. The EHDS includes interoperability requirements and provides its own definition for interoperability (see EHDS Art. 2(2)(f)). Interoperability as a requirement is mentioned in at least GDPR, the Data Act, Cyber Resilience Act, and Interoperable European Act as well. It is mentioned here as a note, however data interoperability is not strictly part of the definition of cybersecurity, but it is relevant to the data governance that the Genome EDIC will set up. These components will need to be created taking into account their future integration into the EHDS. In the next few years, as

¹⁸⁴ EHDS Art. 23(1)

¹⁸⁵ EHDS Art. 23(5)

¹⁸⁶ EHDS Art. 75(8)

¹⁸⁷ EHDS Art. 16 is on “Identification management. Para. (1) gives the right to natural persons to identify themselves using electronic identification (per eIDAS and eIDAS2).

¹⁸⁸ EHDS Art. 16(2)

the delegated acts and implementing acts are published, the Genome EDIC and entities must watch for technical standards and specifications so they can meet them where relevant. Moreover, as data flows more freely between systems and across borders, security measures will and must evolve to protect information throughout these complex pathways. Clear delineation of each actor's cybersecurity responsibilities becomes crucial for effective implementation.

The point of looking at these different components listed above is to spur the consortium into thinking about how these components could impact cybersecurity. We discussed earlier the concept of the “attack vector.” This is important to keep in mind when planning for the IT infrastructure design to be eventually integrated as part of the EHDS. The attack surface, or vector, for cybersecurity vulnerability expands with each interaction with the digital infrastructure.

This type of planning is valuable for integrating into the EHDS as an Authorised Participant, data holder, data user, or even an EHR manufacturer (or another economic operator). Each entity of the Genome EDIC itself or its nodes as part of its 1+MG IT infrastructure could have responsibilities for prevention and response for cybersecurity incidents which could be separately required by NIS2, CER, GDPR, etc. Anywhere in the infrastructure that processes personal data will have the duties of controller, joint-controller or processor to consider from the GDPR. It would be advantageous for each cybersecurity strategy adopted by the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP to be part of comprehensive planning, addressing the overlapping, or similar duties and to streamline implementation.

Next, we look at legal roles not likely to be held by the Genome EDIC or its 1+MG NCP, but nevertheless they could be significant for the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP to understand because these authorities will control access to the secondary system and monitor compliance. Since the Genome EDIC needs to align its data governance and compatibility with the EHDS, these bodies will impact those technical standards to be met and / or enforced. Thus, we next cover the HDAB and the DHA of the member states.

Health Data Access Body (HDAB): This entity is responsible for the security of data accessed for secondary use (Art. 37) per the data permit and only through the Secure Processing Environment. Art. 39 requires HDABs to minimize the data accessed by users and implement appropriate safeguards. The HDAB is responsible for operating the Secure processing environment in compliance with the requirements listed in Art.73. This requirement is in line with data minimization principle of the GDPR and would be very impactful on how data processing is managed in the EDIC. It is assumed that the EDIC as such is not an HDAB since

it can certainly be an authorized participant. Genome EDIC cannot be a HDAB unless the Member State of the seat does it, but would be very unlikely.

Digital Health Authority (DHA): This role will not be fulfilled by the Genome EDIC or the 1+MG NCP but it will be important to follow its development in each member state.¹⁸⁹ This will be a member state appointed body that will be responsible for overseeing the implementation of the EHDS at the national level for MyHealth@EU, and with EHR systems, including establishing technical standards, adopting technical solutions and monitoring compliance. If the Genome EDIC or its nodes will be part of the EHDS, it is important to be aware of the implementation rules nationally to ensure compliance and compatibility of the data and IT architecture for electronic health data.

Cybersecurity required by Multiple Regulatory Frameworks

We close this discussion of the cybersecurity duties within the EHDS by noting that many legislations could potentially apply to a decentralised IT environment that is supposed to support and/ or deliver electronic health data for secondary use (i.e. Genome EDIC, and its 1+MG IT infrastructure, and 1+MG NCP).

EHDS, NIS2, CER or GDPR have their own rules on how cybersecurity incidents must be reported and managed internally, requiring notification and reporting to different bodies (but there may be some overlaps) under CER, NIS2, GDPR, CRA, etc.

We want to point out though that there are similarities in their approaches to cybersecurity risk management and incident response. One clear example of these similarities is offered in EHDS Recital 112. This addresses how the EHDS complements the CRA to address the same cybersecurity concerns:

EHR systems which are products with digital elements within the meaning of Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 should therefore also comply with the essential cybersecurity requirements set out in that Regulation. The manufacturers of those EHR systems should demonstrate conformity as required by this Regulation. To facilitate that conformity, manufacturers should be allowed to draw up a single set of technical documents containing the elements required by both legal acts. It should be possible to demonstrate conformity of EHR systems with essential cybersecurity requirements laid down in Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 through the assessment framework under this Regulation...

As Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 does not cover Software as a Service (SaaS) directly as such, EHR systems offered through the SaaS licensing and delivery model do not fall within the scope of that Regulation.

While the EHDS regulation does not explicitly define Cloud Service Providers (CSPs) as a separate legal role, their responsibilities could be implied through their cloud services that

¹⁸⁹ Details on DHA tasks can be found in EHDS Art. 19.

might support other defined roles, particularly health data holders and/or data users since data will often be stored in cloud as defined in NIS2. It is necessary to look up and down a supply chain for cybersecurity roles and duties that may carry through to the Genome EDIC or the 1+MG NCP.

So, we can see there are overlaps and gaps emerging from our cybersecurity assessment. It would be a good practice for the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP to take advantage of the synergies where possible in planning their overall cybersecurity strategy.

Implementation Timeline for EHDS

The detailed technical specifications and cybersecurity requirements for many EHDS components will continue to evolve through implementing acts by 26 March 2027.¹⁹⁰

For organizations involved in health data management, including the service providers for the 1+MG IT infrastructure and the developers of the tools and portal, this phased implementation creates both challenges and opportunities. By clarifying these roles and responsibilities that might arise in the EDIC that correspond to roles in the EHDS, we can get a better picture on how the EDIC can integrate eventually to achieve its goal of being an authorised participant.

Next, we look at the CRA, which is a logical segue from the discussion immediately above on the overlapping application of the EHDS and CRA for the EHR (electronic health record) systems.

Cyber Resilience Act

Title	Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013 and (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828
Short name	Cyber Resilience Act
Recitals related to Open-Source software	<p>(16) Products with digital elements provided as part of the delivery of a service for which a fee is charged solely to recover the actual costs directly related to the operation of that service, such as may be the case with certain products with digital elements provided by public administration entities, should not be considered on those grounds alone to be a commercial activity for the purposes of this Regulation...</p> <p>(17) Software and data that are openly shared and where users can freely access, use, modify and redistribute them or modified versions thereof, can contribute to research and innovation in the market. To foster the</p>

¹⁹⁰ As we mentioned in an earlier footnote, by March 2027, the Commission will establish comprehensive requirements for secure processing environments through implementing acts as specified in Art. 73(5).

development and deployment of free and open-source software, in particular by microenterprises and small and medium-sized enterprises, including start-ups, individuals, not-for-profit organisations, and academic research organisations, the application of this Regulation to products with digital elements qualifying as free and open-source software supplied for distribution or use in the course of a commercial activity should take into account the nature of the different development models of software distributed and developed under free and open-source software licences.

(18) Free and open-source software is understood as software the source code of which is openly shared and the licensing of which provides for all rights to make it freely accessible, usable, modifiable and redistributable. Free and open-source software is developed, maintained and distributed openly, including via online platforms. In relation to economic operators that fall within the scope of this Regulation, only free and open-source software made available on the market, and therefore supplied for distribution or use in the course of a commercial activity, should fall within the scope of this Regulation. The mere circumstances under which the product with digital elements has been developed, or how the development has been financed, should therefore not be taken into account when determining the commercial or non-commercial nature of that activity. More specifically, for the purposes of this Regulation and in relation to the economic operators that fall within its scope, to ensure that there is a clear distinction between the development and supply phases, the provision of products with digital elements qualifying as free and open-source software that are not monetised by their manufacturers should not be considered to be a commercial activity. Furthermore, the supply of products with digital elements qualifying as free and open-source software components intended for integration by other manufacturers into their own products with digital elements should be considered to be made available on the market only if the component is monetised by its original manufacturer.

For instance, the mere fact that an open-source software product with digital elements receives financial support from manufacturers or that manufacturers contribute to the development of such a product should not in itself determine that the activity is of commercial nature....

Finally, for the purposes of this Regulation, the development of products with digital elements qualifying as free and open-source software by not-for-profit organisations should not be considered to be a commercial activity provided that the organisation is set up in such a way that

	<p><u>ensures that all earnings after costs are used to achieve not-for-profit objectives.</u></p> <p>(20) The sole act of hosting products with digital elements on open repositories, including through package managers or on collaboration platforms, does not in itself constitute the making available on the market of a product with digital elements. Providers of such services should be considered to be distributors only if they make such software available on the market and hence supply it for distribution or use on the Union market in the course of a commercial activity.</p>
Art. 1 Subject matter:	<p>This Regulation lays down:</p> <p>(a rules for the making available on the market of products with digital) elements to ensure the cybersecurity of such products;</p> <p>(b essential cybersecurity requirements for the design, development and) production of products with digital elements, and obligations for economic operators in relation to those products with respect to cybersecurity;</p> <p>(c)essential cybersecurity requirements for the vulnerability handling processes put in place by manufacturers to ensure the cybersecurity of products with digital elements during the time the products are expected to be in use, and obligations for economic operators in relation to those processes;</p> <p>(d rules on market surveillance, including monitoring, and enforcement) of the rules and requirements referred to in this Article</p>
Art. 2. Scope:	<p>This Regulation applies to products with digital elements made available on the market, the intended purpose or reasonably foreseeable use of which includes a direct or indirect logical or physical data connection to a device or network.</p> <p>It does <u>not</u> apply to products with digital elements covered by Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (Medical devices regulation)</p>
Annex 1	<p>Pt. 1 Cybersecurity requirements relating to the properties of products with digital elements</p> <p>(1)Products with digital elements shall be designed, developed and produced in such a way that they ensure an appropriate level of cybersecurity based on the risks.</p> <p>Pt. 2 Vulnerability handling requirements for manufacturers</p>
Annex 2	Information and instructions to the user
Annex 3	Important products with Digital Elements

	<p>Class I. (see annex for the full lists of digital products)</p> <p>Identity management systems and privileged access management software and hardware, including authentication and access control readers, including biometric readers</p> <p>Standalone and embedded browsers</p> <p>Network management systems</p> <p>Physical and virtual network interfaces</p> <p>Operating systems</p> <p>Class II.</p> <p>1. Hypervisors and container runtime systems that support virtualised execution of operating systems and similar environments</p>
Annexes 4 -8	See regulation for details
Art.3 Definitions:	(1)'product with digital elements' means a software or hardware product and its remote data processing solutions, including software or hardware components being placed on the market separately;
	(3) Cybersecurity means the activities necessary to protect network and information systems, the users of such systems, and other persons affected by cyber threats
	(4)'software' means the part of an electronic information system which consists of computer code;
	<p>(5)'hardware' means a physical electronic information system, or parts thereof capable of processing, storing or transmitting digital data;</p> <p>(6)'component' means software or hardware intended for integration into an electronic information system;</p> <p>(7)'electronic information system' means a system, including electrical or electronic equipment, capable of processing, storing or transmitting digital data;</p> <p>(8)'logical connection' means a virtual representation of a data connection implemented through a software interface;</p> <p>(9)'physical connection' means a connection between electronic information systems or components implemented using physical means, including through electrical, optical or mechanical interfaces, wires or radio waves;</p>

	<p>(10) 'indirect connection' means a connection to a device or network, which does not take place directly but rather as part of a larger system that is directly connectable to such device or network;</p> <p>(11) 'end-point' means any device that is connected to a network and serves as an entry point to that network;</p> <p>(12) 'economic operator' means the manufacturer, the authorised representative, the importer, the distributor, or other natural or legal person who is subject to obligations in relation to the manufacture of products with digital elements or to the making available of products with digital elements on the market in accordance with this Regulation;</p> <p>(13) 'manufacturer' means a natural or legal person who develops or manufactures products with digital elements or has products with digital elements designed, developed or manufactured, and markets them under its name or trademark, whether for payment, monetisation or free of charge;</p> <p>(14) 'open-source software steward' means a legal person, other than a manufacturer, that has the purpose or objective of systematically providing support on a sustained basis for the development of specific products with digital elements, qualifying as free and open-source software and intended for commercial activities, and that ensures the viability of those products;</p> <p>(21) 'placing on the market' means the first making available of a product with digital elements on the Union market;</p> <p>(22) 'making available on the market' means the supply of a product with digital elements for distribution or use on the Union market in the course of a commercial activity, whether in return for payment or free of charge;</p>
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	<p>(30) 'substantial modification' means a change to the product with digital elements following its placing on the market, which affects the compliance of the product with digital elements with the essential cybersecurity requirements ...</p> <p>(33) 'market surveillance authority' means a market surveillance authority as defined in Article 3, point (4), of Regulation (EU) 2019/1020;</p> <p>(37) 'cybersecurity risk' means the potential for loss or disruption caused by an incident and is to be expressed as a combination of the magnitude of such loss or disruption and the likelihood of occurrence of the incident;</p> <p>(38) 'significant cybersecurity risk' means a cybersecurity risk which, based on its technical characteristics, can be assumed to have a high likelihood of an incident that could lead to a severe negative impact, including by causing considerable material or non-material loss or disruption;</p> <p>(39) 'software bill of materials' means a formal record containing details and supply chain relationships of components included in the software elements of a product with digital elements;</p> <p>(40) 'vulnerability' means a weakness, susceptibility or flaw of a product with digital elements that can be exploited by a cyber threat;</p> <p>(41) 'exploitable vulnerability' means a vulnerability that has the potential to be effectively used by an adversary under practical operational conditions;</p> <p>(42) 'actively exploited vulnerability' means a vulnerability for which there is reliable evidence that a malicious actor has exploited it in a system without permission of the system owner;</p> <p>(43) 'incident' means an incident as defined in Article 6, point (6), of Directive (EU) 2022/2555;</p> <p>(44) 'incident having an impact on the security of the product with digital elements' means an incident that negatively affects or is capable of</p>
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	<p>negatively affecting the ability of a product with digital elements to protect the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of data or functions;</p> <p>(46) 'cyber threat' means a cyber threat as defined in Article 2, point (8), of Regulation (EU) 2019/881;</p> <p>(47) 'personal data' means personal data as defined in Article 4, point (1), of Regulation (EU) 2016/679;</p> <p>(48) 'free and open-source software' means software the source code of which is openly shared and which is made available under a free and open-source licence which provides for all rights to make it freely accessible, usable, modifiable and redistributable;</p>
<p>Legal Roles</p>	<p>Manufacturer Importer Distributor</p> <p>A person who substantially modifies a product with digital elements and makes that product available on the market shall be considered to be a manufacturer for the purposes of this Regulation.</p> <p>Open-source software stewards (Art. 24) User</p>
<p>Cybersecurity duties of roles that could potentially be in EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Art. 13¹⁹¹. Obligations of Manufacturers shall ensure that a product with digital elements has been designed, developed and produced in accordance with the essential cybersecurity requirements set out in Part I of Annex I.</p> <p>Art. 13(2) manufacturers shall undertake an assessment of the cybersecurity risks associated with a product with digital elements and take the outcome of that assessment into account during the planning, design, development, production, delivery and maintenance phases of the product with digital elements with a view to minimising cybersecurity risks, preventing incidents and minimising their impact, including in relation to the health and safety of users.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conformity assessment (Art. 32) & Annex VIII - CE marking (Art. 28) and Annex V & VI - technical documentation (Art.31) & Annex VII <p>Art. 14 Reporting obligations of manufacturers Art. 15 Voluntary reporting</p>

¹⁹¹ See full article for extensive description on information to be provided, etc.

	<p>Art 19. Obligations of importers</p> <p>Art. 20. Obligations of distributors</p> <p>Art. 24 Obligations of open-source software stewards shall put in place and document in a verifiable manner a cybersecurity policy</p>
<p>Timeline</p> <p>Art. 71</p>	<p>Regulation shall apply from 11 December 2027</p> <p>Art.14 “Reporting obligations of manufacturers” shall apply from 11 September 2026</p>
<p>Application to the Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>The applicability of the CRA to the 1+MG IT infrastructure cannot be determined yet. This law will need close analysis on tools / software / network and information systems to be developed and whether digital products are ‘placed on the market’. The legal analysis will need to be reconsidered at various decision points before the software and hardware tools will be developed and services designed or eventually put into use at later stages. Still this analysis will help to look up and down the supply chain for ITC components, including software, and to perform a cybersecurity analysis to cover information required to the end-user. The Genome EDIC and its 1+MG NCP or other entities that will develop EHR system or system components can develop their cybersecurity, documentation, and technical requirements, and incident reporting requirements in a comprehensive manner, taking into account even possible similar or overlapping duties that might come up under NIS2 as part of a digital supply chain to critical entities.</p>

Commentary on the Cyber Resilience Act

The Cyber Resilience Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/2847) introduces mandatory cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and software applications, to ensure their security throughout their entire lifecycle. The Cyber Resilience Act entered into force on 10 December 2024. The main obligations introduced by the Act will apply from 11 December 2027.

It must be analysed together with the Cybersecurity Act (next table below). The CRA aims to enhance the overall cybersecurity posture of digital health products available in the EU market.

The CRA places obligations on manufacturers, importers, and distributors regarding security by design and default, vulnerability handling, regular testing, the provision of security updates, and incident reporting for actively exploited vulnerabilities and severe incidents.

Art. 2 of the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) defines the scope of application of the regulation. It provides that the regulation “applies to products with digital elements *made available on the market*, the intended purpose or reasonably foreseeable use of which includes a direct or indirect logical or physical data connection to a device or network.”

“Product with digital elements” refers to any “software or hardware product and its remote data processing solutions, including software or hardware components being placed on the market separately”.¹⁹²

To explain this scope more fully we see in the recital that manufacturers’ obligations relate to both “products that can be connected physically via hardware interfaces and products that are connected logically, such as via network sockets, pipes, files, application programming interfaces or any other types of software interface.”¹⁹³ The goal is to safeguard against a broader attack surface and protect against those cyber threats which could propagate through products with digital elements before reaching a certain target, for example by “chaining together multiple vulnerability exploits, manufacturers should also ensure the cybersecurity of products with digital elements that are only indirectly connected to other devices or networks.”¹⁹⁴

Will the EDIC be a manufacturer, importer or distributor of “products with digital elements”?

‘Manufacturer’ is defined in the CRA as a natural or legal person who develops or manufactures products with digital elements or has products with digital elements designed, developed or manufactured, and markets them under its name or trademark, whether for payment, monetisation or free of charge.”¹⁹⁵

The CRA needs to be understood in the context of the New Legislative Framework and follows the rules of “placing on the market” under the Union harmonisation legislation.¹⁹⁶ “Placing a product on the market” requires that there be an offer or an agreement between two or more legal or natural persons for the transfer of ownership, possession or any other property right concerning the product in question; it requires that the manufacturing stage has been completed. This transfer could be for payment or free of charge.¹⁹⁷

The Blue Guide explains that “Placing on the market is considered not to take place where a product is: manufactured for one’s own use *unless* Union harmonisation legislation covers products manufactured for own use in its scope.”¹⁹⁸

For any software or system to be created for the EDIC, it should be investigated if the CRA obligations would apply to manufacturers who create products with digital elements for “one’s own use.” This is also in line with the EHDS rule for EHR that are developed in-house (EHDS Rec. 112).

Open-Source Software under the CRA

We just first took a brief look at whether any software, proprietary or not, could be part of a commercial activity which requires “placing on the market.” A separate issue is if such

¹⁹² CRA. Art. 3(1)

¹⁹³ CRA Rec. 9

¹⁹⁴ CRA Rec. 9

¹⁹⁵ CRA Art 3. (13)

¹⁹⁶ Commission Notice The ‘Blue Guide’ on the implementation of EU product rules 2022, Sec. 2.3.

¹⁹⁷ The Blue Guide, Sec. 2.3

¹⁹⁸ The Blue Guide

software is or partially is made of open source software, and if so, how does the CRA apply or not.

The CRA provides in Art. 3(48) that ‘free and open-source software’ is software the source code of which is openly shared and which is made available under a free and open-source licence which provides for all rights to make it freely accessible, usable, modifiable and redistributable.” The use of such software still has some requirements that are spelled out in specific licenses.¹⁹⁹

Regarding the software to be developed for the infrastructure, the ELSI working group for GDI has commented that the Genome EDIC will likely not develop its own software products but may collaborate with other entities for suitable and, if necessary, custom-made products within the framework of the services it will offer and will otherwise rely on open-source²⁰⁰ tools developed by third parties.²⁰¹ The software it will develop jointly will be open source. It is expected that the Genome EDIC will rely mostly on freely available third-party software, which is usually developed by the academic or for a non-profit environment.²⁰²

As for the open-source software custom-designed for the Genome EDIC in the course of the collaboration with other entities, the applicability of the Cyber Resilience Act may depend on the nature of these collaborative relationships (e.g., whether Genome EDIC has a commercial relationship with a service provider to develop the software on its behalf). Under this situation, the EDIC would be potentially the user, not the manufacturer, unless its actions to “collaborate” could be considered manufacturing jointly. This would require a much closer analysis based on the real work to be executed and any transfer of property.

We would flag here for the consortium to be aware of the CRA recitals 16 – 20, which we have included in part in the above table, even though they are not legally binding, they can aid in understanding the intention of CRA. How open-source software gets integrated into other software, and whether it is part of a commercial activity or placed on the market will be a complex, thorny analysis, and will need to be done probably per each software released that could constitute a “product with a digital element” under the CRA.²⁰³

¹⁹⁹ Mattis van ‘t Schip, *The Cyber Resilience Act and Open-Source Software: A Fine Balancing Act*, 16 (2025) JIPITEC 73 para 1, *citing in footnote 19* P McCoy Smith, ‘Copyright, Contract, and Licensing in Open Source’ in Amanda Brock (ed), *Open Source Law, Policy and Practice* (2nd edn, Oxford University Press 2022).

²⁰⁰ CRA Recital 18 of the Cyber Resilience Act provides more insight into “free and open-source software.”

²⁰¹ 1+MG ELSI WG meeting May 2025, “EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC”

²⁰² 1+MG ELSI WG meeting May 2025, “EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC”

²⁰³ For a discussion on the nuances of how the CRA applies (or doesn’t) to open-source software, please see Mattis van ‘t Schip (2025). Section C of the article specifically addresses CRA and open-source software security.

Initial legal analysis has investigated existing and proposed sectoral EU legislation addressing challenges and duties to secure IoT devices and even its supply chain under the CRA and NIS2.²⁰⁴ NIS2 and CRA work together to cover cybersecurity regulatory gaps for products with digital elements.²⁰⁵ If the Genome EDIC were to rely on open-source software developed by third parties, or in collaboration with such third parties, the Cyber Resilience Act may not apply at all to Genome EDIC. However, since it is expected that the EDIC will operate a secure portal for the nodes or other software tools, it is recommended at the earliest planning stages to check with CRA terms for applicability.

We move next toward the foundation in the legislation that establishes cybersecurity requirements in the EU. The Cybersecurity Act from 2019 is what gives the legal authority and definitions to the cybersecurity regulation, like CRA, CER, and NIS2. It sets up ENISA as a permanent authority and establishes a cybersecurity certification scheme. The cybersecurity certification scheme is important to understand what might come in the future for EU requirements for cybersecurity compliance. Therefore, this table does not have its own commentary section below.

Cybersecurity Act

Title	Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013
Short name	Cybersecurity Act
Art. 1. Subject matter and Scope:	<p>Article. 1: “With a view to ensuring the proper functioning of the internal market while aiming to achieve a high level of cybersecurity, cyber resilience and trust within the Union, this Regulation lays down:</p> <p>(b a framework for the establishment of European cybersecurity) certification schemes for the purpose of ensuring an adequate level of cybersecurity for ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes in the Union, as well as for the purpose of avoiding the fragmentation of the internal market with regard to cybersecurity certification schemes in the Union.”</p>
Art. 2 Definitions:	

²⁰⁴ (Chiara 2022)

²⁰⁵ For a discussion on the combined security of EHDS plus CRA on EHS, and wellness devices and applications to be connected to the EHDS, see F Casarosa, “European Health Data Space – Is the Proposed Certification System Effective against Cyber Threats?” European Journal of Risk Regulation. <https://doi.org/10.1017/err.2024.25>

	<p>(1) 'cybersecurity' means the activities necessary to protect network and information systems, the users of such systems, and other persons affected by cyber threats;</p> <p>(2) 'network and information system' means a network and information system as defined in point (1) of Article 4 of Directive (EU) 2016/1148;</p> <p>(4) 'operator of essential services' means an operator of essential services as defined in point (4) of Article 4 of Directive (EU) 2016/1148;</p> <p>(5) 'digital service provider' means a digital service provider as defined in point (6) of Article 4 of Directive (EU) 2016/1148;</p> <p>(6) 'incident' means an incident as defined in point (7) of Article 4 of Directive (EU) 2016/1148;</p> <p>(7) 'incident handling' means incident handling as defined in point (8) of Article 4 of Directive (EU) 2016/1148;</p> <p>(8) 'cyber threat' means any potential circumstance, event or action that could damage, disrupt or otherwise adversely impact network and information systems, the users of such systems and other persons;</p> <p>(9) 'European cybersecurity certification scheme' means a comprehensive set of rules, technical requirements, standards and procedures that are established at Union level and that apply to the certification or conformity assessment of specific ICT products, ICT services or ICT processes;</p> <p>(10) 'national cybersecurity certification scheme' means a comprehensive set of rules, technical requirements, standards and procedures developed and adopted by a national public authority and that apply to the certification or conformity assessment of ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes falling under the scope of the specific scheme;</p> <p>(11) 'European cybersecurity certificate' means a document issued by a relevant body, attesting that a given ICT product, ICT service or ICT process has been evaluated for compliance with specific security requirements laid down in a European cybersecurity certification scheme;</p> <p>(12) 'ICT product' means an element or a group of elements of a network or information system;</p> <p>(13) 'ICT service' means a service consisting fully or mainly in the transmission, storing, retrieving or processing of information by means of network and information systems;</p> <p>(14) 'ICT process' means a set of activities performed to design, develop, deliver or maintain an ICT product or ICT service;</p>
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	(21) ‘assurance level’ means a basis for confidence that an ICT product, ICT service or ICT process meets the security requirements of a specific European cybersecurity certification scheme, indicates the level at which an ICT product, ICT service or ICT process has been evaluated but as such does not measure the security of the ICT product, ICT service or ICT process concerned;
Legal roles	Manufacturer or provider of ICT products, services or processes
Cybersecurity duties of roles that could potentially be in EDIC and/or nodes	Art. 53(1) A manufacturer may conduct a conformity self-assessment on compliance of the ICT product, service or process where the assurance level is allowed to be “basic.” Art. 55. A manufacturer or provider for which an EU statement of conformity has been issued shall make publicly available the supplementary cybersecurity to assist end users, etc.
Application to the Genome EDIC and/or nodes	The Cybersecurity Act is to be read together with the CRA in case 1+MG IT infrastructure will be deemed a manufacturer or provider of certified ICT products, services or processes. See article 54- 56 on duties of manufacturers or providers of ICT products covered by a certification scheme. The CA gives the mandate to ENISA, and is a legal framework that sets out basic EU cybersecurity definitions. Being a fundamental start to EU Cybersecurity regulation and risk assessment, it must be understood well and paired in analysis with all these other legislations.

Other EU legislation with impact on cybersecurity requirements

We cover next a shorter analysis on a series of legislations that in some way also relate to cybersecurity, but are not treated as extensively as the above tables and commentary. There are many cross references though, such as to EIDAS2 and DGA.

EIDAS2 Digital Wallet for verification and access to EHDS

Regulation (EU) 2024/1183 (eIDAS2) was enacted on 30 April 2024, amending EU Regulation (EU) 910/2014 (eIDAS). This is the EU framework regulating Trust Service Providers, and the new version introduced the European Digital Identity Wallet.

The Digital Wallet will be a means “which allows the user to securely store, manage and validate person identification data and electronic attestations of attributes for the purpose of providing them to relying parties and other users of European Digital Identity Wallets, and

to sign by means of qualified electronic signatures or to seal by means of qualified electronic seals.”²⁰⁶

This definition helps explain the relationship between the *users* and the *relying parties*, which are two roles that we can anticipate will be part of the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP from internal or external users / access.

- “user” means a natural or legal person, or a natural person representing another natural person or a legal person, that uses trust services or electronic identification means provided in accordance with this Regulation;²⁰⁷
- “relying party” means a natural or legal person that relies upon electronic identification, European Digital Identity Wallets or other electronic identification means, or upon a trust service.²⁰⁸

The EDIW will allow individuals and legal persons to officially identify themselves online, share official and legally valid documents, digitally sign and seal, and access public administration and private services online, updating the current framework under eIDAS. EIDAS and eIDAS 2 are crucial for ensuring secure authentication and identification within the European Health Data Space. Electronic signatures, electronic seals, and website authentication, which are key components of eIDAS, contribute to the integrity and authenticity of health data and related transactions.

[EHDS Identification Management and eIDAS 2](#)

EHDS Article 3 on “Right of natural persons to access their personal electronic health data” provides that where a natural person uses personal health data access services, that natural person shall have the right to identify electronically. The requirements for the interoperable, cross-border identification and authentication mechanism for natural persons and health professionals, in accordance with eIDAS2 shall be determined by the Commission. This is to facilitate the transferability of personal electronic health data in a cross-border context. EHDS Art. 16 gives details on the “Identification management” for electronic health data access, but the measures will be coming out in the future in implementation acts giving requirements for interoperable, cross-border identification and authentication mechanisms for natural persons and health professionals.

The application of the eIDAS 2 for the use of the Digital Wallet in the sphere of the Genome EDIC will also depend on if the EDIC would be accessed by “health care professionals.” As eIDAS2 is still waiting on implementation regulations to set the technical aspects for its use, we mention it as something to watch for as the 1+MG IT infrastructure comes into the picture. The key point is that it is expected to be a technology to substantially fortify cybersecurity of authentication and access management.

²⁰⁶ eIDAS2 Art. 1(3)(j)(42)

²⁰⁷ eIDAS2 Art. 1 (3)(b)(5a)

²⁰⁸ eIDAS2 Art. 1 (3)(c)(6)

EU Data Act

The EU Data Act (Regulation (EU) 2023/2854) of 13 December 2023, while not primarily focused on cybersecurity, does add data governance requirements that may affect Genome EDIC's operations related to designing for interoperability and data portability with its 1+MG NCP, especially as a potential authorised participant, data holder or data user in the EHDS.

The EU Data Act was created to free up data held by manufacturers in their connected products, both personal and non-personal data. The Data Act has definitions for legal roles that might apply for cybersecurity responsibilities as data holder, data recipient, third party and arguably as a public sector body. We consider these definitions here:

A **'data holder'** means a natural or legal person that has the right or obligation, in accordance with this Regulation, applicable Union law or national legislation adopted in accordance with Union law, to use and make available data, including, where contractually agreed, product data or related service data which it has retrieved or generated during the provision of a related service."²⁰⁹

A **"data recipient"** is a natural or legal person, acting for purposes which are related to that person's trade, business, craft or profession, other than the user of a connected product or related service, to whom the data holder makes data available, including a third party following a request by the user to the data holder or in accordance with a legal obligation under Union law or national legislation adopted in accordance with Union law."²¹⁰

A **'public sector body'** means national, regional or local authorities of the Member States and bodies governed by public law of the Member States, or associations formed by one or more such authorities or one or more such bodies."²¹¹

If the Genome EDIC or its 1+MG NCP were to be classified as public sector bodies, Chapters III, IV, and V would not apply. By contrast, while "private sector" is not defined in the Data Act, this can be interpreted as data held by private sector bodies, as distinguished from public sector bodies. This distinction is important to understand which parts of the Data Act might eventually apply to the EDIC. E.g., Article 1(2)(b),(c),(d) state that Chapters III, IV, and V apply to "private sector data."

Assuming for this analysis here that the EDIC will be a public sector body, we look next at its likely data processing activities. The EDIC will have a secure processing environment, but that might *not* be considered Data Processing Services as described under the Data Act. 'Data processing service' follows the same definition of NIS2:

"A digital service that is provided to a customer and that enables ubiquitous and on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable, scalable and elastic computing resources of a centralised, distributed or highly distributed nature that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction;" DA Art. 2(8),

²⁰⁹ DA Art. 2(13)

²¹⁰ DA Art. 2(14)

²¹¹ DA Art. 28. The DGA, EHDS and Interoperable Europe Act use the same definition.

The ELSI working group has shared the opinion that the secure processing environment provided by Genome EDIC would not potentially meet this definition of “data processing environment” because it will not have user-configurable computing resources (Article 2(8)(a)), the services will not be elastically provisioned (Article 2(8)(c)), and the secure processing environment will be controlled and restricted. Based on these planned restrictions of the Secure processing environment of the Genome EDIC, Chapters VI and VII would not be applicable to Genome EDIC's operations.

It is still possible that the EDIC will meet this definition of “data processing service” when analysed for other services and/or operations outside of its secure processing environment. None of these technicalities for the potential architecture are known at this stage and so we raise it here only for awareness of the need for greater analysis.

[EDIC as a participant in the EHDS would involve compliance with the Data Act.](#)

The principal take-away from the EU Data Act at this early stage is its focus on making data portable and interoperable, as an obligation for participants in European Common Data Spaces.

Chapter 8 would apply to participants in data spaces. Essential requirements regarding interoperability of data, of data sharing mechanisms and services, as well as of common European data spaces are in Art. 33, and again it requires planning for interoperability and security of data.

Articles 38 and 39 establish requirements for participants in data spaces, focusing on interoperability standards. As a potential authorized participant in the European Health Data Space (EHDS), Genome EDIC should implement the interoperability requirements outlined in Chapter VIII for aspects not specifically covered by EHDS legislation.

Even once this conclusion is reached that the Data Act might apply to the EDIC itself, and that it might impose obligations on portability and interoperability, we see that little unique or more stringent is added related to cybersecurity measures that would not otherwise be imposed by other legislation, such as NIS2 or GDPR. Technical protection measures on the unauthorized use or disclosure of data. Article 11(1) requires data holders to "implement appropriate technical, legal and organizational measures to prevent unauthorized access" to data they are legally obligated to make available. This embodies a "security by design" principle consistent with Article 25 of the GDPR. Protection of Trade Secrets is required by Article 11(2) specifically mandates that data holders take "necessary measures to preserve the confidentiality of trade secrets." This is particularly relevant for proprietary analysis algorithms and methodologies used in genomic data processing. Obligations for Data Recipients are addressed in Article 12(1), data recipients must use data only for authorized purposes and maintain appropriate security measures. Article 12(3) prohibits unauthorized use or disclosure of non-personal data constituting trade secrets.

Timeline and Implementation. The EU Data Act will apply from September 12, 2025. This provides an implementation period during which the EDIC should assess its potential role as a participant in the European Health Data Space. The EDIC should plan for interoperability

and data portability and obviously implement appropriate technical and organizational measures for data security.

Data Governance Act

Regulation (EU) 2022/868²¹², commonly referred to as the Data Governance Act (DGA), creates a comprehensive framework for enhancing data sharing and reuse between public and *private* sectors. DGA facilitates the reuse of data subject to third-party rights through specialized frameworks in cases where the Open Data Directive (ODD) does not apply, hence the two legislations are complementary. The DGA has 4 main areas it addresses:

- (1) the conditions for reuse of data held by European public sector bodies;
- (2) a notification and supervisory framework for the provision of data intermediation services;
- (3) a framework for voluntary registration mechanism for entities that collect and process data made available on altruistic purposes; and
- (4) a framework for establishing a European board for innovation in data economy.

However, our analysis of the Data Governance Act, if the EDIC is within its scope, is considering only its cybersecurity responsibilities based on the legal roles played by various actors of the EDIC and not related to larger data governance issues to be considered separately.

Article 2 has the following definitions that may be useful for the analysis of whether or not this legislation would apply to EDIC:

(17) defines ‘public sector body’ means the State, regional or local authorities, bodies governed by public law or associations formed by one or more such authorities, or one or more such bodies governed by public law;

(18) ‘bodies governed by public law’ means bodies that have the following characteristics:

(a) they are established for the specific purpose of meeting needs in the general interest, and do not have an industrial or commercial character;

(b) they have legal personality;

(c) they are financed, for the most part, by the State, regional or local authorities, or other bodies governed by public law, are subject to management supervision by those authorities or bodies, or have an administrative, managerial or supervisory board, more than half of whose members are appointed by the State, regional or local authorities, or by other bodies governed by public law;

A first step then, is to understand would the EDIC be a “public sector body”²¹³, as we mentioned in the Data Act analysis. Imagine, yes, then it would have under the DGA an obligation to process data “within a secure processing environment” (Art. 5(10)).

²¹² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32022R0868>

²¹³ DA, EHDS, and Interoperable Europe Act use the same definition.

The Data Governance Act also gives a definition in Art 2(20) of a **‘secure processing environment’**:

“the physical or virtual environment and organisational means to ensure compliance with Union law, such as Regulation (EU) 2016/679, in particular with regard to data subjects’ rights, intellectual property rights, and commercial and statistical confidentiality, integrity and accessibility, as well as with applicable national law, and to allow the entity providing the secure processing environment to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including the display, storage, download and export of data and the calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms.”

This is another cross reference from DGA to GDPR that might apply to the EDIC will be required to make secondary health data available in a “secure processing environment” per the EHDS. However, that duty, as explained in EHDS Art. 73, for the Health Data Access Bodies. It is not yet clear if the EDIC would have that role.

Even before the full implementation of the EHDS, operating a Secure Process Environment would have its own cybersecurity duties that would need to be fulfilled by whomever operates it, regardless of the status of HDAB or not.

A novelty of the DGA is its framework allowing the establishment of formally recognized organizations operating as data altruism organizations. These organizations are listed in national public registers maintained by competent authorities in each member state, with additional reporting requirements to a centralized register managed by the European Commission for informational purposes. Candidates seeking recognition as data altruism organizations are required to meet the criteria in DGA Art 18.

Data altruism refers to “the voluntary sharing of data on the basis of the consent of data subjects to process personal data pertaining to them, or permissions of data holders to allow the use of their non-personal data without seeking or receiving a reward that goes beyond compensation related to the costs that they incur where they make their data available for objectives of general interest as provided for in national law, where applicable, such as healthcare...facilitating the development, production and dissemination of official statistics, improving the provision of public services, public policy-making or scientific research purposes in the general interest”.

“Data altruistic organizations” within the meaning of the DGA would have **specific responsibilities concerning transparency and the protection of the rights of data subjects and data owners**. Data controllers are required to provide data subjects clear and comprehensible information prior to any data processing. This information must include details about the general interest objectives and, where applicable, the specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes for which the data will be processed, as well as the purposes for which data subjects’ consent to the processing of their data by a data user. DGA Art. 21. We see though that these requirements are part of the same GDPR rules on informed consent for data processing.

DGA Article 7 specifies that the member states must designate specific competent bodies who will support the DGA implementation by providing technical guidance for data storage and data processing and techniques that ensure privacy, confidentiality, integrity, and accessibility of personal data, state-of-the-art privacy-preserving methods, deletion of commercially confidential information, support for consent and permission requests for reuse, and relevant contractual commitments.

From the ELSI analysis, it is not clear yet how the EDIC could fall within the scope of the Data Governance Act. Article 1 which defines the scope: “a first set of rules applies to public sector bodies, a second set of rules to the data intermediation service providers, and a third one to entities which collect and process data made available for altruistic purposes.” If the Genome EDIC or its 1+MG NCP are considered public sector bodies, that will determine how some parts of the DGA apply. If, however, the Genome EDIC or its 1+MG NCP could operate as a data altruistic organisation, then those parts of the DGA would apply. The point is that the applicability of the DGA will depend on the choice of the legal basis under which the EDIC is operating. The assessment of the applicability of the obligations concerning public sector bodies to the EDIC would require further investigation.

Another point to be analysed is also how data re-use would be regulated either under the DGA article 5 “Conditions for Re-Use” or how it would be instead, or in parallel, regulated under the data re-use in HealthData@EU of Article 52, which introduces a decentralized EU infrastructure specifically designed for secondary use of health data.

Since our scope in this deliverable is on cybersecurity duties imposed by the DGA, we look at only that aspect here. At this time, it does not seem to impose unique cybersecurity responsibilities that would not otherwise be required by NIS2 or GDPR or EHDS or even the Cyber Resilience Act potentially.

Interoperable Europe Act

Regulation (EU) 2024/903 of 13 March 2024 “lays down measures that promote the cross-border interoperability of trans-European digital public services, thus contributing to the interoperability of the underlying network and information systems by establishing common rules and a governance framework.”²¹⁴ The Regulation aims to remove barriers, incompatibilities and the fragmentation of digital public services. This will align with the interoperability between public sector institutions and presumably the use of the Digital Wallet for citizens.²¹⁵

²¹⁴ IEA Art. 1(1)

²¹⁵ IEA Rec. 6: “Key public services with trans-European relevance are intended to give rise to major benefits for citizens where they become interoperable across borders. Examples of trans-European digital public services are services that, by means of cross-border exchanges of data, allow for the mutual recognition of academic diplomas or professional qualifications, exchanges of vehicle data for road safety, access to social security and health data, including pandemic and vaccination certificates, access to single window systems, the exchange of information related to taxation, customs, public tender accreditation, digital driving licenses or commercial registers, and in general all those services that implement the ‘once-only’ principle to access and exchange cross-border data.” All of these documents are expected to be used with the EIDW as introduced in eIDAS2.

Interoperable Europe Act establishes a comprehensive framework for public sector interoperability, which seems it would extend to the EHDS, since its board is contributing to the interoperability design of that data space²¹⁶. The European Health Data Space Board has the task to enhance interoperability at specific domain or policy level.²¹⁷ It should support the Union entities working on solutions relevant for cross-border interoperability of trans-European digital public services, for example on semantic interoperability for data spaces portability and reusability.²¹⁸ The Board should interact with all relevant Union entities in order to ensure alignment and synergies between cross-border interoperability actions and sector specific ones.”

The regulation might be relevant to the nodes as “public sector bodies”²¹⁹ that regulate, provide, manage or implement trans-European digital public services. What is considered a “public service” will need to be investigated by the 1+MG NCP, as this will be defined at the national level.²²⁰

Being a “public sector body” would seem to have implications for interoperability requirements on the data for the ODD, DGA, eIDAS2, and the EHDS. Since the Genome EDIC will be responsible for the Data Governance, they must understand how each node would potentially need to follow the requirements in the IEA.

We state the definition of “public sector body” again here to avoid cross-references:

“the State, regional or local authorities, bodies governed by public law or associations formed by one or more such authorities, or one or more such bodies governed by public law;

‘bodies governed by public law’ means bodies that have the following characteristics:

- *they are established for the specific purpose of meeting needs in the general interest, and do not have an industrial or commercial character;*
- *they have legal personality;*
- *they are financed, for the most part, by the State, regional or local authorities, or other bodies governed by public law, are subject to management supervision by those authorities or bodies, or have an administrative, managerial or supervisory board, more than half of whose members are appointed by the State, regional or local authorities, or by other bodies governed by public law;*

²¹⁶ IEA Rec. 47

²¹⁷ IEA Rec. 47

²¹⁸ IEA Rec. 47

²¹⁹ Data Governance Act shares this definition

²²⁰ IEA, Art. 1(3), “This Regulation applies without prejudice to the competence of Member States to define what constitutes public services or to their ability to establish procedural rules for or to provide, manage or implement those services.”

Should the Genome EDIC or (more likely) its nodes be considered a “public sector body”, we consider next other definitions of the IEA that will be key to understanding how it could affect data governance requirements:

The IEA defines “‘cross-border interoperability’ as the ability of Union entities and public sector bodies of Member States *to interact with each other across borders* by sharing data, information and knowledge through digital processes in line with the legal, organisational, semantic and technical requirements related to such cross-border interaction.”²²¹

The scope of ‘trans-European digital public services’ extends to “digital services provided by Union entities or public sector bodies to one another or to natural or legal persons in the Union, and requiring interaction across Member State borders, among Union entities or between Union entities and public sector bodies, by means of their network and information systems.”²²²

IEA Recital 6 sheds light on what is included in “digital public services”: Trans-European digital public services should include the key public services as defined in the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030²²³, covering “essential services such as health data, including pandemic and vaccination certificates, access to single window systems, the exchange of information related in general all those services that implement the ‘once-only’ principle to access and exchange cross-border data.”

The Interoperable Europe Act introduces requirements for common specifications mandating adoption of standardized approaches to facilitate data exchange by establishing technical rules that enable different systems to communicate. Open standards and specifications should avoid proprietary technologies which might impede or at least complicate information exchange. The Commission will publish Interoperable Europe solutions and the European Interoperable Framework [EIF] on the “Interoperable Europe portal”, by electronic means, in formats that are open, machine-readable.²²⁴ This “portal” is going to be a “single point of entry for information related to cross-border interoperability of trans-European digital public services.”²²⁵

²²¹ IEA Art. 2(1)

²²² ‘Network and information system’ is defined in NIS2 (EU) 2022/2555 Art. 6(1): “(1) ‘network and information system’:

(a) an electronic communications network as defined in Article 2, point (1), of Directive (EU) 2018/1972;
(b) any device or group of interconnected or related devices, one or more of which, pursuant to a programme, carry out automatic processing of digital data; or
(c) digital data stored, processed, retrieved or transmitted by elements covered under points (a) and (b) for the purposes of their operation, use, protection and maintenance;”

²²³ Decision (EU) 2022/2481

²²⁴ IEA Art. 5(1)

²²⁵ IEA Art. 8(1)

“The EIF shall provide a model and a set of recommendations for legal, organisational, semantic and technical interoperability as well as for its governance, that are addressed to all entities falling within the scope of this Regulation for the purpose of facilitating interactions among each other through their network and information systems.”²²⁶

The Genome EDIC and its 1+MG NCP to operate with the EHDS (for example as an authorised participant as discussed in the section on EHDS above) would need to develop its data governance taking into account the standards of the interoperability framework that will be developed. Their architecture must support secure cross-border data sharing capabilities while incorporating interoperability standards specifically designed for an appropriate level of security.

Now we look at the last legislation in this section, that may not be immediately relevant to the cybersecurity of the Genome EDIC or 1+MG NCP, however, it is worth at least an introduction and short analysis related to software tool development.

Medical Devices Regulation

Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on Medical Devices (MDR), lays down rules concerning the placing on the market, making available on the market or putting into service of medical devices for human use and accessories for such devices in the Union.

A medical device is “any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes:

- (1) diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease,
- (2) diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability,
- (3) investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state,
- (4) providing information by means of in vitro examination of specimens derived from the human body, including organ, blood and tissue donations (...).”²²⁷

The ELSI working group has considered how the MDR might apply, and we use that as a contribution for our analysis here.²²⁸ The Genome EDIC will act as a controller by disclosing data, this in itself would not be considered a “medical purpose.”

²²⁶ IEA Art. 5(2)

²²⁷ MDR Art. 2(1)

²²⁸ From the document “EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC” by GDI ELSI Working Group meeting, May 2025

The Genome EDIC may provide tools to support the user in designing their own software (e.g., creation of an AI model to be used on patients in a hospital); in such cases, the MDR would not apply, as the EDIC would simply host software being developed by a third party (the user).²²⁹ Next we quote the analysis of the ELSI group to avoid any misinterpretation:

“Whenever the EDIC provides the users with tools in the healthcare reuse track, and such tools aim to support the user in analysing the genomic data for medical diagnostics or patient care (e.g., statistics about the treatments provided, visualisation tools for clinicians) or in interpreting genomic data for medical decision-making, then software developed and provided by the EDIC might qualify as medical devices under MDR insofar as they would support the interpretation of the data by the user and have an influence on the decision of the clinician. But even this seems a step away from creating a medical device.”

It would seem then that the data platform provided by the EDIC would be outside the scope of the MDR, with perhaps an exception of potentially the tools engaged for the data use in the healthcare reuse track. As with all the other legislations herein discussed, once more is understood about the nature of the tools, the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCP are recommended to consult the MDR to check for obligations in case they will develop a device (i.e. software) that could be used “for a medical purpose” and such device would be “placed on the market”. We take the opportunity to remind the consortium that they should check the terms of the Cyber Resilience Act regarding any development of products with digital elements, including online tools or other software if the MDR does not apply. Where software might not fall under the MDR, maybe it could fall under the CRA or EHR component, if it has such a purpose.

Conclusion on legal analysis: create a comprehensive cybersecurity strategy and check national laws

With the MDR we conclude our review of the individual legislations that have legal roles with corresponding cybersecurity duties, where the Genome EDIC or the 1+MG NCP might fall within their scope. While it is not possible to “volunteer” to comply with certain legislations, for example, CER, NIS2, CRA, it is possible to study what they have in common to guarantee the confidentiality, integrity and availability of data. The laws analysed above should be reviewed carefully for their similar cybersecurity measures, incident response measures and/or data interoperability practices. This will guide the creation of a comprehensive cybersecurity strategy and data governance plan to be used by Genome EDIC and its nodes, that will be valid and consistent (at least in part) even if the applicability of certain laws changes over time.

We remind the 1+MG NCP that they must check their national implementations of the directives CER and NIS2, and any national variations under the GDPR for health data processing, which can be stricter to understand how they might have duties for

²²⁹ Ibid.

cybersecurity based on their legal roles under those legislations. This can be judged only taking into consideration the entities' activities and nature of their legal roles at a national level, for example, as part of a health care structure, or special processing environment, or trusted execution environment, or other digital / health infrastructure.

In the next few years, there will be a coalescence of legal and technological events in the EU health sector, cybersecurity or certification schemes. Much of this has been anticipated in the legal analysis above where it was mentioned several times that the EC will publish implementation acts with details on technical measures that will need to be adopted in order to comply with EU legislation, such as eIDAS2, or EHDS or IEA. The Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP will need to update themselves regularly.

Next, we take a step back from the detailed laws and look more at cybersecurity management at a European level with a closer look at cybersecurity efforts for supply chains and the healthcare sector. This is to encourage looking up and down the digital elements supply chain and inform the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP of available ENISA guidance on cybersecurity and developments related to certification schemes for cybersecurity.

Supply chain security and ENISA guidance

In this section we consider broader issues in cybersecurity, not just from specific legislations, but more in their application all together, including the guidance that is ongoing from Europe's cybersecurity agency ENISA.

Cybersecurity of supply chains

This section considers the legal requirements that aim to shore up supply chain security. This would be important to the EDIC and nodes in its design phase and earliest risk assessment of its software, hardware and services, both provided and sourced.

Multi-country projects like those that successfully achieve the status of EDIC should aim to mitigate vulnerabilities and dependencies coming from their digital supply chains in order to enhance their resilience.²³⁰

We have also seen that the CRA provides for requirements for placing on the market products with digital elements to also ensure that cybersecurity is taken into account throughout each product's supply chains, making final products with digital elements and their components more secure.²³¹ Emphasizing the importance of vulnerabilities introduced via supply chains, the NIS2 sets out cybersecurity risk-management measures (for "essential and important entities") for supply chain security measures that require the use of products with digital elements meeting stricter cybersecurity requirements than even those laid down

²³⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-decade-projects>. Accessed 20/05/2025

²³¹ CRA Rec. 10

in the CRA Regulation.²³² The Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP should aim for a comprehensive awareness of these supply chain security risks and procure digital products and services accordingly.

ENISA Cybersecurity efforts to support NIS2 implementation

ENISA, European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, published in June 2025 its “Technical Implementation Guidance” for NIS2.²³³ We strongly recommend to the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP to review this guidance. It maps security requirements, good industry practices, European and international standards, and national frameworks. This covers guidance and implementation of a policy on the security of network and information systems, risk management policy, incident handling, supply chain security, security in network and information systems acquisition, development and maintenance, policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures, and basic cyber hygiene practices and security training.²³⁴ Regardless of whether NIS2 will apply to the Genome EDIC or the 1+MG NCP, it is helpful reading for guidance.

ENISA also released its NIS360 report looking specifically at the success (or struggle in some cases) of NIS2 implementation across critical sectors in the EU, including health and ICT service management. Regarding ENISA’s investigation, scope into the health sector covered hospitals, healthcare providers, EU reference laboratories, research and development entities for medicinal products, pharmaceutical manufacturers, and manufacturers of medical devices. The report emphasizes that for the sector, the *diversity* of the range of these types of health-sector entities, devices, and technologies, is a source of significant cybersecurity challenges²³⁵.

The Commission will be supporting the sector by preparing a European Action Plan on the cybersecurity of hospitals and healthcare providers.²³⁶ This will include concrete actions for securing data processing in hospitals and healthcare providers, which act as both providers and users of health data in the EHDS. It is planned to include safeguards in relation to log-in and identification management in electronic health record systems or the reuse of data in secure processing environments.”²³⁷

This action plan builds on NIS2 requirements and addresses vulnerabilities unique to the health sector with tailored improvements addressing those gaps. This might be useful for

²³² CRA Rec. 13, NIS2 Art. 3

²³³ ENISA, 2025. "Technical implementation guidance on Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/2690 of 17 October 2024 laying down rules for the application of NIS2 Directive as regards technical and methodological requirements of cybersecurity risk-management measures" June 2025, version 1.0. doi:10.2824/2702548.

²³⁴ Ibid. From “Executive Summary.”

²³⁵ ENISA NIS360 2024, ENISA Cybersecurity Maturity & Criticality Assessment of NIS2 sectors, February 2025, ISBN 978-92-9204-687-3, DOI: 10.2824/1378797

²³⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/cybersecurity-hospitals-and-healthcare-providers>, Accessed 29/05/2025

²³⁷ “Questions and answers on cybersecurity of hospitals and healthcare providers”, Jan 15. 2025, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_25_263, Accessed 29/05/2025

the EDIC's decentralized infrastructure to follow so its development is coherent with ENISA recommendation and the EU Action Plan, seeing that both are moving with an eye toward tomorrow's EHDS implementation. We will watch for updates on this Action Plan since it could be relevant to follow as potential support to aid the transition to the EHDS for health data users (like hospitals), which it is assumed at this stage, will be interfacing with the Genome infrastructure's resources and platform.

Conclusion on Work Accomplished

This deliverable performed the assessment of the consequences of cybersecurity law on the setup of the Genomic EDIC's infrastructure. It analysed the legal roles from various EU legislations and the corresponding cybersecurity duties for those roles that might apply to the Genome EDIC and or to the 1+MG NCP.

It also offered an overall assessment of the consequences of cybersecurity law for both the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG National Coordination Points. Still, which legislations would apply to the Genome EDIC is going to be an ongoing evaluation. We provide in this deliverable the analysis for the Genome or its 1+NCP to study themselves. A wise approach could be to prepare for compliance in a broad manner, taking the "best practices" (like just mentioned for NIS2 from ENISA) for high data quality, cybersecurity, interoperability and data portability on board that we see repeated in various legislations.

Section 4 broadly covers the principal legislations on cybersecurity in the EU. With this cybersecurity impact assessment we hope to raise awareness of the different laws, their overlapping terms, the gaps between them, and the complexity of application to the decentralized infrastructure and nodes. As each new aspect, component, tool or service is designed, an analysis of the impact on cybersecurity rules and duties should be conducted.

In the next section, "Results" we provide a summary of the applicability of the legislations reviewed, the cybersecurity roles corresponding to those laws, and the duties for the Genome EDIC.

Annex 1 offers a quick reference chart for mapped roles to be used as it is by Genome EDIC or its 1+NCPs or by any other entity acknowledging to fall in one of the legal roles in column B.

5. Results

We present in a condensed fashion the legislative analysis which focuses on the laws that give cybersecurity duties and interoperability requirements that the Genome EDIC and its 1+MG NCP may fall within for a variety of potential legal roles. The assertive style in the following relies on the previous analysis.

Please note that D2.8 is devoted to mapping the cybersecurity roles for the Genome EDIC. Yet, the analysis, where possible, has mapped the needs also of the 1+MG NCPs making this deliverable.

<p>CER Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Not likely for Genome EDIC. It seems that the Genome EDIC itself would not qualify as a “critical entity” for the purposes of CER obligations since it does not fall within the “health sector” or “digital infrastructure” as described in the Annex of the CER.</p> <p>However, the 1+MG NCPs as individual nodes may fall under CER in the national implementations, and therefore each one must check based on the function of the 1+MG NCP and that national implementation of CER.</p>
<p>Legal roles</p>	<p>Critical entity</p> <p>Critical entity of Particular European Significance - If the Critical Entity provides the same or similar essential services to or in six or more Member States & formally notified it falls into this category (per Art. 17 (3)).</p>

<p>NIS2 Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Not likely for Genome EDIC. NIS2 applies only to certain sectors, which the Genome EDIC itself does <i>not</i> seem to fall within, namely healthcare, digital infrastructure (as listed in Annex I), or research organization (as listed in Annex II). See the commentary below for the sector-specific analysis.</p> <p>However, we raise the possibility that the individual nodes (1+MG NCP) could fall within NIS2’s scope based on their entity’s services in healthcare or because of services offered by IT facilities.²³⁸ A node– by– node analysis should be done to check for NIS2 applicability at a national level.</p>
<p>Legal roles</p>	<p>Essential & important entities</p> <p>Management bodies (of essential and important entities)</p>

<p>GDPR Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Yes, the GDPR would apply to the Genome EDIC and its nodes, eventually as a controller, joint controller, and processor according to the final data governance and data flow options.</p> <p>The specific legal role of the Genome EDIC (e.g., as a potential joint controller) needs to be clarified.</p> <p>For the interim implementation, the controllership for data disclosure remains in the country.</p>
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²³⁸ We align here with the analysis from the “GDI legal analysis -EU regulations applicable to Genome EDIC:” “However, the situation may be different on the national level. As the secure processing environment are services that will be provided by the national nodes... They may offer their IT infrastructure as computer service outside secondary use. They may also have a direct role for primary healthcare.”

	<p>Consent (dynamic data subject consent) will be the legal basis for disclosure.</p> <p>Other options for legal basis different from consent will remain possible.</p>
Legal roles	<p>Controller (and joint controller)</p> <p>Processor</p> <p>Data subject</p>

<p>EHDS Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Yes, the Genome EDIC is aiming to be an authorised participant of the EHDS as its long-term sustainability goal. The 1+MG NCP could also potentially be health data holders or data users. It will depend on the internal organization at NCP level.</p> <p>The various implementation regulations for cybersecurity and data interoperability specifications will be published by the Commission by 26 March 2027, including its platform for Secondary Use, HealthData@EU. The Genome EDIC and nodes should align its data governance with the adoption of the European Digital Health Wallet, and the rest of eIDAS2 that will be used for access, identification and authentication mechanisms.</p> <p>The rules and definitions for EHR and components could become relevant depending on how the Genome EDIC and 1+MG NCP develop the ICT tools and/or portal.</p>
Legal roles	<p>Authorised participant</p> <p>Controller / joint controller / processor</p> <p>Health data holder / trusted health data holder</p> <p>Health data user</p> <p>Manufacturer /importer / distributor of EHR system or EHR components</p> <p>SPE</p>

<p>CRA Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>The applicability of the CRA to the 1+MG IT infrastructure cannot be determined yet. This law will need close analysis on tools / software / network and information systems to be developed and whether digital products are ‘placed on the market’. The legal analysis will need to be reconsidered at various decision points before the software and hardware tools are developed and services designed or eventually put into use at later stages. Still this analysis will help to look up and down</p>
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	<p>the supply chain for ITC components, including software, and to perform cybersecurity analysis to cover information required to the end-user.</p> <p>Genome EDIC and its 1+MG NCP or other entities that will develop EHR system or system components can develop their cybersecurity, documentation, and technical requirements, and incident reporting requirements in a comprehensive manner, taking into account even possible similar or overlapping duties that might come up under NIS2 as part of a digital supply chain to critical entities.</p>
<p>Legal roles</p>	<p>Manufacturer</p> <p>Importer</p> <p>Distributor</p> <p>- A person who substantially modifies a product with digital elements and makes that product available on the market, shall be considered to be a manufacturer for the purposes of this Regulation.</p> <p>Open-source software steward</p> <p>User</p>

<p>CA Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>The Cybersecurity Act is to be read together with the CRA in case 1+MG IT infrastructure will be deemed a manufacturer or provider of certified ICT products, services or processes. See articles 54- 56 on duties of manufacturers or providers of ICT products covered by a certification scheme.</p> <p>The CA gives the mandate to ENISA and is a legal framework that sets out basic EU cybersecurity definitions. Being a fundamental start to EU Cybersecurity regulation and risk assessment, it must be understood well and paired in analysis with all these other legislations.</p>
<p>Legal roles</p>	<p>Manufacturer or provider of ICT products, services or processes</p>

<p>eIDAS2 Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>Yes, this will apply indirectly to the EDIC if the EDIC or the individual natural or legal persons use the authentication mechanisms, electronic signatures, trust services, EDIW set up by this law. The EHDS also sets out requirements for access management per EIDAS2.</p>
<p>Legal roles for the digital wallet (EDIW)</p>	<p>User</p> <p>Relying Party</p>

EU Data Act Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes	Yes, data governance requirements for Genome EDIC's data interoperability and data portability are likely to apply. Different parts of the DA apply based on private or public sector body. This could also apply to 1+MG NCP.
Legal roles	Data holder Data recipient NOT public sector body (private sector) Public sector body Provider of a digital processing service (as a public sector body)

DGA Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes	<p>How the DGA might apply to the EDIC Genome is unclear. Its rules can apply to public sector bodies, data intermediation service providers, and operators of Secure Processing Environments. If the EDIC Genome might be a public sector body, then the DGA requires processing to be done in a SPE, which would require cybersecurity practices to be in place. If Genome EDICS moves into being registered as a data altruistic organization the DGA would apply with all the analyzed consequences in terms of cybersecurity requirements.</p> <p>The DGA regulates data re-use in some circumstances. The cybersecurity responsibilities are generally like the GDPR (appropriate technical and organizational measures).</p>
Legal roles	Public sector body Body governed by public law Data intermediation service providers Data altruism organisation (Data processors and controllers fall under GDPR rules)

IEA Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes	IEA applies rules to trans-European digital public services. It is not yet clear if the Genome EDIC or its nodes will be considered public sector bodies that regulate, provide, manage or implement trans-European
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	<p>digital public services. If yes, Genome EDIC would need to develop standardized interfaces as specified by the interoperability framework.</p> <p>Looking at its requirements related to cybersecurity measures, it does not seem to add any particular security requirements that would not otherwise be imposed by NIS2, GDPR, or EHDS.</p>
Legal roles	<p>Public sector body</p> <p>Bodies governed by public law</p>

<p>MDR</p> <p>Application to Genome EDIC and/or nodes</p>	<p>It would seem then that the data platform provided by the EDIC would be outside the scope of the MDR. The provision of data to a user would not demonstrate that using the data by itself is for a ‘medical purpose’.</p> <p>Perhaps there could be an exception of potentially the tools engaged for the data use in the healthcare reuse track but not based on currently available information for planning of the Genome EDIC.</p>
Legal roles	<p>Manufacturer, importer or distributor who places on the market, making available on the market or putting into service of medical devices for human use and accessories for such devices in the Union.</p>

6. Discussion

The discussion of the analysis performed under this deliverable is performed for obvious reasons of efficacy and usability along the various subsections. A more summarised discussion is, however, present under the next section and summarized for roles mapping under Annex 1.

7. Conclusions & Impact

This assessment of the consequences of cybersecurity law on the setup of the Genome EDIC's IT infrastructure hopes to reach 3 main results, all of which have a significant impact on the project and on its relevant stakeholders. Along with the assessment of the consequences of cybersecurity law, it has mapped the main requirements deriving from cybersecurity related legislations for the possible entities and roles within the Genome EDIC offering a blueprint and a method also in case of changes in the role's allocation and for “new” entities entering the Genome EDIC. As a third goal, we hope this public deliverable would expand its reach and impact beyond the participant stakeholders contributing significantly to raise legal awareness of cybersecurity duties, how they can overlap and how they can be addressed in a comprehensive cybersecurity strategy.

This deliverable has been structured in a way to remain useful and impactful for both Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCPs (more in general for entities participating in the EDIC).

We reviewed each major cybersecurity regulation to understand what roles might apply to the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCPs. We discussed the cybersecurity related duties that are attached to those roles and pointed out important differences and similarities.

The legal analysis has been summarized in short tables by the legislation reviewed.

The consortium should keep in mind that these conclusions are based on what we can loosely expect of the design and purpose of Genome EDIC, the 1+MG NCP, and MG+ IT infrastructure. Still the mapping of the legal roles remains valid along with the policy consideration suggested. This way both the Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCPs need only to check under their respective applicable national law the legal roles they are in to identify their actual duties.

This way, even if there is a significant change in the data governance structure both Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCPs will need only to check under the relevant applicable national legislation whether or not they fall in one of the legal roles listed in Annex 1 and refer to the corresponding legal analysis above to kick start their cybersecurity compliance.

Cybersecurity measures evolve.

The technologies, encryption standards, and protocols are constantly updated to remain at the state of the art. The first key point is to design a strategy to prevent a cybersecurity incident. For the variety of entities to which these legislations apply, the key is that cybersecurity protection measures must be proportionate to the risk of a security incident, reviewed periodically or when there is an important change, and updated to stay ever ahead of the risk. This is known as a risk-based approach, reflected in industry standards, like ISO27001 or NIST Cybersecurity Framework 2.0. It is advisable to design a comprehensive cybersecurity approach that, for instance, meets the record keeping duties under the GDPR, that are adequate to demonstrate the compliance duties under other legislations where applicable (e.g. CER, NIS2, EHDS, etc.), and at the same time provides to the 1+MG NCP uniform guidance.

The second key point is how to react to a cybersecurity incident. Depending on which legislation is triggered, NIS2, GDPR, or CRA, for example, there are different reporting and incident management protocols with different authorities and timelines. The Genome EDIC and the 1+MG NCPs can take advantage of the similarities to align and harmonise the response strategies and insert them in a single Information Security Management System.

We have seen in the legislative review that many requirements on cybersecurity, documentation, interoperability, and incident prevention and response overlap. It would be a best practice to adopt a cybersecurity strategy that considers the multiple legislations' cybersecurity requirements to align a common strategy, ensuring a more comprehensive implementation and a faster reaction and reporting in the event of an incident.

Going forward, the Genome EDIC must regularly review how these legal roles and corresponding cybersecurity duties may apply to its infrastructure, and the 1+MG NCPs need to check how they may fall within CER, NIS2, GDPR, EHDS, etc. depending on the functions, nature and structure of their node structures. We have seen that many of these laws are

recent. The implementation acts that will provide detailed standards and technical details on cybersecurity measures, data interoperability, etc. are going to be available in the next several months or couple of years. The Genome EDIC and all its entities must keep an eye on these cybersecurity and interoperability specifications so that it evolves to be ready for the EHDS, NIS2, and CER, eIDAS2, CRA, etc. in case they apply.

Our discussion moves beyond the scope of the deliverable (“Assessment of the consequences of cybersecurity law on the setup of the Genome EDIC's IT infrastructure”) in terms of mapping of legal roles and requirements and participation in the Genome EDIC offering insight for managing such an impact. Accordingly, several avenues to maximize the synergies among compliance requirements across different legislations (legal roles) that might apply to different roles in EDIC are offered.

These synergies range from the rather obvious conclusions that Genome EDIC should envisage the role of Chief Information Security Officer (CISO) to more concrete avenues to turn demanding compliance requirements into opportunities for simplification.

A clear example is offered by DPIAs as opportunities for the controller to create a single document where to coalesce technical and organizational measures not only required by the GDPR rules but also by other relevant legislations. At more general level, this could be done with a uniform methodology, shareable with guidelines from the Genome EDIC to the 1+MG NCP and possibly, if eventually agreed, common best practices shared with the dedicated Health Data Access Bodies, if created by member states on how to cope with different applicable duties. As mentioned in our analysis, such an approach can be aligned and combined with the fulfilment of the requirements under NIS2 or CER, for instance, and streamlined along with a comprehensive Information Security Management System aligned with ISO 27001.

In any event, it will prove advantageous for each cybersecurity strategy adopted by the Genome EDIC and/or 1+MG NCP to be part of comprehensive planning, addressing the overlapping, or similar duties and to streamline implementation.

With reference to the potential participation in the EHDS ecosystem as authorised participant, we stressed the importance the Genome EDIC creates its cybersecurity practices and data governance rules for itself and its 1+MG NCP to be compatible with the requirements that will be published in the implementing acts from the Commission providing the security and data governance for being an authorised participant. Similarly, it will be important for Genome EDIC in developing its data governance to keep aligned with requirements for security and technical measures in the SPEs in the EHDS that will eventually be published.

Overall, the discussion of each relevant legislation and of the EHDS components should drive the consortium into thinking about how these legal rules and components could impact cybersecurity expanding eventually the attack surface via attack vectors. The attack surface, or vector, for cybersecurity vulnerability expands with each interaction with the digital infrastructure. This is especially relevant to be considered when planning for the IT infrastructure design to be eventually integrated as part of the EHDS.

The NCPs might be organized to coordinate several trusted health data holders emphasizing the variability of organizational options. This deliverable suggests ensuring a unique policy and a unique SPE at national level. This approach might lead to coordinated results at national and EU levels - via the Genome EDIC - for which this deliverable will prove useful in quickly identifying cybersecurity implications once any participating entity or organization matches itself with the legal roles in Annex 1.

There is an interesting point here to connect to the GDPR roles of processor and controllers for those participants eventually aiming at becoming the “trusted health data holder”. The “trusted health data holder” shall be deemed a controller for its processing of personal electronic health data related to the provision of electronic health data to the health data user pursuant to a data permit or a health data request. The trusted health data holder shall be deemed to act as a processor on behalf of the health data user when providing data through a secure processing environment.

Also, assuming the possibility of IoT to be embedded in the operation of the Genome EDIC , our analysis has investigated existing and proposed sectoral EU legislation addressing challenges and duties to secure IoT devices and even its supply chain under the CRA and NIS2, at least, to the extent NIS2 and CRA work together to cover cybersecurity regulatory gaps for products with digital elements.

This deliverable also concluded that if the Genome EDIC were to rely on open-source software developed by third parties, or in collaboration with such third parties, the Cyber Resilience Act may not apply at all to Genome EDIC. However, since it is expected that the EDIC will operate a secure portal for the nodes or other software tools, it is recommended at the earliest planning stages to check with CRA terms for applicability.

The actual applicability of some legislations examined could not be determined in a clear way since it requires a close analysis on tools / software / network and information system to be developed. For instance, it is the case of the applicability of the CRA to the 1+MG IT infrastructure. Still, this deliverable paves the way for the other WPs and in general for those called to develop them for their own legal analysis before the software and hardware tools will be developed and services designed or eventually put into use at later stages. The analysis performed in D2.8 will help to explore the supply chain for ITC components, including software, and to perform a cybersecurity analysis to cover information required to the end-user.

Last but not least our conclusions offer a simple caveat specific to 1+MG NCPs: they must check their national implementations of the directives CER and NIS2, and any national variations under the GDPR for health data processing, which can be stricter to understand how they might have duties for cybersecurity based on their legal roles under those legislations and as mapped in Annex 1. To do so, they must consider the activities and nature of their legal roles at a national level, for example, as part of a health care structure, or special processing environment, or trusted execution environment, or other digital / health infrastructure.

8. Next steps

There are no envisaged further steps for this deliverable, that is final. Nevertheless, it will certainly impact and serve as a reference point at least for D2.3, D2.4, D2.5, D2.7, D2.9, D2.12.

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 Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 (Digital Markets Act)
 Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 (Digital Services Act)
 Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (NIS2 Directive)
 Directive (EU) 2022/2557 (Resilience of Critical Entities)
 Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (Data Act)
 Regulation (EU) 2024/903 (Interoperable Europe Act)
 Regulation (EU) 2024/1183 (European Digital Identity Framework)
 Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (Cyber Resilience Act)
 Regulation (EU) 2025/38 (Cyber Solidarity Act)
 Regulation (EU) 2025/327 (European Health Data Space).

Annex 1 to D2.8: Roles Matching

A	B	C
Legislation	Legal role	Entity Role
(EU) 2024/1183 (EIDAS2)	Relying party	Genome EDIC / 1+MG NCP
	User	Genome EDIC / 1+MG NCP
(EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)	Controller	Genome EDIC / 1+MG NCP
	Joint - controller	Genome EDIC / 1+MG NCP
	processor	Genome EDIC/ 1+MG NCP
	Data subject	Individual workers, researchers, users of access credentials, health care professionals
(EU) 2022/868 (DGA)	Public sector body	1+MG NCP
	SPE?	1+MG NCP
(EU) 2022/2555 (NIS2)	Essential entities	1+MG NCP if health sector

		1+MG NCP if digital infrastructure
	Important entities	1+MG NCP if research organization
(EU) 2022/2557 (CER)	Critical entity	1+MG NCP if health sector under national implementations
(EU) 2023/2854 (Data Act)	Public sector body	1+MG NCP
(EU) 2024/903 (Interoperable Europe Act)	Public sector body	1+MG NCP
(EU) 2024/2847 (Cyber Resilience Act) And (EU) 2019/881 (CA)	Manufacturer or provider of ICT products, services or processes	
	User	
(EU) 2025/327 (European Health Data Space)	Public sector body	1+MG NCP
	SPE	1+MG NCP
	Manufacturer EHR	
	Authorised participant	Genome EDIC
	Health data holder	1+MG NCP
	Trusted health data holder	
	Health data user	1+MG NCP
	Health professional	
	Health care provider	
	Health institution	